

**“Influence of environmental CSR on Employer Branding in
Pakistan’s Telecom Sector”**

By

Ahmad Awais Butt

Research Supervisor: Dr. Bidit Dey

A thesis submitted to University of the West of Scotland for the degree of Doctor
of Business Administration (DBA)

School of Business and Enterprise

University of the West of Scotland, London Campus

2021

Declaration

I hereby declare that this research work and thesis is entirely my own work and has not been the subject of submission in any other institution. I also confirm that the research and papers used have been properly referenced.

Acknowledgement

I want to thank Almighty Allah for giving me motivation, courage, emotional and mental stability for completing this research journey. I would like to thank my supervisor Dr. Bidit Dey for his valuable guidance and critique.

Thank You !

Abstract

Environment has been largely ignored in the implementation of Corporate Social Responsibility concept in the developing world. For activating employees as key stakeholders, it is imperative to create awareness about their potential role towards enforcing environmental CSR via employer branding. This study is about investigating the influence being exhibited by millennial employees' perception about environment driven CSR practices, on the employer branding of telecom sector companies operating in Pakistan. This study is first of its kind in the developing country context of Pakistan in where environmental side of CSR has been explored. Pakistan is experiencing serious environmental challenges especially air pollution and degradation, and this study intends to raise awareness among millennials about social responsibility of employers towards the environment.

Qualitative research method driven by multiple case study approach has been used in this study for addressing the research objectives and in parallel the interpretivist philosophy and inductive reasoning approach has been applied. The subjective opinion of millennial employees working in telecom companies was required to be extracted so that reality can be observed from the lens of different experiences and awareness level possessed by millennials. Five major companies (four MNCs and one local) are operating in the telecom sector of Pakistan, from which three companies were selected as sample including two MNCs and one local company. Semi-structured interviews have been used as data collection tool and thematic analysis method has been adopted for analysing the results.

Thirty interviews are conducted from millennials working in the three telecom companies with each interview consisting of 26 questions. It has been found that the understanding and awareness of millennial employees about environmental side of CSR is of very basic level and shallow, which has restricted their opinion about employer branding. Presence of moral and social identity among millennials has been found whereas, organizational identification is at minimum and stakeholder theory is not being adhered neither do any of the globally recognized CSR frameworks. Moreover, millennials are not receiving regular and clear communication about the CSR activities of their employers and work pressure faced by millennials keeps them distracted from CSR issues.

Socio-cultural factors of Pakistan, personal characteristics of millennials and disinterest from telecom companies are not allowing millennials to improve their awareness level about interplay of CSR and employer branding. It is recommendation is to develop a formal strategy for CSR, using social media communication for driving internal branding, plan individual initiatives and also join hands with government and non-government agencies for practically contributing towards environmental CSR and ultimately giving themselves a chance to achieve high employer branding in the eyes of millennials.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Employer Branding, Environment, Communication, Millennials, Stakeholders, Telecom, Pakistan, Employer Attractiveness, Social Identity, Morals, Culture, Multinational Corporations (MNCs), Awareness, Environmental Issues, Organizational Identification, CSR Reporting.

List of Abbreviations

CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
EOC	Employer of Choice
MNCs	Multi-National Corporations
ISO	International Standard Organization
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
UNDP	United Nations Development Program
ECSR	Environmental Corporate Social Responsibility
OIT	Organizational Identity Theory
IT	Information Technology

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1. Chapter One: Introduction

The organizational concepts to be undertaken and examined in this research study are contemporary in nature i.e., corporate social responsibility (CSR), environmental side of CSR (ECSR), employer branding and millennial generation employees (also referred as Generation Y). The interplay between environmental CSR and employer branding is to be undertaken in this study in the particular context of Pakistan's telecommunication (telecom) sector. Environment as a factor comes under the concept of CSR theoretically and needs attention in the field of academic research as a key constituent element of CSR. With its social, economic and political dimensions, CSR has emerged as a key concept in the last few decades covering developed and developing countries' context (Carroll, 1999; Jamali & Karam, 2016; Lenz et al, 2017). Concept of CSR has been discussed and evaluated extensively by academicians and practitioners in the contemporary literature as well (Lee and Choi, 2021; Bhardwaj et al, 2018).

CSR is a doorway towards positive reputation across consumer market and employment market which makes this concept worthy of research and discussion in this study (Carroll, 2020). This research study is about evaluating the importance of environmental corporate social responsibility (also referred as ECSR) concept for enhancing and maintaining employer branding. Employer branding embeds attractiveness of an employer and achieving a strong employer brand develops positive attitudes across potential and existing employees ultimately strengthening organizational performance (Ozcan and Elci, 2020; Matongolo et al, 2018). This study intends to evaluate the extent to which environmental ECSR practices can influence employer branding especially when opinion of millennial employees is being considered towards ECSR.

Whilst researchers have used several terms to address the concept i.e., "employer attractiveness", "recruitment image" or "employer brand image" (Kuchero and Samokish, 2016; Reis et al, 2021). This study uses the term "employer brand", defined as "the package of functional, economic and psychological benefits provided by employment, and identified with the employing company" (Ambler and Barrow, 1996).

This definition covers three distinct aspects which are all potentially relevant for employees especially as a package (Tkalac et al., 2016; Lu et al, 2020). Next section will provide a brief background of these concepts indicating their importance.

1.1 Research Background

The concept of employer brand holds importance primarily because of its impact on firm performance along with improved employee relations and employee retention (Gilani and Jamshed, 2017). An argument prevailing in literature provided a significant background for this study i.e., the willingness of employees to stay with their employer is positively influenced when employer branding is strong (Ambler and Barrow, 1996; Tanwar and Prasad, 2017). This research evidence is indicating the deeply embedded nature of employer branding concept. A key element of this study is the millennial generation employees, it is mentioned by authors that millennial generation is most sensitive about CSR and ethical issues (Connell et al, 2012; Dutta and Mishra, 2021). Millennial generation are the people born in or after 1982 (Cone Communications, 2015). Environment on its own as distinct factor has not been given sufficient attention in theory while determining the influence on employer branding (Santiago, 2019). Since, this study is focusing specifically on the environmental side of CSR, it is important to note here that, employees and environment have been highlighted by European Union (2008) CSR framework as key stakeholders for business organizations as depicted in the figure below:

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Figure 1 CSR Framework

Source: Based on European Union, (2011) Illustration

Singh and Verma, (2017) have stated that CSR is a prominent issue today for organizations and it is expected from businesses to invest in CSR practices and policies for showing their responsible behaviour towards the society in which they are doing business. Benefits have been identified by Key, (1995) and Tkalac and Coric, (2018) when organizations engage in CSR activities, in return they boost the morale and confidence of their employees which helps in enhancing their brand image. Researchers over the years have confirmed these benefits exists in the developing and developed countries' context (Carnahan et al, 2017; Balmer and Geysler, 2003; Martin et al, 2011). Image, standing, identity and goodwill are some synonymous used for reputation.

Hur et al, (2017) have argued that organizations are perceived by stakeholders in different ways which directs their perception about the image of the company. CSR gained more importance because for achieving reputation management, a central objective for organizations is to operate in a legitimate manner and it adds into the reasons why CSR is frequently considered as a strategic tool which helps organizations in fulfilling the stakeholders' expectations (Nayak et al, 2017). The relationship between CSR and employer branding is discussed considerably in the literature, however, how does this interplay work in developing countries context is not given much attention (Mahmood and Bashir, 2020).

Striving to become sustainable and socially responsible brands in today's globalized and technological driven business world can enable businesses to attract right talent which ultimately can provide benefits in terms of creating value (Azham and Ahmad, 2020). The importance of environment as a key element of CSR can be determined from the fact, that ISO and EU included environment in their CSR frameworks by laying emphasis on environment as a prominent force that shapes the standing of businesses (Buchanan et al, 2018). After developing a basic understanding and know-how of the key concepts involved in this study, next section will present problem statement which will reveal the scope of this study.

1.2 Problem Statement

This section is about specifying and describing the problem that is under consideration. Appropriate sources and citations have been used for evidencing the existence of the problem. Moreover, information has been presented which will extend the understanding of the readers regarding what is not known about the problem in the particular context.

The triangle of millennial employees, ECSR and employer branding in a developing country context reflects significantly about what is not known and what problem can exist. CSR and employer branding have been studied as separate constructs in the developing country context, however their interplay remains largely unexplored (Gupta et al, 2020).

The link between CSR and the attractiveness of the employer brand has been widely researched across the developed countries' context (Oliveiria et al, 2021, Ryan and Turner, 2021), however, to the best of researcher's knowledge, it has not incorporated employees' identification into this relation in a developing country's context. This link between ECSR and employer branding is an alien interplay that has not availed attention in Pakistan's context which is a major economy of the world. Therefore, in itself it indicates a problem that the underpinning and strong footing of ECSR is not prevailing across the developing country context of Pakistan.

A good number of multinational corporations (MNCs) are operating in Pakistan from few decades and more MNCs are entering this market which means from ECSR perspective a positive construct is expected to be added.

This point is more relevant, because the focus of this study is on telecom sector of Pakistan, and almost all the big companies operating in this industry are MNCs. Therefore, it needs to be known that how the existence of MNCs in telecom sector of Pakistan has shaped the link between ECSR and employer branding.

The crux of this study is the question posed, that exhibits how this triangle of millennial employees, ECSR and employer branding is shaping in Pakistan because in theory it must be forming adequately. Therefore, this study needs to know and explain how employees' identification working in a developing country Pakistan affects the relation between ECSR and the attractiveness of the employer brand.

In terms of evidence some classical and contemporary perspectives are being presented here for indicating the importance of this problem under consideration. Turban and Greening, (1996) in their study concluded that organizations by engaging in CSR activities tend to develop more attractiveness and employers are giving rise to the debate and further evaluation of this relationship. Younis and Hammad, (2021); and Schwaiger et al, (2021) have stated that organizational identification of the employees is imperative for generating improved employer branding i.e. organizational values should match with the values of the employees.

Ronda et al, (2018); Mohamad et al, (2018) have argued that organizations are increasingly focusing on hiring and attracting such employees who matches with the organizational values. This becomes crucial when big players in a market collide i.e., the quest of attracting talented and competent employees working in rival companies and other companies in the market (Dineen et al, 2019). Therefore, it gets important for organizations to project their brand as attractive for employees and CSR has been considered as a key factor that can assist organizations in doing so (Ahamad, 2019; Sharma and Prasad, 2018). Researchers have argued that an effective way of attracting and retaining employees for organizations is to engage in CSR practices (Kumar et al, 2021; Du et al, 2015; Lee et al, 2021). Moreover, the increasing level of awareness across societies is putting pressure on organizations to exhibit their socially responsible conduct for attracting best candidates (Greer and Hauptmeier, 2016).

Therefore, both from an employer and an employee's perspective, it needs to be known that how ECSR is playing a role in achieving or driving employer branding. Moreover, it becomes important to determine that what kind of mindset and perception millennial employees possess towards the employer branding and ECSR constructs.

There are studies that have explored how CSR affects the employer brand through an internal perspective (Kim et al, 2010; Lee, et al., 2012; Tanwar & Prasad, 2016). The importance of identification is also argued by Zerbini, (2017); and Sheehy and Farneti, (2021) who stated that implementing socially responsible policies tends to enhance employee commitment and it also allows people management to be sustainable for the organization.

Moreover, it can be observed here that if this problem question is not addressed then it can cause telecom sector employers in Pakistan to miss out on talented and competent employees who can add greater value for the organization. Also, if the problem question of this study is not addressed then it can also refrain telecom companies from achieving a committed employee base as well as positive reputation across variety of stakeholders. From employees' perspective, it gets important to determine, to what extent they give priority to environmental side of CSR when intending to apply for a job and how their identification with employer brand plays a role (Hosain, 2021). If this extent of priority and identification level is low, then it will need to be addressed by investigating the reasons behind and if it is at an appropriate level then it can be a motivating factor for the telecom companies in Pakistan. Moreover, the nature of identification possessed by millennial employees is important to be known by the telecom sector employers for effectively relating with them. After presenting problem statement of this research study, next section will present the theoretical issues underlying this study and will briefly indicate scope for more research.

1.3 Theoretical Issues

This section will present theoretical issues related to the research problem under consideration for the purpose of exhibiting a clear picture of what the issue is. Moreover, for getting closer to the truth and reality, it is important to identify and integrate the theoretical viewpoint which will make this research reliable.

The focus of CSR lies on nine important factors, which include governance, business relationships, ethics, value of product, employment policies, financial gains, transparency, and involvement of community and protection of environment (Statman, 2013). Environment has emerged as a key pillar of CSR in the last two decades especially with the emphasis paid by ISO and EU on this issue. Therefore, from a strategic perspective, it is important to know that whether telecom companies in Pakistan are using environmental side of CSR as a strategy to improve their attractiveness or they still need to divert their attention towards this aspect. Theoretical evidence demands from businesses to take environmental side of CSR seriously because it can be a critical success factor for companies, especially when millennial employees are being considered.

In the context of developing countries where environment needs more attention, the consideration of ECSR makes more sense. Internal and external factors can affect the relationship between employer branding and CSR which can vary from one organization to another (Turban & Greening, 1996; Bhattacharya et al, 2020; Fares & Palmaer, 2015). Employees and natural environment are significant examples of internal and external factors in this regard (Maon et al, 2017; Zainee and Puteh, 2020). In the context of millennial employees' perception and organizational identification, limited research evidence is available due to which the issues underpinned by this context are not known. The consideration of ECSR by employees working in developing country context is not extensively evaluated i.e., whether the identity of organization is important for millennials working in developing country context.

CSR is referred by researchers as a key organizational value which can generate identification among employees (Kim et al, 2010), however how this identification functions in a developing country context is not known. Moreover, in theory, millennial employees are supposed to take environmental issues more seriously hence influencing employer branding significantly. However, in practice how true and valid is this proposition in a developing country context needs to be investigated. Therefore, in theory organizations are supposed to give high priority to their employees being premier stakeholder and subsequently they should be aware of the role played by CSR in building their image and attractiveness as employer across employees. The purpose of this research is to demonstrate the connections between employer branding and ECSR which theoretically should positively exist.

However, the contextual factors can play their role and can compromise the validation of theoretical perspectives. Millennial employees as key stakeholders also need to be understood and on a theoretical level it needs to be evaluated that how millennial employees give preference to ECSR when selecting their employer. Employer branding exhibits the benefits that an organization can offer and is referred as a sustainable strategy for employers (Tsai et al, 2014). CSR performance is having a significant impact on the minds of employees for attracting them (Weisman, 2017; Lin et al, 2016).

However, what kind of CSR performance is being displayed by employers in a developing country and how it is attracting employees needs to be known. The replicability of these findings achieved by scholars and researchers can only be determined when assessed in the light of empirical evidence gathered from relevant context. Therefore, for reaching closer to the reality in the particular business context of Pakistan, this study needs to be conducted.

These studies are providing a theoretical understanding that poor employer branding restricts their ability to attract talented individuals from the market. However, for determining the replicability of same results in the context of Pakistan needs, a new study is required to be conducted for precisely knowing that whether this holds true for Pakistan or not. Klimkiewicz and Oltra, (2018) and Sierra et al, (2017) have argued that millennial employees tend to possess higher CSR-based employer attractiveness when they have favourable CSR attitude and highly engaged employees obtain information from employer branding about companies who are active in CSR practices. Therefore, for validating this basic theoretical perspective in a developing country context, the ECSR attitude of millennial employees in Pakistan is being analysed in this study. This study intends to evaluate the impact of environmental CSR as a key factor on employer branding which has been extensively studied in the past using traditional factors such as workplace environment's impact on employer branding.

ECSR activities in general impact on employer branding and advertising/recruitment process impact on employer branding. Limited evidence is available regarding investigating the impact of CSR (in terms of natural environment) on employer branding even in the developed country context. This reflects on the scope for more research and reconfirms the purpose of this research which is to evaluate relationship between employer branding and environmental CSR (ECSR). These theoretical constructs are indicating that CSR and employer branding are linked in more than one way which provides strong theoretical foundations for conducting this study in Pakistan's context so that clarity of replicability and truth can be obtained. Individual differences in the personality can influence the reaction of employees towards CSR initiatives (Barrick et al, 2013; Hendriks, 2016).

This overlap and the factor of individual differences are indicating strong theoretical elements which can certainly change the extent of influence that CSR generates on employer branding when considered in a different cultural and institutional environment settings. This section is indicating that few functions of employer branding are coinciding with the impacts of CSR in the context of employees. Therefore, this theoretical issue is intended to be discussed in this thesis.

1.4 CSR and Environmental Issues in Pakistan

The reason behind briefly providing the background about CSR in this section is the development of understanding that how CSR is being perceived across Pakistan. This background will provide a reference point that environmental side of CSR construct is expected to be comprehended across corporate segments of the country. Child labour issue occurred in Pakistan during the 1990s and this was the first time when Pakistan was exposed to the concept of corporate social responsibility (Awan et al, 2012). After this incidence, international and national agencies in Pakistan started working on the awareness of CSR. Despite of this incident, academic and professional literature pertaining to CSR concept is not sufficiently established in Pakistan. United Nations Development Program and Pakistan Centre of Philanthropy are some prominent institutions working in Pakistan for promoting CSR. Ray, (2000) conducted one of the first studies on CSR in Pakistan and found that child labour is a leading issue in this regard existing due to financial problems.

A report published by Sustainable Development Policy Institute, (2002) mentioned that natural disasters demand CSR focus in Pakistan and proactive response of businesses is missing in the country. Later on, a study conducted by Ahmad, (2006) indicated that a divergence on the CSR issue exists in Pakistan as 16 companies were included in this study. Corporate philanthropy and welfare were found as main focus of organizations' CSR activities. Restraining effect of companies' financial performance on CSR was also observed and more focus was being given to financial performance. Ahmad, (2006) observed that CSR in its true essence has just started to emerge as it exists across developed countries.

Later on, a study conducted by Ali et al, (2010) on CSR indicated that CSR activities in Pakistan's telecom industry does not possess a significant relationship with purchase intentions of customers. Recently, another study conducted by Butt, (2016) has concluded that CSR is positively influenced from religiosity, awareness, trust and purchase intentions of customers in Pakistan.

All these aforementioned studies and many other studies have examined the concept of CSR in Pakistan from different perspectives, however there was no study found in literature which considered the environmental side of CSR in Pakistan. However, it can be mentioned here that CSR concept is going through a process of development and understanding in Pakistan (as a developing country) which is an encouraging sign. Fundamental understanding about the construct of CSR concept does exist in Pakistan, and different national/ international agencies are operating in Pakistan for its implementation.

1.4.1 Environmental Issues and Policy in Pakistan

Environmental issues especially climate change has been a significant problem that Pakistan is facing from the last few decades. These issues are giving rise to several health-related problems which have been pointed out by World Health Organization. Below presented picture of the map is indicating that Pakistan is in the top 10 countries of the world that are most affected by extreme weather events in the last two decades.

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Figure 2 World Map of the Global Climate Rate Index 1998-2017

Source: German Watch, (2019)

Pakistan is facing water shortage as well which is a significant environment related issue. Zulfiqar, (2018) mentioned that 21 million people of Pakistan out of a total population of 207 million do not have clean water access and sustainable economic growth is being hindered due to water shortage. The operational causes including inadequate water management policies and resource utilization by the businesses in Pakistan are main reasons behind water crisis (Khan and Awan, 2020). Pakistan has been ranked 3rd in the world by the International Monetary Fund among countries where water shortage is present (Qureshi, 2020).

Air pollution is another key environmental issue faced by Pakistan which has increased consistently in the last decade. Given the worsening air pollution situation of Pakistan, environment protection agency of Pakistan has installed air quality monitors and have started issuing warning to the factories for adding pollution filters (Habib et al, 2021). A panel of top judges in Pakistan recently gave orders to the government for detailing their efforts towards managing the air pollution which shows the threatening nature of this issue.

Especially the urban cities where most industrial and business development has occurred, are facing deteriorating situation of air quality. A report published by Medical Journal Lancet in 2015 stated that approximately 22% of annual deaths are caused by air pollution in Pakistan (Shaikh and Tunio, 2018). Uncontrolled emissions, use of poor-quality fuel and other similar factors are contributing towards worsening air quality in Pakistan due to which “smog season” hits Pakistan every year from the month of October to December (Mohyidin, 2019). Government intervention and awareness campaigns by private sector have become inevitable for managing air pollution especially during smog period (Rehman, 2018). World Air Quality recently published a report containing the list of world’s most polluted countries which is presented below indicating Pakistan in the top 2 most polluted countries:

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at BBC, (2019) Pakistan pollution: Teens fight to save Lahore from toxic air Available online at: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/world-asia-50333327>

Figure 3 World’s most polluted countries

Source: BBC, (2019)

The statistics presented in this section are visibly indicating a poor situation of Pakistan in terms of environmental stability and conservation. Natural environment being a key stakeholder of the businesses needs to be taken care of and preserved.

It is the responsibility of big businesses along with government to engage in protecting the natural environment in which they are doing business. Therefore, it can be stated that conducting ECSR by businesses in Pakistan is imperative for managing the prevailing environmental issues in the country.

To accomplish sustainable development goals through institutionally strong legal, administrative, and technical frameworks, Pakistan's environmental policy is founded on a bottom-up, community-driven strategy (Government of Pakistan, 2015). As a direct consequence of Pakistan's participation in the 1972 Stockholm statement, Pakistan established its Federal Environment Ministry in 1975. The Environmental Preservation Act of 1997 was enacted in Pakistan to ensure that the country's natural resources would be protected, that pollution would be mitigated, that sustainable development would be encouraged, and for other purposes related to these aims. It encompasses a significant portion of Pakistan. On December 6, 1997, the Pakistan Environmental Protection Act came into effect, thereby putting an end to the Pakistan Environmental Protection Ordinance, which had been in force since 1983 (Government of Pakistan, 2015).

1.5 Relevance of Telecom Industry

The importance of Pakistan's telecommunications sector to the country's environmental situation is outlined below. This section gives background on the importance of the telecom sector to environmental sustainability and the type of institutional environment that influences the environmental CSR behaviour of telecom firms. The mobile phone business in Pakistan is rapidly expanding in importance. It is crucial to the economy and is changing the way businesses, governments, and regular people interact and share information. Pakistan's GDP growth is slowing, and the population is rising, therefore the digital ecosystem's contribution to the country's economic and social well-being in the form of new jobs, tax income, and greater productivity is more important than ever. In a study commissioned by the Global System for Mobile Communications Association (GSMA), the telecom industry was estimated to contribute \$16.7 billion, or 5.4% of GDP, yearly (The Express Tribune, 2019).

The introduction of innovative digital resources is radically transforming the way people in Pakistan live and work. In particular, the retail, transportation, and banking sectors demonstrate how digital platforms have become the primary point of access for a wide variety of public and commercial services. Pakistan still has a substantial "coverage gap" and lags behind peers in critical areas, despite the fact that mobile broadband⁶ accounts for fewer than five in ten mobile connections. Pakistan scored a 398 on the latest GSMA Mobile Connectivity Index, which is lower than the South Asian mean of 45.7. (Global Mobile Internet Speed Test, 2021).

The telecommunications industry is offering solutions to increase numeracy and literacy, as well as school enrolment among children of school age. The Jazz Smart School programme has been using mobile technology since 2017 to enhance the educational experience for both students and instructors. Performance dashboards have been established on a variety of digital platforms in an effort to enhance education and keep teachers responsible (Jazz Pakistan, 2019).

In addition, the Ministry of IT and Telecom, through the DigiSkills initiative, has established a no-cost online training platform to help people become ready for digital freelance jobs (Robinson, 2020).

The Pakistan Telecommunication Authority is responsible for enforcing rules and regulations in the country's telecommunications industry on behalf of the federal government, as stipulated by the Telecommunications Act of 1996. In order to cover the entire nation with their networks, cellular mobile providers, to name just one example, have installed 35,000 towers (Hassan, 2021). Tier 1 cities (those with populations above a million) are the economic hubs and primary revenue sources for the global telecommunications, IT, and allied sector. Despite being viable activity centres, Tier 2 (population 100,000-1,000,000) and Tier 3 (population 5,000-100,000) suffer from insufficient transmission lines and grid station electricity. Diesel Generators ¹² are essential to the operation of virtually all sectors of the telecommunications sector. The shift to renewable energy should be supported, but it should be done in a way that is gradual, industry-informed, and socially responsible.

Role of Pakistan Telecommunication Authority (PTA)

PTA, in its role as regulator of the telecom industry, is obligated to provide relevant information on licenced operators to environmental management and control agencies (Pakistan Telecommunication Authority, 2018). Operators are obligated to implement measures for cutting greenhouse gas emissions (GHG), pollution, and garbage in line with the standards set by several nations across the world. Long blackouts and electrical shortages continue to be an issue in Pakistan, especially in the country's rural areas.

Using solar power and other realistic options, we must systematically address the problem of providing backup energy for the nation's telecommunications infrastructure (Pakistan Telecommunication Authority, 2020). Diesel generators are widely used in the telecommunications and information and communication technology sectors, although it is expected that the industry will switch to alternative arrangements whenever viable alternatives become available.

According to the Telecommunication Policy 2015, the PTA is responsible for compiling active data from telecommunications operators and making it publicly available on the website, while provincial and federal agencies dealing with environmental and climate change are tasked with monitoring installed generators. The worldwide compliance with the Specific Absorption Rate (SAR) safety limitations for radio emissions guidelines is a significant achievement. This problem affects all forms of communication technology, including portable devices like cell phones. Pakistan has adopted the ICNIRP-recommended limits on radiation exposure.

Telecom Policy 2015 for Environmental Regulatory Framework

Spectrum trading is addressed under Section 9.7 of the Telecom Policy 2015. The following excerpts from the policy have been reproduced for the sake of clarity. Commitments to the Environment (Faisal, 2017). In coordination with licensees and federal and provincial environmental authorities, the PTA will establish an environmental regulatory framework for the sector that is in line with applicable laws, rules, and regulations.

Towards this goal, PTA will create a method for monitoring licensee performance within the existing environmental regulatory framework, focusing on the following areas: Renewable energy consumption, carbon dioxide emissions, and other air pollution sources caused by their operations include diesel and other kinds of electrical power generation. Preserving and restoring the environment following civil works e) Managing the recycling and disposal of electronic waste, toxic chemicals, and other dangerous items.

The performance of licensees in terms of the environment, as measured against predetermined goals, shall be made public by PTA via its website and other methods. When licensees fail to satisfy environmental standards, the relevant authorities will be informed. The PTA will announce commendations for businesses that have achieved an established environmental benchmark. Licensees' effects on the environment will be monitored by PTA, and the agency has the power to set industry standards, issue orders, and take other measures for violations (Ministry of Climate Change, 2019).

The telecommunications industry has said that it complies with all applicable provisions of the EPA Act, as well as all relevant rules and regulations. The telecom industry has reassured the public that its operations are safe thanks to the oversight of government authorities concerned with matters of ecology. In the event of noncompliance or the continued use of deprecated practises, appropriate action is taken in accordance with the applicable legal framework. Telecom operators, according to industry feedback, must get NOCs and comply with other regulatory bodies' criteria while building out new networks (Pakistan Telecommunication Authority, 2018).

Environmental Focus of PTA

In order to protect the environment without hampering the industry's commercial operations, the Pakistan Telecommunications Authority (PTA) and its shareholders have studied the EOTIP, or Environmental Obligations of the Telecommunication Industry of Pakistan. The cellular provider stated that power generation via generators and other renewable energy solutions has become increasingly important due to frequent power outages, despite the fact that electricity delivery is not the core business of cellular carriers (World Bank, 2019).

Massive capital and operating expenses are said to have resulted from this, which in turn lowered industry-wide investment. While Pakistan's telecom companies employ more than 35,000 towers, frequent power outages stemming from problems with transmission networks and grid station electricity severely hamper their operations. As it stands, the only way to ensure that the telecom sector continues to function in the event of a power outage is for telecom companies to construct diesel generators.

Responding to PTA's enquiry, one telecom provider said that the diesel generators it used to power its infrastructure were a major contributor to air pollution. To ensure the industry has access to power for continued economic growth while reducing carbon emissions, the research suggested implementing investor-friendly rules. A competing telecom provider, however, maintained that the low power needs of modern gadgets necessitated removing restrictions on transformer location.

It was proposed that import taxes be reduced for greener telecom equipment like generators in order to stimulate their procurement. To lessen its carbon footprint, it advocated that the government implement policies including lowering taxes and subsidising the purchase of foreign telecommunications equipment (Pakistan Today, 2022).

Even though they must already deal with five such key environmental protection authorities, the country's telecom operators have questioned the 'environmental obligations regulatory framework,' stating it will add to their troubles and impede down quick site installations. According to publicly available papers, the organisation also pushed for a reduction in import duties on greener telecom equipment, such as generators and investor friendly laws, in order to boost corporate access to power, encourage the sector's sustained expansion, and reduce CO2 emissions. As a communications regulator, the PTA is obligated to share information on licenced operators with organisations responsible for pollution prevention and pollution control. Many developing countries have recommended regulations that operators must undertake to reduce GHG emissions, pollution, and trash (Business Recorder, 2018).

1.5.1 Environmental CSR Policy and Practices of Telecom Companies

This section is providing a backdrop of the CSR practices and activities being undertaken by the telecom companies operating in Pakistan. The approach and mindset of the telecom companies can be reflected from their CSR statements and activities, which will be briefly discussed in this section.

Zong's Environmental Stewardship

Zong is a Chinese firm that has expanded to become the most successful telecom provider in Pakistan. Zong is headquartered in China. One thousand people were benefitted as a result of Zong's environmental activities (8,000 males, 2,000 females). In order to do this, we have worked along with the HANDS organisation to plant trees in Karachi and to assure the continuance of the employee volunteer programme called "A New Hope." Additionally, we have offered help to police enforcement in their fight against covid-19.

In Zong's annual report, the company's chief executive officer makes the statement that "people are at the centre of what we do." We have made it easy for our customers to conduct business with us online by putting the requirements and preferences of our customers first. Zong's ultimate goal is to become the digital service provider of choice for every Pakistani; as a result, the company is continually developing new products and features to better satisfy the requirements of its clientele. They have capitalised on the fact that they are the most widely distributed network in the country without lowering their standards or attempting to catch up with modern trends (Zong, 2021). In response to growing environmental concerns and higher ecological standards in Pakistan, employees at Zong 4G have begun a tree-planting initiative on the company's behalf. Zong has begun an initiative that involves a drive to plant trees and has given the initiative the name "Mera Mulk Mera Bagheecha." The Zong employees who work at the company's headquarters in Islamabad's Hill View Park are responsible for planting a large number of bushes and plants there. In order to provide birds that are in the process of migrating with a safe place to rest during the day, workers have set up bird cages and provided the birds with food and water inside the cages.

Hill View Park is implementing a number of exciting initiatives as part of its collaboration with the Capital Development Authority to enhance the park's commitment to environmental responsibility and its appeal to visitors. These initiatives are designed to make the park more appealing to visitors. The installation of motivational sayings and phrases, the construction of a place for people to pray, the design of a play area for children, the provision of space for fruit trees and medicinal plants, as well as the care and maintenance of the playground itself are all included in this category (Siddiqi, 2018).

Telenor

Norway-based In Pakistan, almost everyone uses services from Telenor. In its sustainability report, Telenor emphasised the need of maintaining a stable climate and protecting the environment. Telenor faces a number of physical threats from climate change, including the likelihood of damage to vital infrastructure and services as a result of the effects of increasing extreme weather events and rising sea levels. Rising carbon prices, energy and fuel taxes, and the potential for increased capital expenditures due to a forced shift toward the use of renewable energy solutions all fall under the banner of climate-related regulatory concerns. Telenor's goal is to achieve carbon neutrality in its Nordic operations by 2030, while reducing carbon emissions in Asia by 50% by that time (Telenor Pakistan, 2021).

The people of Pakistan are already feeling the effects of climate change, including extreme weather, lower agricultural productivity, and water shortages. Despite the fact that Pakistan's contribution to global warming is very small, all possible measures should be taken to lessen its impact. The Chief People and Sustainability Officer at Telenor Group provided background on the climate and environment situation in the country, saying, "While the government remains an active proponent and supporter to reduce carbon emissions on a large scale, I cannot emphasise enough that this is a goal that requires collective efforts across the board, cutting across multiple industries." I believe this is one of the most crucial causes for which we should join forces. The telecoms sector might do the same for the Wheeling of Power Regulations and other laws that open the way for large-scale renewable energy projects established by the National Electric Power Regulatory Authority (NEPRA).

According to this regulation, all BPCs in the country will have access to power from any power plant that complies with the regulation (DISCOs). It is imperative that the Wheeling Policy be successfully executed, with the assistance of government authorities, in order to launch the telecom industry's wheeling activities. To address the long-term needs of consumers, residents, and future generations while simultaneously encouraging a more ecologically responsible society, Pakistan's telecom sector must unify behind a unified goal despite the country's severe competitiveness.

Telenor Pakistan's mission has always been crystal clear: to have a good social effect through environmentally responsible and long-term strategies, such providing our clients with a reliable, high-speed internet connection that is always on. To aid in the reduction of carbon emissions, Telenor has altered its network and implemented additional initiatives. Through better facility management in areas such as implementing an operational excellence model, optimising office space, and reducing fleet size, Telenor Pakistan has been able to reduce its carbon emissions by 35% since 2019. Permission is now being discussed for a power purchase agreement that would expand Telenor Pakistan's use of solar energy to 100% (Telenor Pakistan, 2022).

Ufone

Ufone is a telecommunications company in Pakistan that is owned and operated jointly by the governmental and private sectors. Ufone is supporting the citywide effort to make Islamabad, the capital of Pakistan, smoke-free by partnering with the organisation Tobacco-Smoke Free Islamabad. The Parliamentary Secretary of the Ministry of National Health Services; Regulations & Coordination has proclaimed Ufone tower a smoke-free zone. The Ministry and Ufone have signed a memorandum of understanding to collaborate on this initiative. The Parliamentary Secretary who spoke at the occasion said that limiting people's access to tobacco products is the single most important thing that can be done to reduce cancer rates (Government of Pakistan, 2020). Ufone's top lawyer lauded federal efforts to curb cancer and other diseases people might avoid by making better decisions about their health. As a leading Pakistani enterprise and an ethical business, Ufone was pleased to support this initiative to eliminate tobacco use in the workplace.

The Project Director of Tobacco Smoke Free Islamabad and the Deputy DG of Health announced that Ufone Tower will become a smoke-free zone in conjunction with the World Health Organization's (WHO) theme: Tobacco, a risk to Development. He emphasised the role that public education plays in the effective enforcement of tobacco control regulations and the benefits of preventative measures to both human health and the environment (Ufone, 2019)

Furthermore, Ufone contributed to the "Clean & Green Murree Marathon" to raise public awareness about environmental issues. Ufone is conducting the first-of-its-kind "Clean & Green Murree Marathon" in the scenic tourist destination of Murree to raise awareness about the need of protecting the environment and encouraging responsible vacationing.

This inaugural event will feature an 8.3-kilometer marathon raced by locals, tourists, and government officials. "We are happy to support the cause of Clean & Green Murree to mobilise support for saving the local environment, in addition to promoting the concept of ecologically friendly and sustainable tourism," said the head of public relations and corporate communication at Ufone. Our expectation is that the public's attention to this occasion will lead to increased efforts toward environmental protection on the part of individuals, families, and communities. Ufone is grateful to the Murree Development Forum for engaging us in this initiative, which is part of our continued commitment to fostering Pakistan's economic and social growth (Ufone, 2021).

One recent green event in Damial saw staff from Ufone leading a "Plant a Tree" campaign with the help of 150 students from the adjacent The Citizens Foundation (TCF) Primary School. Ufone, a socially aware business, has been supporting the young of Pakistan for years. Formed with the intention of doing good in the world, the Ufone Volunteer Group recently made a visit to a nearby park and held a discussion with the youngsters there on the need of maintaining a clean and green environment (Business Recorder, 2010).

1.6 Research Aim, Objectives and Questions

1.6.1 Aim

- a. To investigate the impact of Environmental CSR practices on employer branding amongst the millennial employees in telecom sector of Pakistan.

1.6.2 Research Objectives

To determine and analyse the perceptions of millennial employees about environmental CSR and employer branding in Pakistan.

1. To identify and evaluate the environmental CSR behaviour of telecom companies in Pakistan.
2. To generate recommendations for effective CSR within Pak tele section
3. and understanding about the role of environmental CSR in driving employer branding in Pakistan.
4. To evaluate and discuss how environmental CSR practices are influencing employer branding of telecom firms in Pakistan.

1.6.3 Research Questions

1. What is the attitude of millennial employees towards environmental CSR in Pakistan?
2. How millennial employees in Pakistan perceive employer branding in relation with environmental CSR?
3. What are the current environmental CSR practices and policies being used by telecom firms in Pakistan?
4. How telecom companies in Pakistan are communicating about their environmental CSR policies and practices?
5. What kind of influence is being exhibited by environmental CSR practices on millennial employees across telecom firms in Pakistan?
6. How telecom companies in Pakistan can improve their employer branding with the help of environmental CSR?

1.7 Research Rationale

This section is presenting the motivation and reasons behind undertaking the particular research study in Pakistan's context. The extant literature has not extensively explored the interplay between Environmental CSR, Employer Branding and millennial job seekers' attitudes and this indicates a relevant research gap to be addressed.

In addition, the interplay of these variables in the context of developing country Pakistan has not been explored yet which gives a strong motivation to undertake this study. Millennial employees and environmental side of CSR are two concepts that are yet to be explored in Pakistan's context. Moreover, the kind of environmental problems Pakistan is facing exhibits a dire need of creating awareness about the serosity of ECSR in Pakistan. Engaging in this research study is one significant way of improving understanding and awareness about the management of environmental issues especially by putting pressure on big companies to initiate ECSR activities by realising their responsibility.

Telecom sector of Pakistan is dominant by MNCs of different countries including China, UAE, Norway and Egypt. Only one telecom company 'Ufone' is a Pakistani public sector company and is a wholly owned subsidiary of Pakistan Telecommunication Company Limited. Therefore, a key motivation is to determine that how these MNCs have implemented CSR culture in Pakistan and how concerned they are about protecting natural environment through CSR. Similarly, a central motivation behind this study is to evaluate the preferences of millennial employees who are expected to be conscious and reactive towards environmental issues (Tyson et al, 2021; Bulut et al, 2021).

From the employer perspective, a key motivation to evaluate that how and to what extent current telecom companies are fulfilling their environmental responsibility by taking care of natural environment which is a key stakeholder. ECSR is a concept essentially prevailed across the developed country context, therefore, it will be of interest to evaluate that how MNCs operating in Pakistan's telecom sector are employing this concept.

Employer branding in both domestic and multinational companies is dominant in the development of a strategic competitive advantage and corporate reputation (Nappa, 2022). Employees have been found as demanding when it comes to environmental impacts and transparency of CSR disclosure (Lawal et al, 2017). However, a key motivation in this regard is to determine that whether employees in a developing country Pakistan tends to demand and prioritize environmental side of CSR when applying for jobs in the telecom industry. Due to the cultural differences between developed and developing countries, it is of interest to examine, whether millennials in a developing country consider environment related CSR practices of employers while applying for jobs. Therefore, the motivation of evaluating millennials (as internal stakeholders) in terms of their ECSR awareness and evaluating telecom sector employers' focus towards ECSR is strengthened by considering these aforementioned implications of underestimating opinion of employees.

Naeem and Welford, (2009) found in their study that considerable number of MNCs working in Pakistan possess written CSR policies in comparison with local listed companies. This empirical evidence also gives a motivation to determine that if the trend of developing policies on environmental practices has changed so far for MNCs while operating in Pakistan.

A key rationale behind this study is to determine the level of organizational identification possessed by employees in response to the ECSR practices and activities implemented by the telecom sector firms. As per Pratt, (1998) when an employee is able to relate herself or himself with an organization, only then organizational identification is developed, and organizational values have a key role to play in this. Therefore, it is also about how the employer is communicating, informing and engaging its employees about their ECSR practices. This signifies a key motivation of the study in a twofold way i.e., to know what kind of ECSR practices are being executed and how well these are being communicated for giving rise to organizational identification.

Interestingly, Naeem and Welfrod, (2009) found that all the MNCs operating in Pakistan have developed written policies about conservation and protection of the environment. Global level environmental campaigns have been influential in this regard especially about climate change. Given this backdrop, it is of interest to investigate that if 100% MNCs have environment protection policies, then to what extent they are actually implementing the policies under their CSR activities.

It is also interesting to note here that the interplay of three central variables (employer branding, ECSR and millennial employees) is being evaluated in this study from different perspectives which means a concrete understanding is expected to be achieved. A study conducted by Deloitte, (2017) revealed that ethical behaviour is considered as priority by millennial employees and a considerable number of employees have not considered working with some companies because of their CSR behaviour and values. Another study by Deloitte, (2016) have found that considerable number of employees have indicated that they might switch employers if their existing company does not fulfil its social responsibility. Findings of Jones et al, (2017) and Cone Communications LLC, (2016) are supporting these findings.

These two above mentioned research findings are indicating that it is not clear whether millennial employees give preference to environmental CSR practices and whether they have the potential of influencing employer branding based on their concern towards environment. There is a fine line between the constructs of environmental CSR and other ethical CSR practices i.e., clarity has not been evidenced about the sensitivity of employees towards ECSR. Therefore, a key motivation of this study is to determine that whether millennial employees (as internal stakeholders) across Pakistan's telecom industry have the potential of influencing employer branding by giving preference to ECSR.

The context of Pakistan is important for initiating research investigation on CSR because Yu et al, (2019) recently stated that with increasing foreign direct investment in Pakistan, environmental CSR concerns are being raised. Especially the OECD guidelines on CSR are asking MNCs to ensure adoption of certain measures and compliance of CSR norms. These aspects are indicating that CSR and employer branding are linked in more than one way which provides strong theoretical foundations for conducting this study in Pakistan's context so that clarity of replicability and truth can be obtained.

1.8 Summary of Contributions and Findings

This study intends to find employer branding being influenced by the environmental CSR driven thinking of millennial employees in Pakistan.

It is expected to be determined that millennial employees in the telecom sector of Pakistan are sensitive towards environmental issues and are being treated as key stakeholders by their employers. A potential contribution is the awareness about environmental CSR as a key driving force behind developing employer branding i.e., a considerable increase in the level of employer and employee awareness is a key contribution intended. A key finding expected to be found is the active participation of MNCs in the environmental sustainability across Pakistan as four out of five telecom companies operating in Pakistan are MNCs.

Another key finding expected to be found is the presence of an emotional connection of millennial employees towards environmental issues and their intention to push their employers towards behaving responsibly towards the natural environment. A potential contribution is the validation and application of organizational identity and stakeholder theory in the developing country context of Pakistan which can be a driving factor towards improving the relationship between employer branding and environmental CSR.

1.9 Overview of Thesis

This thesis is consisting of six chapters with each chapter contributing towards the study in unique manner. Below presented is the brief description of each chapter which is showing the organizing aspect of this study:

Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter has presented the research context and the research problem to be investigated. The motivation behind conducting this study is presented in this study and the theoretical issues have been presented which are urging this study to be conducted.

The roadmap and route of this study has been exhibited in this chapter and rest of the chapters are then developed in line with this roadmap. Research aim, objectives and questions have been outlined in this chapter which are required to be addressed in this thesis.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

Providing theoretical and empirical underpinnings along with the development of conceptual framework are two main sections of this chapter. The most relevant and updated literature has been presented in this chapter for understanding the CSR and employer branding concepts. In this chapter, the viewpoints of scholars, practitioners and researchers working in the relevant discipline has been put forward. This chapter has focused on providing supporting evidence for the research objectives and questions which are being addressed in this thesis. Theoretical foundations have been established in this chapter by including stakeholder theory and organizational identity theory. This chapter has reflected on the role of different factors that can shape and that are important for the interplay of CSR and employer branding. Conceptual framework has been developed in this chapter by considering the picture painted by the literature review and the scope of research objectives.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

This chapter has established the research methods and strategy that is going to be used in the thesis for achieving the research objectives and questions. Data collection and analysis methods have been chosen in this chapter along with their respective justifications.

Research philosophy and reasoning approach to be used in this thesis has been presented i.e. the overall research design has been outlined. Ethical considerations and challenges faced during the data collection process are mentioned in this chapter along with validity and reliability issues faced by the researcher.

Chapter 4: Results

This chapter has presented the interpretations of the results that were gathered through semi-structured interviews. The quotes of the respondents are presented in this chapter against each question.

Sense making has been conducted by interpreting the results of interviews so that themes can be identified. There are three sections of interview questions which are interpreted in this chapter.

Chapter 5: Discussion and Analysis

Five themes have been established in this chapter along with subsequent sub-themes after interpreting results. Each theme is then discussed critically with the help of examples from literature and results. Quotes of respondents have been used in every sub-theme while discussing and evaluating the application of theoretical concepts. Themes and sub-themes have been aligned with results, literature review findings and research objectives and questions. Clarity of arguments and trends have been achieved in this chapter.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Recommendations

This chapter has concluded the key points and crux of the thesis by presenting concluding remarks. Moreover, future research directions have been presented indicating potential areas that can be researched in line with the findings generated by this study. Contribution to research and implications of research have been presented covering key areas on which this study's findings can implicate.

New insights provided by this study have been presented as contribution of research. Limitations of the study are also presented which covers different types of limitations that the researcher had to face during the completion of this study. Lastly, a set of recommendations have been provided for addressing the findings. Literature review findings have been used for justifying the recommendations being given and an alignment with research objectives was considered during this process.

2. Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Perspectives

2.1.1 Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory says that anyone who gets affected from the business activities of organizations is their stakeholder and organizations bear a moral responsibility towards their stakeholders (Freeman, 2004). An extension of this definition and understanding is available in literature. For example, the individuals involved in the decision-making process or taken into the consideration for carrying out any decisions are referred to the stakeholders and it is imperative to manage their interest and power as well (Golob et al, 2017). However, Nielsen and Thomsen (2012) inform that the interest of these stakeholders is not limited to the extrinsic factors, where they also take the intrinsic factors like the care towards the environment and society into consideration.

Stakeholder Theory and CSR

Within the context of businesses social role, corporate social responsibility had become one of the widely recognized and accepted concepts within the organization policy (Freeman, 2008). The sustainability terminology had taken different definitions for resolving the issue of modern development positively. A consensus had also been developed in the literature review ensuring proper compliance to the stakeholders need, voluntary ad triple bottom line (Barkemeyer and Bigge, 2014; Weisman, 2017). However, this consensus gets blurred with the implementation of corporate social policy. There are multiple issues involved within the CSR including greenhouse gas emissions, animal testing, anti-corruption, and product responsibility. The multi-national organizations carrying out operations at a large scale tends to ensure contributions to the host country (Doni et al, 2021). They are expected to positively benefit the entire community apart from the business motivations. Aaker, (2010) used the terminology of corporate citizenship for such kind of act.

CSR also tends to benefit the organizations and MNCs from the political perspective of CSR (McLennan and Banks, 2019). The common factor is to implement the central function of the stakeholder approach. Business organizations need to fulfil the responsibility and interest of the relevant stakeholders (Mehra, 2014).

The hub and spoke model could be effectively used to represent the connection between the organization and its stakeholders. The organizations tend to carry a relationship with different stakeholders' groups (Freeman, 1984). The research study needs to identify all the relevant concepts and views in this regard identifying the stakeholders as societal groups (Donaldson and Preston, 1995; Arikian et al, 2016). Freeman (1984) defines the stakeholder as an individual carrying the potential to affect the organizational image or its achievements. Taking support from an instrumental perspective, the firm managing its stakeholders positively can achieve desired success. It means that the organizations largely depend upon the stakeholders for their survival. However, Freeman, (1984) define it as a narrow concept.

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Figure 4 Stakeholder Theory

Source: Freeman, (1984)

Stakeholder Theory taking value from managerial mechanisms informs that an organization must take care of its stakeholders positively that could be affected by its actions (Freeman, 1984). Freeman (1984) defines a stakeholder as an individual carrying influential power within the organizational operations.

The stakeholder theory focuses on the key relationship existing between the organizations with its social welfare, communities, customers, and employees (Donaldson & Preston, 1995). Francis et al. (2019) also defines it as a leading paradigm related to CSR.

Taking support from the stakeholder theory, which is a strategic tool, CSR is utilized as a tool by the organizations for managing several stakeholders linked to the organization including employees, suppliers, business partners, non-gain organizations, government agencies, and shareholders (Cuesta-Valiño et al., 2019). All of these stakeholders connected with the organization falls into two key groups including the internal and external ones (Randle et al, 2019). These stakeholders tend to carry high importance in determining the key features of the CSR actions by the organizations to ensure its suitable growth as well as long-term survival (Brulhart et al., 2019).

2.1.2 Organizational Identity Theory

The identity theory emerges from the seminal work by Erikson in 1968 related to “Identity, Youth, and Crisis”. Erikson focused on the identity concept for overcoming the “identity crisis” with an emphasis on the disorientation experienced by the soldiers returning to the home after a war. This theory focuses on the posttraumatic stress by which these men felt strangers to themselves (Erikson, 1968).

Akbari et al, (2020) argue that the organizational identity could be considered as a relatively fluid and unstable concept. The key perspective of the Organizational Identity Theory is to address all the needs of the stakeholders to arrange them at the same platform. Taking value from symbolic interactionism, OIT focuses on the perspective related to the language, meaning and thought organizing the connection of the employees with the organization (Martin, 2009; Key, 1995). Identity theory supports understanding the need by which the organizations must keep the stakeholders engaged with themselves to achieve desired success (Lupina-Wegener et al, 2020).

Previous studies have shown that there is a great role played by the employees’ perspective in setting the external as well as an internal image of the organization meaning that the CSR activities lead to better organizational identification.

The reason is that the employees could positively identify themselves by relating them with the socially responsible organization (Ashforth et al, 2016; Turban and Greening, 1997). Dutton et al. (1994) inform about the organizational identification concept by which multiple implications are existing to understand the relationship between the organization and employees as the organization is predicted with suitable deliveries like organizational citizenship behaviour, job satisfaction, and job involvement (Halbesleben and Bellairs, 2016; Organ, 2016).

Taking value from the stakeholder perspective, the organizational relationship with the stakeholders puts a direct impact on the attitude and behaviour of the stakeholders (Freeman, 1984; Barnett, 2005). Madsen and Rodgers, (2014) agree to the same informing that the stakeholders positively relating themselves to the organization display positive attitude and behaviour. It means that the CSR initiatives displayed by the organization support them in setting positive relationships with the stakeholders compelling them to display a positive attitude.

The social identity theory had been used in different perspectives for proposing the relationship between the expected employee outcomes and perceived CSR mediated through the organizational identity (Hogg and Terry, 2004). Specifically, when the employee perceives the organizational CSR positively, then they remain satisfied and develop a strong relationship with the organization as well. It leads towards a positive attitude from the employees at work (Gioia et al, 2013). Previous studies showcased a relationship between the employees' reaction and perceived CSR with a mediating role of organizational identity. For instance, Carmeli et al. (2007) recommend the organizations make use of perceived CSR to promote the organizational identity amongst the employees to gain better employee outcomes (Jones, 2010), intent to stay (Jones, 2010), job satisfaction (Kim et al., 2018), and job performance (De Roeck et al., 2014).

Perceived CSR supports in improving the organizational performance as the employees feel confident in connecting themselves with the organizational identity motivating them to make a valuable contribution to the organization (Ellemers et al., 2004; Upham, 2006). Bartels et al. (2010) agree to the same informing that the suitable organizational identity supports the employee in completing their tasks effectively. Shen and Benson (2016) also found support in using CSR to improve employee performance with a direct connection with organizational identification. Organizational identification supports the employee in relating themselves positively with the organization and perceiving the organizational values effectively as well (Pratt, 2003).

Moral Identity and Organizational CSR

The previous sections research the moderating role of moral identity in the scenarios like organizational injustice impact on the counterproductive working behaviour (Wu, et al., 2014) and a moderating role between the supervisor abuse of customers and employee organizational deviance (Greenbaum et al., 2013). Taking value from the relationship between the organizational initiatives and employee response, this study also proposes a relationship between the employees' organizational identification and organizational CSR actions.

Moral identity showcases the knowledge related to the self-definition linked to the moral traits (Aquino and Reed, 2002), which can be used as a source of personal intrinsic motivation (He and Pham, 2014). The individuals possessing high moral identity, moral schemes in a chronic manner are active for information processing Lapsley and Lasky (2001, p. 347). Specifically, the people with stronger moral identity are more likely to showcase moral identity-based knowledge for managing their behaviours (Aquino et al., 2009; Ihlen et al, 2015). Comparatively, the people coming with low moral identity takes less care of the morality or ethics along with their moral values and moral schemes. Reed et al. (2007) agrees to the same informing that the moral identity tends to direct the people to focus less on the moral information. Therefore, the CSR initiatives undertaken by an organization tends to support in influencing the employees' positively with high moral trait or identity.

A high level of moral identity indicates that there is a high chance of noticing moral-related information supporting the individuals in showcasing a better capacity for identifying the others based on the morality-related variables (Turner et al., 1987). Researchers argue here about the variables often used for identifying the others with a high social identity linked to the ethical, religious, political or avocational groups (Tajfel and Turner, 1986; Hogg et al., 2004). The moral identity in such cases directs the attention of the moral information linked with the groups carrying moral traits. Making use of self-categorization theory (Turner et al., 1987), individuals tend to evaluate the linkage between their self-categorization process and social group to activate their social identity by categorizing themselves as a group member.

Making use of identity-based perspective (Tajfel and Turner, 1986; Hogg et al., 2004), individuals take part in the groups aligned with their attributes and values positively to meet their psychological needs related to the sense of being and attributions. It allows the individuals to compare their similarities and differences with each other in a particular group.

2.2 Concept and Dynamics of Millennial Generation Employees

The generation born between 1982 and 2004 is defined as Millennials or Generation ‘Y’ (Howe and Strauss, 2009). This generation has different set of values and behaviours in the professional environment (Deal et al., 2010). Özçelik (2015) looked at the millennial generations’ differences compared with other generations finding that the active workforce globally includes the millennials. It means that the millennials occupational values tend to carry a high value for the organization as they carry different expectations reflected in the recruitment strategies of the organization as well. For instance, Hammer and Pivo (2017) inform that millennials tend to behave and act differently as compared to the other generations. There are two key types of millennials including perfectionists and overachievers. They can be teacups as well appearing tough on the outside but are quite soft from inside. Ozanne et al. (2016) makes use of the difference between the generations taking value from their age and experience aspect. However, the differences between them rise because of age cohorts instead of age effects expected to remain confined to the generation age.

2.2.1 Characteristics of Millennials

The Millennial generation is the most critical part of the workforce, and this notion is global. As this study focuses on the millennial workforce, hence it is imperative to elaborate the definition of this category. For this study, anyone born between 1982 and 1996 would be termed as a Millennial (Dimock, 2019). This generation will constitute over a third of total workforce globally by 2020. (Facts, Millennial Careers). The Millennial generation is highly distinctive when it comes to defining its traits. Having a strong preference for personal attention and high degree of self-esteem is one of the principal characteristics of this generation.

They are highly technology savvy and core believer in teamwork. The motivational determinant of this breed is difficult to be ascertained by the managers, as their scope of expectations is grossly different from their older colleagues (Meola, 2016). Walden, Jung, and Westerman (2017) inform about some key traits of millennials including teamwork, lack of initiative, and lack of etiquette. Özçelik (2015) also argue that the values of the millennial tend to vary largely focused on frequent feedback and lack of willingness to fully commit their time at work. Where Singh and Shukla (2016) argue that there is no work-related difference existing amongst the generations. Meng, Reber, and Rogers (2017) inform that generational differences could occur based on the experience and issues experienced by two individuals coming from different generations. Where some of the common characteristics amongst each generation had been shown in the table below:

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Figure 5 Characteristics of Generations

Adapted from Kowske et al, (2010)

As per the table, there are some prominent characteristics of Millennials including Pressured, authority acceptance, special, confidence, etc. Walden, Jung, and Westerman (2017) inform that characteristic of the millennials had taken this shape explained by their upbringing as they had been raised by helicopter parents. They had made it believable that they are the better ones compared with other people belonging to other generations (Singh and Shukla, 2016). Moreover, the millennials come with a sense of entitlement as well reflected through their demands within the educational organizations and employers. However, Meng, Reber, and Rogers (2017) argue that millennials come with a preference for strict rules; instead, they reject such kinds of rules. They are motivated by the employer offering them a suitable opportunity to make their decisions, execute them, and receive feedback as well.

Due to the different traits and characteristics of the millennials, some researchers believe that they tend to act differently as well compared to the other generations (Stewart et al. 2017). Zhao (2018) analyse the previous researcher to evaluate the differences amongst the working attitude of different generations using different measures like intent to turnover, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction. The research indicates that the satisfaction level of millennials is low as compared to the older generations (Meng, Reber, and Rogers, 2017; Pînzaru et al. 2016). Where the organizational commitment remains consistent across all the generations. However, the intent of leaving the organization is higher amongst the millennials as compared to the other generations.

Zhao (2018) agree with the same informing that substantive differences are existing amongst the generations. However, Walden, Jung, and Westerman (2017) argue that the generational difference mainly occurs outside, where it is not reflected well within the work settings. Yet, Özçelik (2015) acknowledge the different working preferences and attitudes amongst the millennials as compared to the other generations. Previous research showcase that the ability of processing information and cognitive processes are highly affected by age factors. Moreover, the change in lifestyle values and attitudes also accompany the age factor. In other terms, age could affect the individuals' perception as well as attitude towards CSR (Özçelik, 2015). For instance, Singh and Shukla (2016) researched to showcase that the age factor plays a key role in the perceiving of ethical conduct that is quite higher at the age of 40+ group followed by the lower age groups.

Related to the CSR satisfaction and trust, Walden, Jung, and Westerman (2017) inform that younger people are more satisfied with the organizational actions, where this satisfaction tends to reduce with the age factor leading towards more distrust and cynicism. Where, Meng, Reber, and Rogers (2017) argue that age is not only the single factor affecting the perceiving of ethical conduct by an individual as his work experience and educational attainment plays a key role in this regard as well.

2.3 Concept of CSR and Business Organizations

Herrera and Heras-Rosas (2020) inform about Carroll definition playing a key role in showcasing organizational CSR by which the organization must fulfil all the necessary legal, economic, philanthropic, ecological and ethical activities towards the society. (Dumont et al, 2017) (Tran and Nguyen, 2020). (Herrera and Heras-Rosas, 2020). Business organizations must pay keen attention to the environmental factors as well including employees need, customers right, contractual obligations, and environmental effectiveness (Krajnakova et al, 2018) (Ilyas, 2018; Zalezna et al, 2020).

Figure 6 Social responsibility in the process of management; a comparison of models

Source: Carroll, (2016) and Baden, (2016)

Popa and Salanta (2015) Stonkut et al, (2018). The recent definitions related to CSR showcase the rising interest of the stakeholders towards the fulfilment of ethical, economic, social, and ecological activities by the organization.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found at Lee, T.H.; Riffe, D. (2019) Business news framing of Corporate Social Responsibility in the United States and the United Kingdom: Insights from the implicit and explicit CSR framework. *Bus. Soc.* 58, 683 -711.

Figure 7 A review of definitions of corporate social responsibility (CSR)

Source: Lee and Riffe, (2019)

Alshamari et al, (2021) There are multiple activities involved within the CSR compelling the organizations to pay equal attention to the environment as well as the community. The method by which the organizations fulfil their social responsibility instead of focusing just on profits refers to “corporate social responsibility” (Aguinis and Glavas, 2019; Coombs and Hallaway, 2018). Nine critical factors must be focused on by the organization to ensure effective CSR operations including financial gains, product value, business relations, governance, community involvement, employment policies, and environmental protection (Emerald Publishing Group, 2020).

Aftab et al, (2021) inform that the organizations engaged in CSR activities can boost work commitment, job satisfaction, and organizational identification positively. Li et al, (2019) inform the employee as a key asset of an organization. It means that the organizations being successful in developing and sustaining a strong relationship with the employees can achieve their business targets positively. For the same reason, organizations need to pay attention to the economic, social, and environmental aspects of CSR positively (Zhao et al., 2020).

Employee engagement tends to benefit both employers as well as the employee. For instance, the employees make positive efforts to benefit the employer with creative ideas and actions; where, the employee receives better compensation and support from the employer side keeping both of them satisfied (Manning, 2019; Pasricha et al, 2018). It means that the CSR activities are of benefit for both the organization and employee. Job relevant CSR activities also allow the employees to gain suitable skills and develop them professionally as well for making a positive contribution to the business growth and success. Sarfraz et al, (2018) argue here that organizations in modern times perceive employee engagement as a key tool for achieving success and taking social initiatives for both private and NGO organizations (Pérez, 2015; Bode & Singh, 2018). This trend had also been reflected in the critical times of COVID-19 encouraging both employee and employer to establish strong relations with each other (Kelley et al., 2019).

The organizations need to ensure carrying out regular communication with the stakeholders related to the CSR for sustaining their trust and meeting the growing commitments of the business related to the CSR (Xiao et al, 2020). Duthler and Dhanesh (2018) also recommend the organizations can involve the relevant stakeholders (employees) within the internal CSR communications. Effective internal communications related to CSR allow the organizations to understand and manage the employees' needs positively leading towards the exploitation of more innovation and growth opportunities (Gruber, Kaliauer, and Schlegelmilch, 2017; Hendriks, 2016). The organizations also gain the benefit of gaining positive support from the employees' side by disclosing the CSR aims with them enhancing the chances of achieving the objectives. Lee (2020) argues here that the working conditions, supervisor support, etc. all tend to play a key role related to the organizational CSR activities.

It also tends to support the organizations in assessing the needs and desires amongst the employees related to CSR. This study also focuses on the demandingness aspect of the employees related to the environmental, social, and economic activities of the organization (Duthler and Dhanesh, 2018). The CSR performance of the organization is highly impacted by the demand of the employees. However, it is necessary to mention that employee demandingness refers to the difference between organizational activities and employee expectations (Weder, Einwiller, and Eberwein, 2019).

Organizations can build long-term relations with the employee through CSR activities. Park, Kim, and Kwon (2017) argue here that CSR perceptions tend to influence employee attitude and behaviour. It means that CSR activities play a great role for the organizations in generating and sustaining employee trust and commitment (Sindhu and Arif, 2017). It also tends to put a positive impact on the employee stress level encouraging them to offer innovative and growth-oriented support to the organization. However, the lack of communication could affect employee trust leading towards enhancing absenteeism rate as well (Moliner et al., 2019).

Wu and Chen (2015) suggest here that organizations must pay attention to their CSR activities for accomplishing their economic and social goals. The existing literature mainly focused on determining the relation between the perceived CSR and different employee-related outcomes like job satisfaction, and organizational commitment (Barcelos et al., 2015; Lin et al, 2019). However, there are limited studies making use of a systematic method to explore the impact of organizational CSR on the behavioural and attitudinal outcomes of the employee (Gruber et al, 2018).

2.3.1 CSR and Employees

CSR is mainly defined as an organizational responsibility impacting society. The responsibility scope could be taken from the fulfilment of the general, ethical, and legitimate requirements by the organization (Hameed et al., 2016). On the other hand, the employees are the key stakeholders of the organization paying attention to the several CSR frameworks. For instance, the European Commission (2008) identifies four key responsibilities for an organization related to the employees and CSR:

Figure 8 Fields of CSR proposed by the European Commission

Source: European Commission (2008)

Furthermore, the ISO 26000 framework provides information about the key aspects of the organizational responsibility involving Labour Practices and Human Rights.

Figure 9 Core subjects of CSR in the ISO 26000 framework

Source: Based on International Organization for Standardization (2014)

The literature had certainly paid attention to the linkage of employees with organizational CSR activities. It also implies job selection as one of the key aspects of CSR. Hameed et al. (2016) also informed that CSR influences organizational identity and commitment affecting employee productivity and motivation level. There are various theories available for explaining the same notion.

For instance, the motivational theories indicate different needs of the employee related to CSR including work-life balance, health management, and social benefits putting a direct impact on employee motivation, satisfaction, and innovation in an organization (Schaefer, Terlutter, and Diehl, 2020). It means that the cognitive and affective judgement of the employees is highly affected by the CSR actions of the company. The other areas of CSR are also expected to boost organizational attractiveness (Ko, Chan, and Wong, 2019). For instance, the social identity theory claims that CSR puts a positive impact on the self-esteem and social identity aspect of the employees.

Moreover, the potential and current employees could create a link between the organizational image and their reputation. Tian and Robertson (2019) said that the employees prefer working in an organization possessing suitable values. Where the employees feel unsatisfied to work in the organizations making use of unfair methods to generate profits. Considering the rising ecological as well as social needs amongst the individuals, the organizations must reflect legal, ethical, and social side within their actions (Nirino et al, 2020). Sardana et al, (2020) also recommend that the organizational attributes must be attributed as a signal for positively influencing the market and environment to emerge as a socially responsible organization.

However, it is necessary to mention that the CSR performance does not necessarily highlight the social side of the organization. For instance, HP despite having good CSR performance scored fewer ratings in the CSR performance (Kim et al, 2018). It means that CSR image and CSR identity terms are quite different from each other requiring suitable actions as well as marketing from the organizational side.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Cho S, Chung C and Young J, (2019) Study on the Relationship between CSR and Financial Performance, Sustainability 2019, 11, 343

Figure 10 Positive effects of different CSR components

Source: Cho et al, (2019)

Employer branding and expected effects of CSR

The employer brand refers to the image of the organization for taking positive care of the employees' needs and requirements. The employer branding functions differ from each other based on the employee or employer perspective (Carlini et al., 2019). Considering the employer perspective, an employer differentiates itself from the competitors to offer better support to the potential and current employees. It is one of the key components of employer branding allowing the employer to attract current as well as new employees (Puncheva-Michelotti, Hudson, and Jin, 2018).

Related to the employee perspective, the employer offers a key opportunity to the current employees for practising innovative and effective decision-making at the workplace for ensuring high success and growth for the organization (Yameen et al, 2021). There are multiple emotional as well as functional aspects involved within the employer branding perspective simplifying the decision-making process (Bharadwaj and Yameen, 2020).

The employer brand tends to showcase the suitable quality of the employer allowing it to catch and sustain the attention of the current as well as potential employees carrying high importance in the employer selection decisions.

It is quite understandable that a new employee is unable to understand the characteristics of an employer prematurely putting the employer selection decision at risk. The employees make use of employer image in the market as criteria for making the employer selection decision (Hoppe, 2018). Employer branding tends to refer to the values of the organization. It could be used by the potential as well as current employees to compare their values with the organizational ones to make the employer selection decision (Kashyap and Rangnekar, 2018). The employer brand could also be used by the employees to set up their image amongst their friends. The key goal of employer branding is to sustain the current and attract new employees (Kumari and Saini, 2018). It also contributes positively to the organizational brand image as well as company culture leading towards improved performance.

Figure 11 Functions and effects of employer branding

Source: Bustamante & Brenninger (2014), based on Stotz & Wedel-Klein (2013)

This section clarifies that the employee branding tends to offer suitable benefits to the employer taking value from the potential impacts of CSR on the employees. Both employer branding, as well as CSR strategies, are focused on building preferences and trust in the company's favour leading towards the increased identification amongst the company and employee compelling the organizations to strongly integrate themselves with CSR (Kim et al, 2017).

2.4 Environmental side of CSR in Organizations

2.4.1 Environment within CSR

Environmental CSR refers to the initiatives by which business organizations attempt to reduce their carbon footprints like wastage management, recycling, energy usage and water usage (Bahta et al, 2021). Business organizations in the contemporary world are the biggest contributors to pollutions due to the excessive usage of natural resources putting a bad impact on biodiversity. Therefore, suitable actions need to be taken for reducing the human activities impact being carried out in this regard. It is not sufficient to take the initiatives for neutralizing the carbon emissions; instead, the business organizations need to shed environmental burden from all of their business operations starting from the designing stage to the consumer stage. The Corporate Social Responsibility context was mainly recognized after the publication of the European Commission Document in 2004 with the name of "Green Paper on CSR" (Jones et al, 2020). The document showcased that there is a key responsibility of the organizations towards the environment that must be fulfilled by the leaders and managers. Therefore, business organizations need to take suitable actions for bringing suitable changes at the workplace to develop such competencies and strengths for combating strongly with the environmental effects. The analysis of the corporate social responsibility theory within the managerial context provides an understanding of different characteristics existing within the context of society, business, and environment.

The difference existing between these factors determine the method of interaction and collaboration. The last 20 years had been quite prominent for the increased awareness of CSR amongst the relevant stakeholders to attain desired positive results. However, the CSR concept is understood differently in different areas.

For example, the business organization in Poland consider social responsibility as a voluntarily social or ecological aspect for carrying out all the actions (Dabirian et al, 2017). Where, some companies consider sustainable actions as core ones for complying effectively with the relevant legislation; otherwise, they could experience issues in managing their business operations effectively. This kind of thinking also guides the entire decision-making process of the organization. Such an approach is quite effective in enhancing the life quality as well as the implementation of sustainable development concepts positively.

Socially responsible entities are completely aware of their responsibilities towards the environment; therefore, they ensure to take positive actions to reduce their pollution as well as harmful substance emissions (Forcadell and Aracil, 2017). They tend to focus on improving the efficiency of their natural resource and reducing their carbon footprints up to the maximum extent. Individuals and organizations in the contemporary world must understand that the excessive usage of natural resources from their side is certainly going to create a deficit for future generations. Therefore, all the individuals, as well as organizations, are equally responsible for efficient resources utilization to offer a suitable opportunity to the future generations for growth.

The literature review in the area of corporate social responsibility showcased that a large number of studies had been carried out focusing on the negative impacts of the organizations as well as the relevant stakeholders. It is not suitable for organizations or individuals to compromise on environmental effectiveness for the sake of profitability. The Glavas notes provide information about three key trends emerging in corporate social responsibility are. The first one is related to the organizational role within the society. It means that either there is a role of the business organizations to look beyond their profits or not. The second question is that either CSR is normative or not. It refers to the question that it is obligatory for the organizations to think before generating profits only. If CSR is an obligation for the organization, then it is their social or moral responsibility to make positive actions for social well-being. Many scholars had agreed to the normative role of CSR for business organizations. The third question is related to the financial performance of the company. It means that when business organizations generate suitable profits, then they can bring positive results for both company and society. Taking value from the World Business Council related to Sustainable Development, CSR tends to carry high importance for the business organizations to ensure social well-being.

It is the key reason by which there is a clear need of carrying out detailed research to understand the potential benefits of social activities by the business organizations over their silent stakeholders. Eco-management is one of the key concepts existing in this regard reducing the negative impact of the organization. Business organizations are facing pressure to reduce their environmental impact due to the increasing awareness amongst the relevant stakeholders. Some authors also argue that business organizations can make use of environmental protection as a strategy to enhance their financial performance because they will experience a decrease in the usage of raw materials and energy costs. It also refers that the social responsibility for the business organizations is actually to generate profits without putting a negative impact on the environment. The entrepreneurs in the modern world are coming up with suitable sustainable and eco-management plans to reduce the overall carbon emission rate. For instance, about 81% of the regional entrepreneurs in 2019 accepted corporate social responsibility as their key responsibility and showed an aim to take suitable actions for reducing the overall carbon emissions positively.

2.4.2 Responsibility of Global Climate Change

The world in recent times is changing a key issue of Climate Change, whose spectrum had increased even further in the 21st century. The rise of the physical, as well as the biological temperature, had put many species in danger. Khojastehpour and Johns (2014) argue here that the inefficient usage of resources is the biggest contributor to climate change in the world. It is also a rising key concern for all the relevant business stakeholders (Halldorsson and Kolak and Pinkse, (2012) argue here that some business organisations are also making efforts to reduce their impact on climate change and accept the regulatory changes positively.

The climate change issue in the modern world had become a global one. It is becoming a key responsibility for business organizations to reduce their negative impact on the climate as well as the environment. The performance of the business organizations is strongly interlinked with the same factor (Zhou et al, 2012). It means that the business organizations are being expected to showcase positive actions towards the environment. The political and social forces are playing a key role in motivating the organizations in this regard (Schendler, 2021).

Moreover, legislative measures are also necessary to provide a clear direction to the business organizations (Oberseder et al., 2013). The organizations also need to arrange investment for undertaking environmentally friendly actions for achieving desired positive results.

Climate change is one of the key issues at the current moment because the rise of the physical, as well as the biological temperature, had put many species in danger (Kolk and Pinkse, 2012). Halldorsson and Kovacs (2010) argue that the stakeholders' attention had diverted towards the climate change and natural resources excessive usage. Due to the rising attention of the stakeholders in the developed countries, many organizations had to take positive actions for reducing their impact on climate change (Kolk and Pinkse, 2012). As climate change is an international environmental-related issue; therefore, it tends to carry high importance as a part of organizational strategy (Kolk and Pinkse, 2004). All the organizations are engaged in the wider business environment and the impact on the environment affects their business expectations and performances (Werther and Chandler, 2005). Therefore, it implies that business organizations in the modern world need to be more socially aware and active towards the environment (Werther and Chandler, 2005).

2.5 COVID-19 and Telecom Sector of Pakistan

The pandemic refers to the outbreak of a disease requiring consideration related to the crisis management similar to response and effective decision-making for a natural disaster like a hurricane, terrorism, and collapse (Glantz, 2014). Many studies had focused on the pandemic by arguing that the disease outbreak is no different to the natural disasters occurring for the human being carrying an equal level of implications (Xu et al., 2016). The researchers had a keen interest in evaluating the role of the organizations during the occurrence of such pandemic in the human world (Gardberg et al., 2019). The novel Corona Virus outbreak also known as COVID-19 created multiple health implications all across the world causing The World Health Organization to declare an emergency. Multiple economic, as well as social and environmental risks, were created because of the COVID-19 outbreak. Similar to the past example, business organizations need to understand their social responsibility in such kinds of scenarios and take rapid actions to ensure suitable future development after the pandemic (Ding et al. 2020).

The United Nations also made a call for organizations all across the world to combine for developing a strong resilient team to combat global crisis like climate change, pandemics, etc. instead of returning to the stone world (UN, 2020).

The immediate impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on Pakistan's telecom sector is visible in the growth trends of vital telecom indicators. However, the sector braved the adversity rather converted it into an opportunity. As it is, digitization of the economy was already underway when the pandemic struck Pakistan by end-March 2020 (Shafi et al, 2020). The telecom sector met with a huge demand from corporate set-ups and individuals alike to meet the social, educational, health-related, and economic requirements across the country. This unprecedented situation created rather daunting circumstances for PTA as it had to ensure connectivity, provide broadband services at lower cost, disseminate free information on the pandemic to the entire populace, counter disinformation, and put up with the pressure to provide broadband services in rural and far-flung areas for educational and other online activities, to name a few.

Despite a revenue decline of 2.4 percent, Pakistan's telecom sector has contributed 128 percent more to the national economy and managed to withstand the impact of COVID-19, said the Pakistan Telecommunication Authority (PTA) in its annual report. The official document revealed that 98 percent of Pakistani households own a mobile phone, adding that the mobile service penetration level reached about 81 percent toward the end of October with 172.3 million mobile subscriptions (Ahmed, 2021). There was also an impressive growth trend of 17 percent in broadband subscriptions that crossed 90.1 million in October while 4G subscriptions registered an exponential increase of 60 percent during the same period. The pandemic has also led to the rise of broadband penetration to 39.2 percent in FY20 from 33.8 percent in FY19. The telecom sector contributed Rs278.4 billion (\$1.7 billion) to the national exchequer which is 128 percent higher than the previous year's Rs121.9 billion. The contribution to the national economy came in the form of Rs41.5 billion on account of general sales tax and Rs141.1 billion in the shape of other PTA deposits, according to the report (Ahmed, 2021).

COVID-19 Monitoring Cell

A COVID-19 Monitoring Cell was established at PTA to ensure that the industry mounts a prompt and effective response to the pandemic in consultation with GoP. The Cell was tasked with leading a massive public awareness campaign on the electronic, print, digital and social media, also utilizing blogs and websites, Ring Back Tones (RBTs), and awareness SMSs in Urdu, English, and regional languages. The Cell also engaged in IP whitelisting and facilitating COVID-related helplines by providing short codes and UANs to various organizations. PTA directed mobile operators to send COVID-19 awareness messages to subscribers across Pakistan. During March-June 2020, a total of 1,843 million messages were sent to mobile users and more than 1 million cautionary messages were sent to travellers and persons suspected of contracting the virus. Moreover, PTA also directed mobile operators to replace the standard RBT with a message on how to prevent Coronavirus; the function was auto activated on mobile devices of 79.4% (131.7 million) subscribers (PTA, 2020). About 240 million SMS were disseminated about the precautionary measures to be taken by students, teachers and parents while school opening during COVID-19. SMS for taking precautionary measures against coronavirus were disseminated to almost 1 million travellers/suspected persons with corona virus symptoms.

To provide health-related information services to the public, PTA allocated the short code 1166 to the National Command and Operations Centre (NCOC); this code continues to be used nationwide by people keen to keep abreast with COVID-related information. PTA assisted the ministries of National Health Services and Interior, the National Disaster Management Authority (NDMA), and NIH in their efforts to track and trace patients' migration, and to identify patient clusters for implementation of smart lockdowns. It is imperative to mention that the connection created between the customers and brand at such difficult times is far stronger as compared to the relationship developed in peaceful times. It means that the COVID-19 offered a great opportunity to the business organizations for engaging themselves in effective CSR strategies as well as agendas (Zhao, 2021).

2.6 Understanding Employer Branding

2.6.1 Significance of Employer Branding

Ambler and Barrow (1996) describe the employer brand as "the package of functional, economic, and psychological benefits offered by employment, and identifiable with the employing organisation." Employer brand propositions are defined by brand strategists in accordance with the brand identity, which is conceptualised as stable and enduring basic characteristics, or brand DNA (Aaker, 1996).

Employer branding is a direct or subtle phenomenon, which encapsulates all the organizations. It is the distinctive ability of the brand, which is used as a tool for recruitment, retention and engagement of the worthy human resource. The acquisition of the right talent is determined by the credibility of the brand itself. Moreover, this credibility must converge with the core organizational values while having a strong reflection in the practices of human resource management (CIPD, 2021).

The organizations must be thoroughly aware and be cognizant of the interests of all the stakeholders, employees as well as customers. Over the years, marketing techniques have evolved and developed to attract and retain the customer base. The concept of loyalty to a consumer brand has improved by exploiting the tools of direct communication with the customers (Mosley, 2019). Employer branding is not different from the definition of a conventional branding where a potential or existing customer is offered the value proposition. Employer branding works in similar fashion where the organization positions itself as the most lucrative mode of professional engagement to the existing and potential employees. The strength of the employer brand lies in its ability to connect the organizational values and strategies with the brand of the company as known to the outside world. One of the principal components of this arena is the strong adherence to the ethical standards in dealing with all sorts of affairs pertaining to the employees' affairs. It can thus be established that the reflection of ethical virtues and principles in the core business strategies are the cornerstone in determination of the health of the employer brand for the prospective and existing employees (Keohane, 2020).

Earlier studies link the development of employer branding with the strong value proposition employers have to offer internally as well as externally (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004). Molk and Auer (2018) do not agree with the top down approach of employer branding suggesting that the employer branding literature “largely theorizes employer branding as a controllable management process rather than as a social phenomenon” (p. 485).

As per the authors, the dynamics of the social fabric command a significant influence on the power structures of an organization and subsequently it has the impact on the employer branding. Edwards (2010) discusses the significance of perceived employer branding and explores its calibration with the concept of shared employment experience. The author defines employer branding as the “identification of elements of the character of the organisation itself; features such as the organisation’s key values and the guiding principles underlying how it operates as a collective entity” (p. 7). It is therefore a shared experience of the employer and the employee, which also gets impacted by the individual actions of the employee.

When a company uses employer branding, it may showcase its distinctive characteristics and demonstrate how it distinguishes itself from the competition. Employer branding, according to Wilden et al. (2010), allows a company to ensure that it has access to potential employees through marketing to them. It is possible to describe employer brand success as having a well-known and visible presence; a strong feeling of relevance and resonates; and, most importantly, a clear competitive edge. A measure represented in the image on the next page was developed to highlight the strategic concerns associated with features of a successful employer brand. This metric was developed to illustrate the strategic concerns associated with the attributes of a successful employer brand.

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Figure 12 Metric of the characteristic of a successful employer brand

Source: Moroko & Uncles, 2008

2.6.2 Role of Internal Branding

There exists a strong correlation between employer branding and internal branding. Internal branding focuses on the internal customer i.e. the employee and the strategies deployed in internal branding are similar to those for positioning of the company or the product to the outside world. It can thus be inferred that internal branding is in effect a vital component of internal marketing (Barros-Arrieta & García-Cali, 2020). The fundamental aim of internal marketing is to promote the brand among the workforce to the extent that it motivates the quality delivery of the brand value to the outside world (Foster et al., 2010, Saleem and Iglesias, 2016), including potential recruits. As with any other brand strategy, internal branding would also require the relevant tools, which have the lasting impact. Employees always seek professional growth to enhance their professional worth and that only becomes possible by regularly holding relevant and worthy training programmes. In addition, the culture of appropriate internal communication also plays an instrumental role in earning employees' loyalty and commitment, which is positively directed towards achievement of strategic goals and objectives. It can therefore be stated that these initiatives constitute the behavioural disposition of an employee which gets aligned with the brand identity (Vallaster & de Chernatony, 2006).

The recurrent application of brand values does get noticed and it eventually gathers support of the workforce (Hankinson, 2012). The ultimate objective of investing in employer branding and internal branding is to fortify the corporate brand (Hoppe, 2018). And this is achieved by a strong calibration of both the aforementioned brands which collectively makes it possible for the organization to develop a strong corporate brand that resonates a vibrant organizational culture and formidable corporate identity.

Chhabra and Sharma (2014) assessed the three determinants of employer branding including the brand name, organizational culture and compensation. Jain and Bhatt (2015) suggest that recruitment and retention strategies must have a strong footprint of organizational support and infrastructure if the optimum level of performance from the employees is desired. The culture and identity of any organization are the fundamental determinants of an employer's positioning (Jiang and Iles, 2011; Sageder et al., 2018). The studies of Saraswathy and Balakrishnan (2017) and Davies et al. (2018), also conform to organizational culture and organizational identity as the stepping-stone for the internal brand positioning.

Yang et al. (2015) investigated the impact of internal branding and employer brand promises on employee brand behaviour in the hospitality industry as part of their research. According to them, the branding cycle includes the creation of an internal brand, the launch of a brand, and the behaviour of a brand.

Following Yang et al. (2015)'s findings, internal branding has a consistent impact across all age groups of employees; however, internal branding has a different impact on employees who work in the BC (business-to-consumer) and BB (business-to-business) industries (business-to-business).

Employer branding and corporate social responsibility programmes are also thought to have a positive impact on employee recruitment, retention, and development (Turban & Greening, 1997; Brammer et al., 2007; Lin et al., 2012). CSR initiatives that include employer branding are more effective at communicating CSR actions to stakeholders while also generating internal company benefit, such as staff retention and improved performance. The understanding of a company's employees about the brand's internal influence on them is the foundation of the company's devotion to its brand. Using data from the hotel industry, Yang et al. (2015) looked at the impact of internal branding and employer brand promises on employee brand behaviour.

Specifically, their research framework concentrates on the branding cycle, which is illustrated in the image below and consists of the following elements: internal branding, brand commitment, and brand behaviour.

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Please contact the thesis author for further
information.

Figure 13 Branding Cycle

Source: Yang et al, (2015)

They observed that age groups have minimal impact on internal branding, but a significant one for employee BC and the other for the other for the other in their study. IB (internal brand) had no link with years of employment, however both BC (brand commitment) and employee BB (brand loyalty) were significantly influenced by years of employment (brand behaviour). According to Yang et al., (2015) research, hotel employees with greater levels of education are less likely to feel stuck in their professions. As a result, they are more confident in their abilities and less concerned about finding a job that fits their needs. Companies could also consider creating an internal marketing brand to educate their employees, which is highly suggested by Yang et al. (2015).

As part of their study, they found that younger employees with more education and shorter tenures at their organisations were more likely not to be influenced by corporate branding. These personnel must be reached through a range of branding techniques, including providing them with ongoing training and development opportunities and establishing a performance-based reward programme. Even while employee brand commitment has an impact, the manager's responsibility is to influence employee attitudes and behaviour through internal branding (Yang et al., 2015).

2.6.4 Employer of Choice and Employer Branding

The importance of a company's brand has long been recognised as a valuable asset in attracting highly qualified individuals. The brand has garnered a great deal of attention as a means of attracting and retaining clients. It is a word used in human resources management to describe the process of attracting and maintaining high-calibre individuals (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004). Businesses may offer a package of psychological, economic, and functional benefits to their employees as part of their employer branding strategy in order to distinguish themselves from their competitors (Ambler and Barrow, 1996). A number of past studies have found that employer brand plays a significant role in the recruitment and retention of highly qualified employees (Branham, 2001; Rampl, 2014).

According to Lievens (2007), the first step in becoming an EOC is to build a value proposition and promote particular promises both internally and publicly. When it comes to branding an organisation, it all comes down to pushing two concepts: value propositions and promises (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004).

The distinction between "Employer of Choice" and normal recruitment outcomes such as "job pursuit intents," "acceptance intentions," or "job-organization attraction" is made here by the authors (Chapman et al., 2005). Applying for employment with an organisation indicates an applicant's "intention to pursue employment with the organisation." Clearly, the candidate's desire to remain in the applicant pool, rather than his devotion to a certain position, can be seen in this instance. Alternatively, work organisation attraction examines a company's overall attractiveness to potential employees, such as how enticing a position is to an individual. Job organisation attraction is a subset of job attractiveness.

In order to evaluate whether or not a candidate would accept a job offer from the organisation should one be extended, "acceptance intentions" are sought from applicants. Employees who want to work for Employer of Choice (EOC) are more likely than those who do not want to work for other organisations to choose EOC over other companies during their job search process.

Previous research has concentrated on the employer brand and typical recruitment outcomes, such as job-hunting intentions, among other things (Devina et al., 2016). Employer branding and Employee of Choice (EOC) research, on the other hand, are in short supply. As a result, it is critical to identify whether or not the employer brand plays a part in the formulation of an EOC strategy. EOCs that connect with an individual's interests and values, or organisations into which they believe they can fit into the role of EOC, according to Edwards (2009) are preferred by individuals. This match can be explained by the person-organization fit. The "person-organization fit" refers to the degree to which a person's values align with the values of the company in which they work (Kristof-Brown et al., 2005). According to this term, the compatibility between employees and the organisation is defined as a match between the views, cultures, and values held by the employees and those held by the organisation as a whole (Lauver and Kristof-Brown, 2001).

According to the findings of Bhatnagar and Srivastava's research, the person-organization fit is associated with the employer's reputation (2008). In spite of this, their research was based solely on qualitative information. This study employed the case study technique to determine the significance of the person-organization fit in the process of attracting new employees. The study looked at the need for quantitative research in this area and discovered a link between the person-organization fit and the employer brand, which was previously undiscovered.

As a result of our interest in how a person-organization fit might aid in the transfer of employer brand dimensions to the EOC, our second study objective focuses on this topic. An EOC must have created an environment that attracts and keeps the finest and brightest people in order to be eligible to be designated as such. Because of this, the subject of what it takes to become an EOC must be addressed in this context. For businesses to remain competitive, they must market their EOCs (excellent working environments).

The characteristics that must be present in order for an EOC to be developed, on the other hand, have largely been overlooked in earlier studies (Lenaghan and Eisner, 2006). According to them, just one study has looked into the relationship between employer brand determinants and employee turnover (Rampl, 2014). Employer brand was found to be influenced by two of the four variables that make up an employer's brand: workplace culture and job content, according to the findings. Also investigated was the role of employee brand emotions on the transfer of employer brand determinants into the EOC.

According to researcher's opinions, EOC has not been investigated as a factor in recruiting outcomes such as the intention to pursue (a career in the organisation) (Cable and Judge, 1996; Carless, 2005) or the likelihood of being hired.

Employer branding is a human resources method that businesses use to recruit and retain employees (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004). According to Ambler and Barrow, it is described as "a bundle of functional, financial, and psychological benefits supplied by labour and associated with the employing organisation" (1996). According to Berthon et al. (2005) and Collins and Stevens (2006), the concept of an employer's brand can be divided into two categories (2002). An employer's brand can be measured in several ways. The first step is to gain an understanding of how the organisation is regarded by its stakeholders and the broader public.

Second, employee perceptions of work attractiveness are important in determining the overall attractiveness of an employer's brand. For the purpose of developing an instrument for assessing the employer brand, three of the five aspects provided by Berthon et al. (2005) were considered and analysed. The social, economic, and development aspects of all three of these categories are important considerations to consider. As a result of the assessment of the literature, three new dimensions, namely corporate social responsibility (CSR), work-life balance, and diversity, were introduced (Hillebrandt and Ivens, 2013; Tanwar and Prasad, 2017).

An EOC can be defined as a company that motivates potential employees to work there and to stay with the company over the long term (Cable and Turban, 2003). Thus, a company is considered an EOC when it attracts and retains the best and brightest individuals.

2.6.5 Employer Branding and Need of Person-organization fit

Organizational fit can be defined as the relationship between an employee's values and beliefs and the employer's image (Lauver and Kristof-Brown, 2001). Employer-employee alignment has been studied from the perspective of the person-organization fit, which is often employed in conjunction with that research (Christiaans, 2013). People-organization fit research has shown that potential employees relate an organization's brand to their beliefs, wants and ideas; a match between the two creates higher interest in the organisation for the individual (Schneider, 1987).

Prospective employees, according to Backhaus and Tikoo (2004), evaluate and contrast the company's brand image with their own personal values and characteristics. Attracting employees based on their skills and personality traits is an important part of building a strong employer brand (Srivastava and Bhatnagar, 2010). Employer branding also serves as a technique for conveying the values of an organisation to its stakeholders, allowing employees to ensure that they fit in with that organization's culture (Parmar, 2014). While this may be true, the employer brand can attract employees who share the organization's values and culture. As a result, the employer brand helps employees determine if they are a good fit for an organisation based on their beliefs and personal abilities.

In this way, they are more likely to believe that their values and abilities are in line with the organization's values and expectations. The person-organization fit acts as a bridge between employer brand and EOC characteristics. For example, companies utilise social media to publicise their employee advantages, such as professional development programmes or international trips, among others. It is a set of digital platforms that allow individuals around the world to collaborate and share information with each other (Elefant, 2011). In social media, social networking sites (SNS) allow users to create content, engage with various public stakeholders, and build relationships with other users (Boyd and Ellison, 2008).

Networking websites such as LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube, and Instagram are all examples of SNS (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). Many people are now using social networking sites (SNS) (Greenwood, 2012). Companies can also use these sites to post job openings and descriptions. Because it allows organisations to contact a broader range of people, this is a more efficient and cost-effective technique than traditional methods (Hull, 2011).

Employers can also use it to communicate their organization's structure and culture to their target market. Among Generation Y respondents, these sites are very popular. Social media can be used to target younger demographics (Richardson and Thomas, 2012). Employers also check for current job postings on LinkedIn and Twitter, as well as other social media sites, and seek further information from current employees (Kwok, 2011). Backhaus and Tikoo (2004) suggest that enterprises must present potential employees with appropriate information so that the latter can determine their level of fit with the organisation.

Rather than having an autonomous relationship with the EOC, social media may influence the relationship between the person-organization fit and EOC. It is possible to use social media to identify and attract candidates with a better match between their personality and the organisation (Cober et al., 2004). Companies can frequently promote their principles and culture to subscribers through their career pages, social media profiles, and blogs. Employees that have access to more information have a better fit between themselves and their employer (Dineen et al., 2002). To put it another way, a good person-organization fit is a congruence between the candidate's work-related ideals and the culture of an organisation. Potential employees can learn about an organisation on social media, but they may not consider it their EOC or first-choice brand because they believe there is a mismatch between their beliefs and knowledge and those of the organisation.

2.6.6 Brand supporting behaviour

A front-line service employee's performance comprises of in-role, extra-role and anti-role behaviour. Negative front-line performance, such as whining about one's job, is an example of the latter. Employees who are under a lot of stress in their roles are more inclined to destroy the brand. As opposed to this, terminology like "brand champions" and "brand ambassadors" are used in the literature to describe high-performing employees who help customers connect with a company's brand through their own actions. When it comes to describing brand supportive behaviour, "in-role" and "out-of-role" are two terms commonly used in the literature (Erkmen and Hancer, 2015).

In-role behaviour is necessary and anticipated, and it serves as the foundation for continuous performance evaluation. If it is not shown, it has an impact on the rewards given and could lead to punishments being imposed. In contrast, extra-role behaviour, also known as organisational citizenship behaviour, is a good and optional behaviour that is not described in job descriptions, is not recognised by formal incentive systems, and does not have any negative implications if it is not carried out. Supervisors appreciate it (Dyne and Le Pine, 1998) because it improves the coordination of organisational tasks (Dyne, 1998). To attract and retain top talent, it increases the organization's ability to make it a better place to work (Unal, 2013). An additional benefit is that, in a dynamic workplace, individuals may not be able to predict all of their desired behaviours.

This can help the organisation adapt more quickly when the environment changes. Even if academics agree that organisational citizenship behaviour is a multi-dimensional performance measure, there is no consensus on the number of dimensions it has (Unal, 2013).

There are two basic categories that academics use to classify it. To begin with, there's organisational citizenship behaviour-organizational, which comprises behaviours that assist the organisation in general, such as adhering to informal standards to keep things organised (compliance and conscientiousness). As a second category, OCB-I covers actions that directly benefit individuals and indirectly benefit the business, such as aiding overworked co-workers with pertinent tasks (altruism) (Unal, 2013).

Similarly, academics disagree on the aspects of brand loyalty. Burmann and Zeplin (2005), for example, propose seven dimensions, namely helping behaviour, brand consideration, brand passion, sportsmanship, brand endorsement, self-development and brand growth. They are not the only ones who think this way. However, according to Burmann et al. (2009), it only has three dimensions: helping behaviour, brand enthusiasm, and potential for growth. Organizational citizenship behaviour and brand citizenship behaviour can be considered synonymous because of the "subtle changes" made to the organisational citizenship behaviour construct by Chang et al. (2012), while King and Grace (2012) argue that the two concepts are distinct because of the "helping behaviour, sportsmanship, and the development of brand enhancement."

Employees can become brand advocates if the company's internal branding is done well. According to King and Grace (2012) and Lohndorf and Diamantopoulos (2012), brand championship is measured in terms of employees' affective commitment and brand citizenship behaviour (extra-role behaviour) and in terms of employees' brand building behaviour (extra-role behaviour) (2014). Based on social exchange theory, it can be argued that if an organisation provides employees with the information and skills necessary to deal with their roles' inherent ambiguity and helps them better understand their roles as brand representatives, employees will, in turn, perform their in-role duties better and display more role behaviour. Research shows that internal branding has a considerable impact on employees' in-role behaviour and on their extra-role (brand/organizational citizenship) behaviour (Ozcelik and Findiki, 2014). Additionally, King and Grace (2012) show that organisational socialisation (an internal branding component) has a considerable beneficial impact on extra role (brand citizenship) behaviour.

2.7 Cultural Lens

In the wider academic literature, culture has been defined in different ways over the years, however in essence culture is associated with meaning and characteristics possessed by a group of people living and working in a society (Burton et al, 2011). Some societies tend to change their culture as distinct values and apply it across identities, beliefs, and norms, and attitudes in community practice (Halkos & Skouloudis, 2016). Culture has also been understood as the collective programming of the mind which differentiates a group of people from others such as, ethnic group, or regional group or as a nation (Hofstede, 1994). The impact of national culture on CSR has been investigated by academic scholars with the help of cultural dimensions that were developed by Geert Hofstede in 1980 and 1994. The objectives, values and set of beliefs are seen as constituent factors of national culture of a country (Hofstede, 2001). The perception of socially responsible activities and accepted principles performed by organizations tend to vary from one culture to another (Kang et al, 2016). Below presented are the cultural dimensions proposed by Hofstede:

Power Distance

This aspect of organizational culture deals with the perception of unequal distribution of power which gets readily accepted as well as expected by the employees of lower grades (Halkos & Skouloudis, 2017). The power distance score carries the converse score phenomenon with individuals having high score are the ones who will not challenge the status quo while the individuals on the lower end of the scores will be difficult to govern and they will always seek the change of power dynamics (Hofstede, 2001; Hofstede et al., 2010). Earlier studies (Ho et al., 2012; Kang et al., 2016; Thanetsunthorn & Wuthisatian, 2018) establish a direct correlation of high power distance and CSR issues. Another study of Kang et al. (2016) also reveal that high power distance multinational corporations produce better results in arena of socially responsible activities. This can be attributed to their culture of strong economic footprint and leadership. It can therefore be concluded that organizational culture with high power distance will have a mammoth support for CSR initiatives from their employees as they will have no intention or pretext to challenge it (Hofstede, 2001; Hofstede et al., 2010). The endorsement by the employees will thus always be there.

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Source: Hofstede, (2022)

Figure: Pakistan's Cultural Dimension Scores

Having a score of 55 puts Pakistan in the category of high-power distance country and the score of 14 depicts Pakistan as a country where cumulative values take hold as against the individual dispositions. The communities in high power distance societies exhibit the trait for acceptance of the hierarchical order and they do not seek any rationalization. On the contrary, people in low-power distance society seek distribution of power and they cannot be satisfied with any justification from gross inequalities. Pakistan therefore falls in the category where the power distribution is highly unequal. In addition, a high score of 50 for masculinity depicts a male dominated society, which aligns with the notion of long-term orientation. This aspect reveals the strong preference for valour, contention and material bounties as parameters for accomplishment. This makes the society highly competitive when there is a race to achieve more. At the same time, Pakistan scores mid-way in this category and it suggests a strong footprint of the opposite gender as well. The score of 70 for uncertainty avoidance is high and it depicts that Pakistanis are not comfortable with uncertainties. This can be related to the embedded financial insecurity, which an average Pakistani experience in his formative years. The primary issue in this scenario is the disposition of a society to acknowledge that future will always remain unseen.

Is there any method to control the future or the outcome of the events or should it just be allowed to happen? Countries with a high UAI are highly change resistant and unwelcoming towards unconventional approaches and solutions. On the contrary, countries with low UAI are more progressive and have a practitioners' approach in devising solutions.

Individualism versus Collectivism

This dimension relates to the degree of symbiosis that exists in a society (Hofstede Insights, 2019). As the name suggests, the individualistic societies are those where there is loose family bond and other relationships. Individuals are mostly left to their own devices to set their priorities and goals. They are in effect in charge of themselves. By contrast, a collective society has a strong family bond and other support groups where the members are interdependent on each other for the individual wellbeing of self and the family. The price for this collective protection and care is the unconditional loyalty (Hofstede, 1994). The same applies to companies as well. Any organization operating in individual society is not concerned with any cumulative benefit or social disposition unless there exists any strategic or tactical interest for the business to intervene (Ringov & Zollo, 2007). On the other hand, organizations operating in societies with absence of individualism tend to engage more in CSR (Ho et al., 2012; García-Sánchez et al., 2016; Kang et al., 2016). Companies operating in collective society are more concerned with the social impact of their business decisions (Ho et al., 2012). This arises out of inherent concern for the community, which is an essential part of the social fabric. The directions and guidance to the stakeholders in context of CSR are thus given accordingly (García-Sánchez et al., 2016).

Masculinity versus Femininity

If a society appreciates competitiveness, assertiveness or personal accomplishments, it can be termed as masculine society. The self-centred approach plays a pivotal role in this environment. This is the kind of society where the materials acquisitions are the parameters of wealth and power (Hofstede, 1980; Ringov & Zollo, 2007; Ho et al., 2012). The most important aspect of such a society is to outsmart the opponent and be the best at what you do (Hofstede Insights, 2019). On the contrary, the societies with a high degree of passion and care for others, practicing modesty and harmony, valuing relationships tend to be feminine society (Hofstede, 1980; Ringov & Zollo, 2007; Ho et al., 2012).

This environment encourages acquiring a high quality of life and not distinction (Hofstede Insights, 2019). There is plenty of anecdotal evidence to suggest that there exists a negative correlation between masculinity and CSR engagement (Ringov & Zollo, 2007; Kang et al., 2016; García-Sánchez et al., 2016; Thanetsunthorn & Wuthisatian, 2018). The organizations are less cognizant or concerned about the impact of their decisions on the society in the masculine cultures. The first and foremost priority for the businesses is to gain as much financial success as possible even if at the cost of societal interests. Profit maximization is primary motive here. In contrast, the feminine society tends to prefer a more humane approach and it values relationships. The companies in this environment focus more on cumulative well-being over monetary gains (Kang et al., 2016). The focus of corporations in these societies is enhancement of quality of life through value added initiatives (GarcíaSánchez et al., 2016).

Uncertainty Avoidance

This factor relates to the degree to which a society accepts uncertainties or ambiguities (Hofstede, 1994; Ringov & Zollo, 2007; Ho et al., 2012). People having score of uncertainty avoidance tend to stay in their comfort zone and are less enterprising. They are reluctant in exploring new ventures or getting into unforeseen situations (Hofstede, 1980; Hofstede, 1994). In contrast, people with low scores have a strong tendency to explore new ideas and situations. They have a positive attitude and tend to be more progressive by embracing unconventional approaches (Hofstede, 1980). There is significant evidence in the earlier studies that suggest that cultures with low uncertainty avoidance have a strong preference and admiration for CSR ventures (García-Sánchez et al., 2016; Halkos & Skouloudis, 2017; Thanetsunthorn & Wuthisatian, 2018). Societies with high uncertainty avoidance are less flexible and thus more change resistant in every dimension (Ringov & Zollo, 2007). Whereas there exists a high degree of cooperation and engagement by stakeholders across the spectrum in context of CSR initiatives in societies with low uncertainty avoidance as the environment is more conducive to change (García-Sánchez et al., 2016).

Long-term Orientation

The long-term orientation depicts the society's adherence to the future, decisions pertaining to long economic sustainability and tenacity (Hofstede et al., 2010; Halkos & Skouloudis, 2017). In contrast, a society with short-term orientation is less flexible and adheres more to the age-old customs and traditions (Hofstede, 1994). They focus on immediate gains and results while confining their focus pegging their parameters of happiness to the present (Thanetsunthorn & Wuthisatian, 2018). Evidently, the high engagement of CSR correlates with society having preference for long term orientation (García-Sánchez et al., 2016; Halkos & Skouloudis, 2017). It is a well-established fact that organizations having long term orientation are not solely focused on quarterly financial statements but they intend to be an essential component of the society at large with the intention to contribute for the welfare of the community they operate (Hofstede Insights, 2019). The stakeholders of such companies have a larger perspective of societal gains as against the monetary proceeds. They believe in decisions, which have a positive impact on the environment, and the societal progress is of paramount importance to them.

Indulgence versus restraint

This particular dimension deals with the degree of checking the impulsivity of the society. The context in this dimension is all about self-control over desires. Weak control corresponds to indulgence while strong control depicts restraint (Halkos & Skouloudis, 2017; Hofstede Insights, 2019). Members of indulgent societies tend to seek happiness irrespective of consequential costs. And this act often results in lower degree of moral order with regard to the societal norms (Hofstede et al., 2010). On the contrary, people hailing from restrained environments staunchly believe in suppression of happiness and tend to abide by the social norms even at the expense of compromising individual happiness and quality of life (Hofstede et al., 2010; Halkos & Skouloudis, 2017). There is no considerable amount of literature available on this subject. However, there is one study by Thanetsunthorn and Wuthisatian (2018) which analyses indulgence and restrain in context of corporate readiness to be actively engaged in promotion of socially responsible activities.

Since the people hailing from societies that are more indulgent have stronger inclination for moral order, it may affect the CSR decisions in a negative way. This would be extremely detrimental for the direct stakeholders (Thanetsunthorn & Wuthisatian, 2018). Moreover, the indulgent societies would also not heed to environmental activities and welfare of the society as a whole.

2.8 Conceptual Model

Figure 14 Conceptual Model

Source: Ahmad, (2019)

The extraction and development of all the variables included in the model has been achieved through a process in which the literature review findings, theoretical underpinnings, context and background information along with the scope of research objectives and questions were considered. To keep the conceptual model relevant, the variables selected are embedded in the rationale and motivation of this study which is linked with the objectives and aim of the research. Stakeholder theory, CSR framework and conceptual evaluation of employer branding concept has led to the development of these variables.

Since this study is about investigating the impact of environmental CSR on employer branding due to which the conceptual model starts with the input of two important variables i.e., environmental CSR policies and internal/ external communication of the CSR policies and activities. This model is reflecting that when an organization develops their respective CSR policy document including policies on environmental CSR, only then there arises the need of communicating and disclosing it internally and externally. Therefore, with the help of CSR policies, firms can manage their reputation and branding. In case, if an organization has not formulated its CSR policies, then their chances of achieving, sustaining and improving employer branding reduces significantly.

This reflects that an imperative pre-requisite in the conceptual model presented is the presence/undertaking of environmental CSR policies or related policy document. It is important to note here that environmental CSR embeds specific issues and concerns such as, water, energy, biodiversity, recycling and carbon emissions and few other factors. Therefore, this study will focus precisely on the presence of environmental CSR policies which are then required to be communicated. Therefore, the input of this model indicates that organizations are required or remain in need of communicating about their environmental CSR initiatives and activities using different set of communication modes/tools. This presence and dissemination of the nature/scope of environmental CSR policies initiates the process of achieving employer branding by engaging employees in the process. Internal and external communication methods can be different.

The second part of this model is the process which is driven by and a continuation of the input i.e., self-categorization, moral identity, social identity and behavioural characteristics of millennial employees (existing and potential).

If the input components are not present, then this process can either cease to exist or it can be negative significantly because if information about organization's CSR policies/efforts is not available then employees will not be in a position to form their opinion objectively which then reflects their perception about employer branding and reputation. All these four factors included in the 'process' stage of conceptual model can vary frequently from one employee to another because how an employee identifies himself/ herself with her/his organization relies on the way or the extent to which they feel a sense of belongingness via self- evaluations. Self-evaluations of employees who are currently working for a company and for employees who are not working for any company may also tend to differ.

This shows that internal and external communication factor included in the 'input' stage of conceptual model is imperative for organizations that are aiming to maintain and improve their employer branding. Since moral identity describes individual differences in moral characteristics given that individuals can differ in terms of the degree to which being moral is central to their self-concepts, therefore moral identity will be a major decisive or determining factor during the 'process' stage of this conceptual model. For the purpose of driving moral identity positively organizations have to make sure that effective and systematic internal and external communication is in place because moral identity heavily relies on individual personality traits and values of an individual which cannot be shaped to a large extent via certain communication tactics. Organizational awareness regarding positively influencing moral identity of potential and existing employees becomes essential in this regard.

Social identity is about perceptual, emotional, and affective belongingness of individuals which means that organizations can address social identity by initiating and communicating their CSR activities/policies which can also to a certain degree positively impact the moral identity because moral identity is inter-linked with social identity. Characteristics of millennial employees (existing and potential) is the fourth variables included in the 'process' stage which can significantly shape or affect the nature of social and moral identity an employee tends to possess or develop. Therefore, it gets important for organizations to understand the characteristics of millennial employees as they belong to a certain generation (generation Y) and usually possess certain characteristics i.e., confident, smart, rule followers, optimistic, and pressured.

The next stage of this conceptual model is 'output' which consists of two variable factors i.e., organizational identification and stakeholder management. It can be mentioned here that both these factors may work for existing employees both effectively irrespective of the fact that an individual is employed or is searching for a job because organizations have to use internal and external communications both for effectively disclosing and disseminating their CSR activities/policies. Organizational identification is defined as the extent to which a person senses oneness or sameness with an organization which can be a simple process for existing employees. The relationship between CSR activities and organizational identification have been studied significantly in literature and social identity theory is widely applied to explain the relationship between CSR and organizational identification.

This means that the strong presence of social identity can drive or ensure the achievement of organizational identification and this social identity relies on the presence and communication of environmental CSR policies/activities. This explains the functioning of this conceptual model from first stage (input) to third (output). The achievement of organizational identification after the process stage will also fulfils the underlying concept of stakeholder theory proposed by Freeman, (1984) i.e., the responsive of the organizations towards its stakeholders and in this study the key stakeholder under consideration are the existing and potential employees. If this output stage is positive, then it can lead to positive or improved employer branding.

2.8.1 Internal and External Communications

With the recent attention towards CSR, CSR communication had become much important for the organizations as well as for keeping all the stakeholders informed about the organizational CSR activities. CSR term is often used as an interchange with sustainable development, social enterprise, corporate ethics, triple bottom line, corporate governance, corporate citizenship, etc. (Anuradha and Bagali, 2015). The common aspect linking all these terminologies is to compel the organizations for paying attention to the environmental, economic, social and ethical aspects in an organization (Crane and Glozer, 2016).

CSR carry the potential to influence the stakeholders positively when they are aware of the social activities being carried out by the organization. Coombs and Holladay (2013) believe that effective communication is necessary for the organizations to catch and sustain the stakeholders' interest towards CSR. Bayoud and Kavanagh (2012) share similar information that the CSR carries the potential to enhance the organizational image in the market as well as attract the investors only if it is communicated to them positively. It implies that effective communications related to CSR are equally important for the organizations to gain benefits along with the CSR actions.

Despite the CSR area, it is the responsibility of the organizations to decide that either they want to engage themselves in appropriate communication strategies, community empowerment, charitable giving, etc. It tends to support the companies in sustaining their focus on the right area; otherwise, they are unable to achieve desired success (Mishra, 2017).

Amaladoss et al. (2013) recommend here that the organizations need to focus on effective communications to ensure gaining positive results from their CSR activities. This type of communication also tends to carry importance for the organization in boosting its image in the business market. There are multiple benefits delivered to the organization with effective CSR communication. For instance, it could influence the stakeholders' perception positively. For example, the consumers become brand ambassadors for the organization sharing its positive aspects with other individuals for attracting them towards the company (Crane and Glozer, 2016). CSR communication benefits the organization in sharing its concern and key messages with all the relevant stakeholders for keeping them aligned at the same target (Coombs and Holladay, 2012). The positive word of mouth marketing carried out by the organization customer benefits the organization in attracting more customers towards the company (Anuradha and Bagali, 2015; Coombs and Holladay, 2012).

In case, if the customer delivers the negative word of mouth related to the organizational image, then it becomes difficult for the organization to sustain its image positively in the business market. CSR communication tends to support the organization in multiple manners including the effective management of all the stakeholders' expectations to achieve the targeted positive results (Porter and Kramer, 2002; Wang and Berens, 2014).

Related to the rising growth of the CSR concept and understanding amongst the people, the organizations must ensure carrying out their CSR activities positively to reflect the stakeholders' interest and expectations from the organization. For the same reason, organizations need to come with a proper CSR Communications Strategy.

Different scholars (Crane and Glozer, 2016; Oberseder et al., 2013) recommend the organizations specify the number of stakeholders to be targeted by them for managing their CSR activities for achieving the desired amount of success in the business market and establishing strong relations with the stakeholders as well. Related to the CSR communications channel, Kim and Ferguson (2014) defined two key categories including controlled and uncontrolled media channels. “Company controlled channels include the ones like social media outlets, newsletters, advertisements, brochures, company websites, etc.; were the uncontrolled media channels including experts blog, news media and other social media channels” (p. 3). The organizations avoid carrying out aggressive marketing related to their CSR activities as it might create scepticism amongst the stakeholders reducing the organizational credibility; therefore, they prefer that the CSR communication channels must be used differently by the organizations related to the interest and characteristics of specific stakeholders.

2.8.2 Organizational Identification, Social Identity

Organization identification refers to the similarities and differences existing within an organization itself (Ashforth et al., 2008). Kim et al., (2010) state that there is a strong relationship existing between organizational identification and CSR activities. The key theory for explaining the relation between organizational identification and CSR is Social Identity Theory (Kim et al., 2010). Taking value from this theory, the individuals determine their identities about the interaction carried out with other people in different social environments. They also attempt for achieving and sustain positive social identity up to the maximum extent. Similarly, the individuals attempt to connect them with the groups carrying prestigious images for improving their self-worth and esteem needs (Tajfel and Turner, 1979). Therefore, the organization prestigious image tends to play a key role in developing organizational image.

The individuals are inclined towards the organizations having a positive or attractive image (Pratt, 1998). It means that the CSR activities support the organization in improving its image and attracting key stakeholders. It also enhances the employees' desire for connecting them with the organization.

The self-categorization theory explains the identification of an individual with an organization. This theory informs that the individuals classify themselves in different categories based on their belonging through self-evaluation (Turner, 1986). Organizational membership forms a key aspect of an individual's identity; therefore, self-evaluation like organizational identification is affected significantly by the values and practices of the organization. It means that that CSR practices could foster the self-categorization process of an individual positively because it provides an opportunity to the individual for sharing the same attributes contributing to the strengthening of one's self-concept (Brammer and Mellahi, 2015).

In other terms, CSR participation could prove to be effective for the organization to raise awareness amongst the individuals for evaluating their desired behaviour and identity with the organization. The individuals involved actively within an organization can identify more aspects of the organization supporting them in realizing and validating their actions (Turker, 2009). It means that individual participation ensures and strengthens the organizational related identity (Arnett et al., 2003).

2.8.3 Stakeholder Management and Employees

According to a recent study, an organization's long-term viability may be dependent on getting the cooperation of a wide range of stakeholders (Bhattacharya et al, 2009). As a result of the organization's aims and achievements, stakeholders include any groups or individuals who can affect or are influenced by those goals and achievements (Freeman, 1984). Primary notion of this theory is that organisations' capacity to incorporate the expectations and requirements of stakeholders into their business strategy is vital to their success and survival because stakeholders provide critical resources and returns to the company's bottom line (Roeck and Delobbe, 2011).

It is necessary to strike a balance between the interests of stakeholders and the needs of those in charge of managing the organization's actions, and this must be done. Employees have traditionally been regarded as the most valuable asset in a company's operations. Due to the fact that they are both impacted by and affected by their employment, employees play a significant role in the success or failure of an organisation (Azim, 2016).

When it comes to corporate social responsibility and its stakeholders, employees are the primary focus. According to Collier and Esteban (2008), an organization's ability to carry out CSR efforts is dependent on the responsiveness and participation of its employees in those initiatives. It is as a result of this that performing effective CSR initiatives necessitates the participation of employees now more than ever before. Different research studies revealed that the long-term sustainability of an organization takes a great value from the regular cooperation coming from the stakeholders' side (Bhattacharya et al., 2009). Taking value from the Stakeholder Theory, the stakeholder is the individuals affected by the organizational targets or actions (Freeman, 1984).

This theory focusses that the organizational existence taking great value from its capability to manage the stakeholders' expectations as they tend to offer key resources to the organization required for their survival (Roeck and Delobbe, 2011). Therefore, organizations need to balance their activities and stakeholders' expectations positively. It is no doubt that employees tend to form the backbone of an organization. Therefore, they tend to play a key role in organizational success (Azim, 2016). It compels the business organizations to offer a special place to the stakeholders within the context of CSR. Collier and Esteban (2008) also said in this regard that an organization is highly dependent on the employees' response for engaging within the CSR activities to ensure effective delivery. It means that the employees' connection tends to play a key role in the CSR activities implementation.

2.8.4 Environmental CSR

Environmental CSR is focused on reducing the damaging effects being made by the business processes in the areas related to waste management, business travel policies, energy usage, water usage, emissions, and recycling (Padilla-Lozano and Collazzo, 2021).

The organization can classify their CSR activities into environmental, internal and external categories. The interior classification in this regard comprises employee health, safety, and work-life balance. The external responsibilities involve the cultural and social actions being taken by the organization in the local community. It also involves the regular actions by the organization to improve the social development and local community. The third category in this regard is Environmental Responsibility. This category of CSR includes multiple actions like energy usage, water usage, emissions control, and efficiency (Jones, 2021).

The emphasis of the organization over the environmental aspect refers to the Environmental Corporate Social Responsibility Activity i.e., ECSR. There is a general perception related to the negative impact being made by the organizations especially the energy related firms on the environment. The key reason for the same is bulk industrial production affects the ecological environment adversely (Carroll, 2021). Many business organizations across the globe are taking different actions for combating this issue positively through the implementation of the ECSR concept and strategies. The case organization in this study make use of voluntary practices to support environmental sustainability apart from legislative compliance. Some studies also divided ECSR into different categories including active ECSR, voluntary ECSR, passive ECSR, and obligatory ECSR. Active ECSR covers all the activities undertaken by the organizations apart from the legislative requirements to support environmental sustainability (Munro, 2020).

The passive ECSR refer to the activities by which the organization puts a minimum effort to comply effectively with all the necessary legislative requirements (Sellitto et al, 2020). The obligatory CSR is similar to the passive one; however, the effort level in this case by the organization to comply with the legislative requirements is quite positive. This study focuses on proactive CSR that is quite important especially in the energy sector because of its high negative impacts on the environment. The reason is the large CO₂ emission for the generation of electricity with the usage of coal fuel. The European Union countries are also taking substantial actions for shifting to green energy by imposing different bans as an attempt to reduce the CO₂ emissions; however, this sector had still not reached eco-friendly features (Munro, 2020a).

Therefore, the study believes that the involvement of the organization in the pro-environmental factors is quite necessary within this sector. The organizational board is mainly responsible for developing and implementing the environmental policy of the organization by managing suitable conditions. It allows all the team members to engage with each other to benefit the organization in achieving its environmental goal positively (Van Zanten et al, 2020).

2.8.5 Organizational Identification, Social Identity

An individual's level of identification with an organisation is defined as the extent to which they believe they are a member of the group (Ashforth et al, 2008). Numerous studies have indicated that corporate social responsibility (CSR) actions have a significant impact on an organization's brand recognition (Kim et al, 2010). Organizational identification and corporate social responsibility (CSR) are well explained by the social identity theory, which provides a thorough explanation of the link. According to social identity theory, people perceive themselves as a product of their social relationships.

People strive for and work hard to retain a positive sense of social identity. As a result, people tend to identify themselves as members of organisations that have a prestigious reputation, which can help them feel better about themselves and meet their esteem needs (Tajfel and Turner, 1979).

As a result, a company's distinctive image serves as a source of organizational identity for the business. employees are more inclined to identify with their employer if they believe the company is well-regarded and has a positive image in the marketplace (Pratt, 1998). Socially responsible organisations, on the other hand, strive to improve the company's public image while also recruiting new consumers and partners. Because of this, CSR programmes may raise an employee's desire to identify and identify with the company, hence increasing their desire to identify and identify with the company.

In contrast, the notion of self-categorization helps explain why a person feels a sense of belonging at his or her place of employment. Those who evaluate themselves in terms of their own self-worth are said to categorise themselves into groups with whom they identify or identify more strongly (Turner, 1986).

A significant part of one's identity is derived from one's affiliation with a particular organization, and as a result, positive organizational values and practises can have an impact on one's perception of one's own self-worth. As a result, corporate social responsibility practises can assist employees in categorising themselves by allowing them to connect with companies that share similar identity features, which in turn enhances their self-concept. It has been established that organizational identity has a favourable relationship with corporate social responsibility (Brammer and Mellahi, 2015).

Having the opportunity to become aware of their employer's desired conduct and to be able to compare their own identity with their organisation through participation in CSR provides an invaluable learning experience for employees. Individuals who are actively involved in their organisations are more likely to feel a strong sense of belonging to them, and their role identities will be fulfilled and validated as a result of their actions (Turker, 2009).

2.9 Chapter Summary

This chapter has presented key theoretical underpinnings of the research study and has critically discussed diverse concepts involved. Stakeholder theory and organizational identity theory have formed the basis of this research and have emphasized on the consideration of employees and natural environment as central stakeholders. CSR as a concept has been understood as such practices, behaviours and policies that are directed towards the well-being of the stakeholders. Organizations are using CSR for gaining competitive advantage in the market. Millennial employees have been presented as having a distinct reputation as compared to other generation employees especially in the context of sensitivity and priority given to the natural environment and CSR activities. Communication and strategy have been presented as key factors that are driving the CSR performance of the companies especially the MNCs are taking CSR practices seriously because of pressure from international agencies. Employer branding has been presented in this chapter as a concept which develops the reputation and image of a company in the eye of employees. Employer branding as a concept has been validated in the literature and is mentioned that CSR performance does implicate on the employer attractiveness.

Companies today are pursuing internal branding for exhibiting their socially responsible image to the employees which in turn helps them to retain the competent staff. CSR is about utilizing the company resources and it has not been researched extensively in the literature that how CSR functions at the time of a crisis such as COVID-19. Lastly, this chapter has presented conceptual framework which has been developed in the light of literature review findings and scope of research objectives.

3. Chapter Three: Research Methodology

A detailed review of the contemporary literature and the precise context of the study undertaken (which is to investigate the impact of Environmental CSR practices on employer branding amongst the millennial employees in telecom sector of Pakistan) is presented in the previous chapters. This section is now presenting discussion about the chosen research methodology along with its justification, merits and demerits. Moreover, the motivation of choosing the context of Pakistan was also presented previously. The justification of choosing the case study method in this study is also being presented. The data collection process is also a key highlight of this chapter i.e., the process or phases of data collection experienced for the purpose of achieving the contribution to body of knowledge which this thesis intended to achieve. Research strategy that is being used in this thesis will be presented in the chapter along with a discussion on the chosen research philosophies. This chapter is also presenting the explanation which can justify the adoption of particular research methodology in the thesis. Chosen research design is also being presented in this chapter along with associated justifications. Whereas ethical considerations and data collection tools are also being included in this chapter followed by a brief concluding summary in the end of this chapter.

3.1 Research Philosophies

Saunders et al, (2011) proposed the ‘research onion’ which gives a simplified yet structured way of developing and understanding the ideas of a research paradigm that researchers can use in their respective contexts. The figure below is indicating the ‘research onion’:

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2014) "Research Methods for Business Students" 6th edition, Pearson Education Limited

Figure 15 The Research Onion

Source: Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, (2014)

In this research, an important step is to outline the underpinning research philosophy because it facilitates a particular direction for undertaking the vital stages of collecting data, analysing data and then interpreting the data. Positivism and interpretivism are two key philosophies that social research can follow with both philosophies widely acclaimed. Natural science tends to widely use positivism approach because it examines the facts and uses rigorous measuring tools (Burns, 2011). Positivists view reality as independent of human beings and it keeps the ontological argument separate from epistemological question about the nature of reality and how reality can be discovered. Despite of its popularity, a key criticism on positivism states that it lacks flexibility and often it is not successful in seizing the processes of how things actually work and how things actually are (Lincoln et al, 2011; Easterby-Smith et al., 2008). Moreover, observations are not taken into consideration significantly by the positivism which restricts the effectiveness of data collection process.

For these mentioned reasons, positivist approach is not being adopted in this research thesis especially because this thesis is depending heavily on the interpretation and observation of the data that will be collected from human participants reflecting on their experiences.

3.1.1 Adopting Interpretivism

Interpretivism has been adopted as research philosophy in this thesis for which reasoning will be presented in this section. Bailey, (2010) have mentioned three key categories of qualitative research i.e., collaborative social research, social anthropology and interpretivism. Since this study intends to collect information from different telecommunication companies and employees working in those companies due to which the concept of multiple realities becomes suitable and provides a rationale to use interpretivism.

The subjective opinion and aspects of human activities have been stressed by the interpretivism and that too by considering the meaning instead of the measurement of the social phenomena (Crossan, 2003). Therefore, the particular contexts of the phenomena are taken into account by the interpretivist approach and while providing the interpretation of data, this approach makes use of contextual understanding. Since the telecom companies in Pakistan are working with different set of policies and approaches due to which it is important to extract the respective contextual understanding of their employees which makes interpretivism suitable for this thesis. If the contextual differences and distinctive nature of telecom companies is not taken into consideration, it can restrict the insights to be found by this thesis.

Qualitative and interpretivism approaches have facilitated meaningful contributions towards stakeholder research which covers employees and consumers (Kumar, 2014; Glesne, 2013). Examining employees as stakeholders is a key academic discipline underpinned by this research and gives an element of justification towards interpretivism and ultimately will align with the selection of qualitative method. The reason why selection of a relevant research methodology needs to be aligned with a particular scientific research philosophy is because it helps in developing an understanding regarding how the knowledge is gathered and research can be comprehended (Beverland and Lindgreen, 2010).

Moreover, it enables the linking of academic theories with the realities extracted from the application of primary data collection tools (Collins, 2010). It can be noted from the outermost layer of research onion that interpretivism generate subjective results which is the reason why this approach is closely related with the nature and subject of this thesis. Silverman, (2009) stated that interpretivism acknowledges, along with other people's views, individuals use their views for exploring the ideas and for understanding cultural existence and importantly acknowledges the opinions of people that are valuable to them. Therefore, a subjective reality is determined by the knowledge results of interpretivism which can be used by the researcher for understanding truths and comparing the key findings.

Naturalist research methods are at the base of interpretivism philosophy which provides precision to the approach. It has been stated by Scotland, (2012) that when the intention is to improve the understanding level about any situation of the phenomenon, then studying it in natural context becomes highly desirable i.e., by considering the viewpoint of the participants especially when previous understanding of the participants about the phenomenon is not the basis of research. The research topic of environmental CSR and employer branding in this thesis is not based on the previous viewpoints of employees working in the telecom industry, moreover, the natural context of these companies is to be explored in this thesis irrespective of their country of origin, size and scale of operations. Therefore, these factors not only provide the justification of using interpretivism, also it will assist in drawing highly relevant and precise findings.

The interpretivism philosophy believes that by using the reality (which knowledge cannot change easily) the assumptions possessed by the respective researcher will be integrated across the whole research process (Blumer, 1969). Since the underlying objectives of this thesis is to analyse the perceptions of millennial employees about environmental CSR and employer branding in Pakistan, and to determine the influence being exhibited by environmental CSR practices on millennial employees. Therefore, by observing the reality about these objectives through interpretivism, the researcher can present a concrete picture especially by challenging researcher's own assumptions.

Therefore, for making the analysis and discussion critical, the interpretivism philosophy is appearing suitable in this thesis.

Moreover, interpretivism encourages the researcher to engage in detailed dialogues with the respondents (Willis, 2013; Rubin and Babbie, 2014). This aspect makes interpretivism suitable for this thesis because there are few concepts to be covered in the interview questions which will naturally require to engage in detailed dialogue with respondents to make sure they are understanding and answering adequately.

Social construction of the reality is embedded in the interpretivist research which reflects that given the new settings, relationships and cultures, this social construction can change, and achievement of truth can become difficult based on objective reality (Goldkuhl, 2010; Wahyuni, 2012). This can be a challenge in this thesis to contain the information and responses in such way that considers the element of variation in the social construction of reality because cultural dimensions of organizations can implicate on its employees.

Written records of the conversation/ dialogues occurred between the researcher and the participants along with conducting persuasive arguments are two significant criteria that can be used for examining the research when adopting an interpretivist view (Mills et al, 2006; (Baxter and Jack, 2008). Therefore, for achieving the research aim which involves the interaction with the millennial employees, the interpretivist approach has been adopted. By doing so, it will be probable to obtain new insights by evaluating the research problem in a unique perspective and explaining the interaction of variables in a new light (Babones, 2015). Employer branding and environment CSR concepts require the application of an interpretivist approach because it facilitates collecting views and hearing about the feelings of the participants regarding the concepts under investigation. The figure presented below is indicating about the reasons why interpretive paradigm is chosen in this study:

Beliefs	Interpretivist Paradigm	Positivist Paradigm
Epistemology	The findings of research cannot prevail without researcher	Existence of research findings is possible without researcher
Ontology	Realities that are constructed socially	A single objective reality exists is the basic belief
Methodology	Use of unstructured interviews and observations	Structured interviews, surveys and questionnaires

*Table 1
Justifying
Chosen*

the

Methodology

Source: Creswell, (2014)

As mentioned earlier, an interpretive paradigm is being used in this study mainly because it allows the use of social construction of the reality which can differ from one participant to another and ultimately can develop results that are without any distinct pattern which is imperative for validating a positivist approach. For validating the interpretive studies, the discourses available in specific areas needs to be considered by the subject being investigated (Wilson, 2010; Ritchie et al, 2013). The views and opinions of the subject are constructed by the social realities which makes it highly subjective in nature. Since the positivist approach resides in the presence of a single reality which is objective in nature and the subjectivity embedded in the research topic of this thesis especially with millennials' perception about employer branding makes it difficult to use positivist approach. Interpretive view is being implemented in this thesis under the interpretivist paradigm which is appearing as the most compatible paradigm for this thesis.

The scope of this research is also indicating the feasibility of interpretive paradigm because it will assist in understanding the research problem in an enhanced manner in the real-world context. Thus, the research phenomenon in this thesis has both social and organizational focus which signifies the appropriateness of the interpretive approach.

Since shared and subjective meaning has become the main concern of this thesis due to which the interpretive point of view is constituting the central philosophical position. A key assumption considered by the interpretive paradigm is referred as transactional epistemology which provides an assumption that what we know and understand cannot be changed easily (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). Certain beliefs will already be possessed by the researcher regarding the precise object under investigation and such beliefs are not expected to be changed easily because the understanding of the researcher depends on these beliefs. In relation to employer branding, environmental CSR and millennial employees, each of these variables require the conclusions to be aligned with the views of participants i.e., hearing what participants have to say and then drawing inferences for the analysis.

In addition, environmental CSR concept revolves around understanding and knowing the social context and the aim in interpretive research is to explain and explore factors linked with a specific social setting instead of proving any hypotheses (Fletcher, 2017). These arguments and the developed understanding are indicating the suitability of interpretivist approach for this thesis. Next section will discuss the adoption of a relevant research approach and its fit with the research paradigm and context.

3.2 Research Approach (Inductive)

This section will exhibit the decision of selecting the research approach as research philosophy is already decided in the previous. Clarity on the selection of research approach is also recommended by (Saunders et al, 2014). Deductive and inductive are two prominent approaches available for researchers and are widely used (Bryman and Bell, 2007).

3.2.1 Selecting Inductive and Leaving Deductive Approach

The deductive approach is about starting the research with sufficient information in hand about the concept under investigation for the purpose of developing research hypotheses which are then evaluated in an empirical manner (Saunders et al, 2009). For developing hypothesis and a theory, researchers tend to rely on the available literature when following positivist approach which then is required to be validated with the help of relevant statistical evaluations (Riermer et al, 2012).

The flow of deductive approach is from general to specific which ends with revision of the theory proposed. On the other hand, a real-life observation is used as a starting point in the inductive approach by undertaking a certain phenomenon and then a theory is built (Bryman and Bell, 2007). This approach starts from specific and then becomes general making it entirely different from the deductive approach.

3.3 Process Behind Selection

Since the inductive approach is being used in this study, it is important to understand that why this decision has been made. The focus of researcher started with generic observations on environmental side of CSR practices and their influence on employer branding mediated by perceptions of millennial employees which is a specific focus has enabled this decision. By extracting information from relevant participant individuals, the intention will be to determine themes which will assist in the formulation of theories in an inductive manner (Neuman, 2008).

For the purpose of building the conceptual model, the researcher evaluated current theories that are relevant with the research topic which is helpful towards strengthening the viewpoint of this study. The questions designed for collecting the data were aligned with literature review findings and research objectives after which data was collected. After this stage, a general theme revolving around the topic was extracted as considerable data was available to do so. This led the researcher work on determining patterns in the collected data and on developing a theory which has the potential of explaining those patterns. Therefore, inductive approach being the primary approach has allowed significant themes drawn from the data to facilitate research findings without the limitations that structural methodologies can impose. Next section is highlighting the research methods that are available and the one that is being used in this study along with its justification.

3.4 Research Methods (Qualitative versus Quantitative)

Qualitative and quantitative are two widely used and acclaimed research methods available in literature which researchers can use in line with their research requirements (O’Leary, 2010). Saunders et al, (2014) have differentiated both these research methods by stating the main distinguishing factor i.e., non-numeric (text-based, words) and numeric data (based on numbers).

Qualitative method is being used in this study for which the reasons are to be presented in this section.

3.4.1 Quantitative Research

This method lays its reliance on statistical and mathematical analysis of the numeric data in the light of which the results of study are then understood (Kumar, 2014). A positivist approach is normally adopted by quantitative method and large data size is aimed to be gathered in this method. Therefore, this method is not feasible for application in this thesis because this study is making use of interpretivist approach and relying on social construction of the reality instead of numbers and statistical analysis.

3.4.2 Qualitative Research

Interpretations of dialogues and textual data is the main source of qualitative data analysis instead of relying on mathematical results (Somekh and Lewin, 2011). This method usually tends to take small size of respondents as compared to quantitative method and embedded the objective of gaining detailed insights about the research problem under consideration. According to Yin, (2014) qualitative method is considered feasible and appropriate when such topics are being investigated that are relatively new or when not much knowledge already exists regarding the research problem. This aspect is indicating the relevance and fit of qualitative method with the research thesis under consideration as environmental focus of CSR in a developing country Pakistan is a relatively new topic and little is known about this area. Moreover, the research objectives and questions of this study can be addressed with the help of inductive research position making qualitative method feasible. The need of qualitative data is evident in this study as well as the integration of grounded theory because the use of grounded theory is a significant characteristic of the inductive approach. With the integration of grounded theory, it becomes imperative for the researcher to conduct research without any biases and with an open mind especially when collecting and interpreting results.

3.4.3 Justification for the use of Qualitative Research

Participation of the researcher is required in interpretivist methodology, the way it is performed relies significantly on the use of qualitative data collection and analysis tools. The researcher is intending to conduct data collection process by asking questions to the respondents directly, hence making sure that participation is achieved. This participation is imperative because evaluation, verification, interpretation and description are four research objectives that in the view of Bryman and Bell, (2011) can be attained and addressed effectively with the application of qualitative methods. This thesis has a particular requirement of using interpretation and description for addressing the research aim which is to investigate the impact of Environmental CSR practices on employer branding amongst the millennial employees in telecom sector of Pakistan. Therefore, the participation is to be ensured for various reasons which will enhance the data collection and analysis process of this thesis being a qualitative study.

Interviews and focus group discussions are prominent methods of collecting qualitative data and often these methods provide the opportunity of collecting data in a holistic manner. Ultimately these methods allow the achievement of a deeper explanation and enables identification of underlying factors behind the particular phenomena (Mertens, 2009). Such data collection is referred as exploratory in nature which reflects that not much literature is currently available in the specific context of a research topic. The developing country context of this study is a new location in the perspective of environmental CSR topic and little information is currently available in literature about this topic. When an inductive approach is adopted in a study, it strictly means that exploration of the topic in depth is the main purpose of research questions that have been established.

Moreover, it essentially intends to add to the contemporary body of knowledge about the research area under consideration by gathering new views and insights instead of intending to prove the existing body of knowledge wrong or right. Most of the research objectives established earlier in the study are aiming to evaluate factors that are external in nature and are based on the opinion of millennial employees. The attainment of these objectives can be facilitated by extracting benefits out of qualitative methods making quantitative method less feasible and qualitative method highly feasible because quantitative results will be invalidated in this scenario.

The respective experiences, education level, job roles and competence level of participants are diverse which means each participant will comprehend the interview questions being asked in their unique manner. This means that in a qualitative study, the researcher can increase his/ her participation which will make it easy for the research to assist the respective participants in line with the conversations' central points (Creswell, 2009). This will enable the viewing of subjective reality within the required context of the study.

3.5 Research Strategy

Different research strategies are available in literature from which researchers can take benefits depending on the nature and context of their respective studies. Different schools of thought have produced distinct research strategies with the help of particular theories that falls under each school of thought (McMillan and Schumacher, 2010). Several research strategies have been studied by Bryman and Bell, (2003) and it has been concluded by them that the nature of research problem and its external influences makes one strategy efficient for a particular study. However, in general it is not simple to refer any strategy better than the rest.

An exploratory research strategy has been adopted in this study because it assists in determining current gaps in the literature and also it employs primary method of research for adding to the body of knowledge and research. For addressing the research objectives of this thesis, a specific focal point has been chosen after identifying gaps in the contemporary literature which will require further exploration and reasoning. Exploratory research embeds a key characteristic which is about seeking to evaluate and understand opinions and beliefs, this aspect is aligned with the interpretive philosophy indicating relevance of exploratory research for this thesis (Buchanan and Bryman, 2007).

Within the realm of exploratory research, this study is adopting case study approach which is a challenging approach for researchers in social science (Crowther and Lancaster, 2013). Simple qualitative research method is feasible for this thesis and how is being presented in the next section.

Access Issues

While using case study method, a key challenge is to make sure that the researcher has access to the organizations that has been selected especially when the researcher is facing travel problems and geographical location of the organizations is far away (Lewis et al, 2003; Robert, 1995). This aspect is important because the time spent by the researcher with the participants of relevant organizations can impact on the way data is collected. Moreover, for developing the comfort level and understanding about the data collection process the issue of time and geographical location becomes important to consider. Therefore, a key challenge faced by the researcher in this thesis during data collection was lesser control over time. The selection of case organizations was a well-thought-out process because there are five telecom companies operating in Pakistan i.e., four MNCs and one local private-public partnership company.

Therefore, the researcher decided to include a mix of local and MNCs in data collection process for obtaining a comprehensive view and understanding of the telecom industry in terms of employer branding and environmental CSR relationship. The official websites and Facebook pages of these companies were accessible due to which the researcher was able to draw a meaningful comparison among these telecom companies. Apart from this, the researcher had to rely heavily on his personal contacts and social networks for accessing the millennial employees working in these companies because through social media platforms the response was not encouraging.

The use of e-mails was also not providing desired results and response, after which the researcher relied completely on using his personal contacts for gaining access to the millennial employees and convincing them to participate in the data collection process with no pressure. Since this study is focused on millennial employees due to which more time was incurred in accessing the right employees and to be able to identify the millennials working in these companies was a challenge in itself. Once the communication with potential respondents was established, a briefing about the nature and intention of this research study was presented to them. Key emphasis was given on the aspect that how their participation will be helpful towards the achievement of research aim and objectives that this study has established.

Moreover, the importance of their opinion and the inclusion of their company in this study was explained to them which gave motivation to some employees and for many of them it was not good enough motivation. The number of potential respondents contacted and the number of respondents who agreed to participate in the data collection process were significantly different i.e., more than 50 millennial employees were contact directly and through social network, whereas only 30 employees agreed to participate.

Data Collection and Analysis

Purposive (non-probability) sampling approach has been adopted in this study. Sample size was intended to stay between 30-40 interviews because this is the average sample size used by the doctoral studies conducted in recent years using similar research methods. The researcher consulted several research articles and doctoral theses for this purpose and found this sample size figure adequate. However, 30 interviews were conducted in the end given the limitation of time, resources and especially due to the significant impact generated by the COVID-19 factor.

Existing millennial employees of telecom industry were taken as sample respondents because it will allow the researcher to generalize the findings and understand the thought process or preferences of millennial employees. Interview questions developed initially were between 15-20 as the intention was to cover the important aspects presented in the research objectives and literature review. However, after conducting pilot study the number of questions went up to 34-35 as more aspects were added in the questions that appeared to be missed initially and it became evident from the pilot study results that more questions need to be added for effectively addressing the research objectives. This was then reduced to 24 questions when it was ensured that no irrelevant question is part of the interview questions list, and all the significant areas are covered in the existing questions. Therefore, it was a time taking process to finalize the questions of the interview. The guidance of research supervisor was also very helpful during this stage.

Semi-structured interviews as part of qualitative method were used as data collection tool and interview questions were developed by taking into consideration the scope of research objectives, conceptual model and the literature review findings. Each interview was approximately 20-25minutes long and due to different geographical locations, the interviews were conducted using social media app i.e., WhatsApp calls.

A key benefit that interview technique provides during data collection is the chance to ask follow-up questions which then helps in providing a detailed analysis. The subjective view of the millennials was required in this study which was attempted to be extracted with the help of semi-structured questions. The respondents were able to use their past experiences, perception and understanding about the concepts being asked in the questions while giving their responses which was useful in addressing the research objectives of the thesis. The interviews were conducted in a flexible manner rather than a strict manner i.e., for making respondents comfortable during the process the interview was processed as a discussion instead of stimulating a feel of questioning. At the same time, it was observed during execution of interviews that some respondents were finding it hard to focus throughout the course of all questions and some respondents were not keen to answer the question precisely instead they gave their general opinion. These limitations experienced during the interview execution were acknowledged and researcher showed flexibility instead of halting the interview process by allowing the interviews to complete as smoothly as possible.

Moreover, interpretive studies as mentioned by scholars makes use of interviews as a valuable technique of data collection because it improves the ability of respondents to express their opinions by not considering the preconceptions possessed by the researchers (Doolin, 1995). Therefore, this thesis as an interpretive study has adopted interview technique as a key source of evidence.

Even though it is recommended to record all the interviews while doing qualitative research for ensuring good quality research, however in this thesis it was not possible to record most of the interviews because these were not conducted face to face. However, transcripts were developed for each interview using hand notes and pointers which were then analysed with the help of thematic coding method. The respondents were only comfortable to answer the interview questions via WhatsApp calls due to which it was not possible to record the conversation, and most of the respondents did not gave permission to record the interview. However, with the help of transcripts the data analysis process was carried out. Bryman and Bell, (2007) mentioned that when evaluating qualitative data, coding is the first step because it provides assistance in connecting and identifying different factors constructed to theoretical ideas. Therefore, thematic tables were developed in line with the results and transcripts of the responses which included main themes and their sub-themes. Patterns and similarities were identified which constituted the thematic table.

The process of coding was conducted manually in the light of literature review and in a deductive way, whereas inductive approach was also applied within which empirical study was induced. The appendix A is representing the list of codes. Considerable patterns were evaluated in the data with the help of continuous reading performed by the researcher on the responses gathered. The relevant theories included in this thesis were also utilized for linking or understanding the research findings in the light of already existing academic and professional perspectives.

3.6 Research Design for Case Selection

Conducting research with a particular suitable research design holds importance for researchers and the consideration of the most appropriate data collection method and most suitable approach is at the core of developing research design (Hancock and Algozzine, 2016). A focused and aligned formulation of research design is required when case study design is the priority because it enables the researcher to develop the relations between distinct factors embedded in the research aim and objectives. Therefore, a specific structure and plan was developed by the researcher for undertaking the data collection and analysis process. It has been stated by Gering, (2007) that case selection holds critical importance for carrying out this case study research. Especially when the research is exploratory in nature and objective is to develop a theory, then the case selection becomes even more important i.e., in terms of contribution towards the results the case selection has to be comparable, however in terms of theoretical interest the outcome may vary.

Therefore, while selecting the three organizations from telecom sector of Pakistan, it was considered that which companies are relatively more active in communicating with employees and relatively more engaged in CSR activities. Moreover, a conscious effort was to select three companies with each company representing different country of origin i.e., one company is Pakistani (Compan Z), one company is Chinese (Compan Y) and one company is Norwegian (Compan X). Another factor considered was the number of years that telecom companies have spent operating in Pakistan and it was found it has been more than 10 years that these companies are operating in Pakistan. In terms of scale of operations and customer base, all the companies are fierce competitors and hold significant market share making them all important players.

Therefore, by applying these strategy aspects as a checklist, a careful decision was made of including three companies in case study selection. The use of checklist has been suggested by Miles and Huberman, (1994) when going for case study selection because it relies on information and strategy related to the research problem being studied and assists in generalizing the research outcome along with considering the ethical strategy when making a comparison of different case studies.

3.6.1 Pilot Study

A key challenge for researchers is to fine tune and improve the accuracy of questions that are to be used in data collection especially when semi-structured interviews are to be conducted. A pilot study was conducted for this purpose which actually proved helpful in enhancing the accuracy of questions. Moreover, it was also important to conduct pilot study for determining that whether respondents are able to understand the questions and the precise context of the questions is being answered appropriately (Van et al, 2001). After conducting the pilot study which was very brief as only few respondents were included in it, it was observed that some important aspects of the research objectives are being missed in the questions and some aspects need more clarity in terms of asking the questions in an understandable way.

Due to these two reasons, the number of questions were then increased to 24 which were 20 earlier. This pilot study was important to carry out for determining that whether the responses being given by millennial employees are suitable for enabling the researcher to draw concrete conclusions by addressing the research objectives. Two interviews were conducted in this pilot study as a result of which conciseness and clarity of questions was improved. The researcher observed that some aspects are appearing as alien to the respondents, and it needs to be ensured that millennials understand and can relate to the terms and concepts being used in the questions. Therefore, rephrasing of the interview questions was one important change that was conducted after pilot study completion. Moreover, questions were divided into different categories for making it easy for respondents to understand the context of questions.

The sequence and order of the questions being asked was also changed for making it easy for respondents to understand and some questions were merged for avoiding asking too many questions to the respondents where it was possible without damaging the clarity of questions.

Moreover, it was decided by the researcher to provide a short brief about some key terms used in the interview questions so that they remain aware of the context and meaning of the questions being asked. The length of some questions was also reduced for keeping the attention of the respondents alive in the process.

3.7 Considering Reliability and Validity of Research

Determining reliability and validity of research study is important to identifying the consistency and applicability of the results. Reliability can be measured using variety of ways and various scholars have referred towards consistency of results as optimal way of evaluating both validity and reliability (Denzin et al, 2011). Considering the nature of this thesis, consistency of results is difficult to achieve when this same study has to be implemented after a short or long period of time, however it can be achieved for some other studies. Since the adoption of an interpretivist view has essentially reflected that the research problem is intended to explore an existing norm which can change as the time will go by and quite probable that new scenario will be created with time which will provide different results when a future study is conducted.

Even though measuring reliability of this study is complex with the help of consistency in results, some strategies were applied by the researcher for enhancing the reliability of this study. For example, transcripts of every result were developed comprehensively for making sure that no aspect of data is missed and for enabling the researcher to remain engaged with the interview process and the answers being provided. Any follow up question asked was also noted in writing and then was asked to respondents for gaining insights from the respondents who part of data collection process were. It was ensured that alignment is maintained throughout different chapters of the study e.g., literature review was conducted in line with the scope of research aim and objectives, conceptual framework was developed in line with literature review findings and nature of research objectives, interview questions were in line with literature review findings, conceptual framework and research objectives.

And lastly the themes developed and analysed were also in line with the previous understanding and inferences. This way, validity and reliability has been attempted to be improved by the researcher.

3.8 Reflexivity in Qualitative Research

Reflexivity usually involves evaluating belief systems and judgements of the researcher by himself or herself. The objective behind application of reflexivity is to determine any incidental effect on the research generated by any personal belief of the researcher. The researcher in this study has applied reflexivity for reducing the likelihood of any bias exhibited by the researcher. The intention is to enhance the credibility of this study. This process holds importance because the research context of study is Pakistan's environmental CSR and since the researcher belongs to this country due to which there are possibilities that pre-conceived notions might have affected the research process.

The researcher engaged in reflexivity by adopting specific steps i.e., editing the subjective statements of the researcher on continuous basis, after conducting an interview meaning immediately, jotting the notes about thoughts of researcher himself and comments of participants during the interview. It was a difficult process to question your own self about how I know what I know and then analysing my own perceptions that were not based on factual evidence (Roulston, 2010). Moreover, it was not easy to integrate my own thoughts and understanding of the research context in a way which is not unduly manipulating the results.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

Approval of research ethics form from the ethics committee of the university, making sure voluntary participation of respondents, formal consent of respondents, not forcing any respondent to answer all the questions, ensuring data protection and anonymity of respondents, briefing respondents about the nature and purpose of data collection process, and making sure that participation in data collection process will not cause any harm to respondents' job and well-being are some key factors that were covered in meeting ethical considerations.

Considering, understanding and addressing ethical considerations is a vital aspect of any research study especially when the research involves interaction with human beings as respondents. Qualitative research studies and social research are two avenues in particular which embeds critical ethical considerations which researchers have to comply with. For maintaining a high standard of ethics in research, an ethical approval is required to be taken before initiating data collection process (Lewis, 2003; Gliner and Morgan, 2006). The researcher is expected to pay much attention towards the ethical side of research and then proceed towards data collection stage. Therefore, for complying with this aspect, the researcher made a formal application to research ethics committee of the respective university and seek their permission about initiating the research process. The key purpose of research, the established aim and objectives of research, the rationale behind the research and the research design was shown by the researcher to the committee. In addition, the steps to be taken for ensuring the confidentiality of the respondents and steps for ensuring the maintenance of respondents' anonymity was also exhibited to the ethics committee for getting their approval. A deeper sense of awareness and understanding was exhibited by the researcher about the range of ethical issues that research can pose and how to mitigate the issues. After all these stages, the researcher gained the ethical approval from the ethics committee.

According to Resnik, (2018) it is the responsibility of the researcher to provide clear and basic understanding about the research topic and its purpose to the respondents so that they can make their decision to be part of data collection process fairly and freely. This aspect was applicable in this study because case study qualitative approach was being implemented involving interviews due to which the researcher adhered to these ethical considerations.

Moreover, voluntary participation of the respondents was ensured by giving respondents the freedom and choice and by not pressurizing them directly or indirectly by any means. A consent form and participant information sheet were used for this purpose which are presented in the Appendix B. Moreover, labels were used for each case organization included in the study i.e., Case X, Case Y and Case Z so that anonymity of each organization can be maintained.

3.10 Chapter Summary

To summarise this chapter, this researcher adopted an interpretivist philosophy that led to a deductive approach, establishing the framework on an extant theory from the literature. Next, the researcher elected a multiple case study approach to validate the findings and solidify the results as illustrated in the figure. Due to the nature of the research topic, the researcher opted to use the qualitative method in order to expand and elaborate on the research subject. Due to the nature of this study, the researcher was obliged to select a cross-sectional time study in which a phenomenon is observed over a specific period of time. The use of interviews and the way in which the researcher collected data are all linked to the decision to adopt an interpretivist view. This was a significant decision, as it ultimately helped to determine that the study needed to obtain highly qualitative results, and hence interviews were used as a primary data collection method alongside multiple case studies. The subjectivity of the topic at hand had a significant effect on the decision-making that has been discussed as part of this methodology section; however, the choices made helped to fulfil the objectives set out at the start of the section.

4. Chapter Four: Analysis of Results

4.1 Introduction

This chapter is about presenting analysis of the results that were gathered with the application of semi-structured interview technique of data collection. These results will be presented in the textual paragraph format for making complete sense out of it. The analysis of the results is intended to be made easy due to which the proper and formal presentation of the gathered results will be conducted in this chapter. Since the total number of respondents participated in the data collection process was 30, therefore this section will analyse their results for understanding the trends and dimensions exhibited by them. Moreover, the analysis will consist of the thematic headings representing the results. Based on the interview results gathered and literature review findings, below is the list and respective descriptions of the themes that have been developed:

4.2 Thematic Table

No	Themes	Sub-themes	Quotes of millennial respondents
1	Cultural Impact	Social Dynamics of Millennials Scope and Strategic Importance of CSR practices Impervious Organizational Performance	“I think this pretty much covers every social step that a company takes”. “As employees we do have some responsibilities and I am sure that behaving well towards the environment is equally important for employers and employees”. “employees often get the backlash on the behalf of their employers for not upholding the natural

			environment when doing their business”. “as an employee I am not worried about these things so I cannot answer properly on this”
2	Awareness of Environmental CSR	<p>Acknowledgement of Environmental challenges</p> <p>Environmental issues faced by Pakistan</p> <p>Role of Government and COVID-19</p>	<p>“Plantation is very seriously required as green campaign and then all social media platforms are important for communicating the message of the group”.</p> <p>“The company should proactively use social media platforms for running campaigns about changing weather or climate which is an international issue as well”.</p> <p>“I think if a telecom company pledges its commitment and joins hands with government’s initiatives like Billion Tree Tsunami only then I think I will consider them as attractive”.</p> <p>“Government is fighting this issue properly and I do believe that companies should strictly follow guidelines of government to keep their brand attractive”.</p>

<p>3</p>	<p>Potential of Millennial Employees</p>	<p>Absence of Employee voice behaviour</p> <p>Presence of moral and social identity</p> <p>Dealing with strict work/job routine</p>	<p>“They do not share such information frequently and they never ask us”. “I have not seen any such information sharing which is about environment related activities”.</p> <p>“I am too busy in my job, I have no time to think and read about this stuff”.</p> <p>“I think it can influence my view about that company but first it has to happen and I think companies should do it”.</p> <p>“Yes, I often relate myself with companies who are putting efforts towards our environment”.</p> <p>“I find it closer to human nature and there is no surprise that one can develop association for the company even if the company is not my employer”.</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>Customer/Business focus</p>	<p>Neglecting employees and environment as stakeholders</p>	<p>“it is the responsibility of the company to think about environment related issues and it is as if you are asking employees more than their capacity because I have not witnessed any such example before and never heard of it before”.</p>

			<p>“As per my observation the awareness of Environmental CSR exists in my colleagues and co-workers, but we still need a lot more and we together need to put extra milestones in environment side of CSR”.</p> <p>“Yes, I think the reputation is being compromised due to lack of focus on environmental CSR”.</p> <p>“I know for a fact that customers are offered with packages and facilities, but not the environment”.</p>
5	Lack of Communication	Ignoring internal branding and social media	<p>“I remember last year the company shared some figures about their social work after which I do not think they have shared anything and they do not take our input anyway”.</p> <p>“sometimes on Facebook they see information about any activities related to society but that is not strictly for the employees internally”.</p> <p>“I would say it is not clearly communicated and it is not regular as well mainly because only selective meetings between management</p>

			<p>sometimes refer to CSR initiatives”. “The company should proactively use social media platforms for running campaigns about changing weather or climate which is an international issue as well”.</p>
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Table 2 Thematic Table

Source: Ahmad, (2021)

4.3 Cultural Trends and Impact

A key finding of this theme is that cultural factors and social background of respective millennial employees may have an impact on the level of awareness and understanding that they possess. It has become quite evident from the interview results because diversity in answers have been observed which exhibits that conceptual understanding and clarity of millennials differs considerably. However, at the same time, there are several similarities identified which are encouraging for reaching on a concrete conclusion. This theme has indicated that different contextual factors and cultural trends are shaping the view or opinion of millennial employees about the environmental CSR and employer branding concepts.

Moreover, it is the role of these factors that no considerable influence of environmental CSR activities has been found on employer branding. Before initiating the discussion, it is imperative to note here that theoretically Environmental factors comes under the concept of CSR which means addressing ECSR will naturally indicate that consideration of CSR concept as environment is a key constituent element of CSR and when the term CSR will come under discussion then it will reflect and embed the environment as well.

The answers to the question related to the social dynamics of millennials were meaningful and gave a certain direction to the results as respondents were clear in their answers. The element of culture and its influence on millennials can be evidently observed in the light of their answers. Most of the respondents stated that they do not consider environment CSR while switching or applying for jobs. One respondent from company X stated that, “While I apply for a new job or switching job, I consider 40% of environmental CSR Performance of the employer”. Five respondents clearly stated that, they do not consider such factors when applying for jobs and they are only interested in the salary”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “I can say this about their social activities, but I have not done this specifically about the environment factor”. Four respondents from company Y clearly stated that they do not pay attention to such factors when applying for jobs and they are more interested in either salary or job role. This commonality factor of giving importance to salary and not showing concern about environmental aspects is the result of overall culture that is prevailing i.e., short-term orientation.

Three respondents from company Z stated that, they only consider their professional growth when applying for jobs and two respondents considered job security as attractive point which they believed that company Z will provide them. One respondent from company Y and two respondents from company X stated that, they only restrict themselves to the job advert information when applying for jobs and they do not think about CSR issues. Overall, it has been observed from the responses of this question that ‘environmental CSR’ is not considered by the millennial employees of telecom sector in Pakistan when they are switching jobs or are applying for jobs. Therefore, it can be observed here that uncertainty avoidance is high, and millennials are focusing on the aspects that will reduce the level of uncertainty in terms of their professional career and are ignoring the environmental side.

When asked about reviewing the CSR policy of employers, the answers to this question were showing clear trends and patterns as most respondents saying that they do not review CSR policy and some respondents saying they do but this was not one of the decision-making factors. One respondent from company X stated that, “Yes, I definitely review the CSR policy while applying or switching jobs, but I cannot say that it helped me in my decision”.

One respondent from company X stated that, “I did not review it because for me it was not relevant and obviously my decision is based on other factors”. One respondent from company X stated that, “frankly speaking I did not review CSR policy”. The collectivist society produces thought processes that are coherent about different concepts and these results are indicating that due to cultural influences, a certain thinking pattern has prevailed across millennials i.e., they are not concerned about policies which can actually shape their future prosperity.

Respondents from three different companies giving similar responses when asked about reviewing CSR policies and environmental performance of employers is indicating that cultural impact is dominant. For example, one respondent from company Y stated that, “it depends because for my first job I did not review CSR policy, but when I switched my job, I did have a look on CSR policy for the sake of information”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “no, even though I once read it, but it does not influence my decision”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “No, I do not read company policies, I only see the job advert information”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “Why will I read CSR policy unless I am applying for HR jobs”. Overall, the responses showed that millennial employees do not have much interest in the CSR policies of the employers and their decision is not dependent on CSR performance of the employers.

The answers were clearly indicating a pattern as almost all the respondents gave importance to an eco-friendly office environment because it is associated with their presence in that vicinity. One respondent from company X stated that, “I think it is very important to work in an eco-friendly office surroundings because for working hard and good I need such environment”. One respondent from company X stated that, “I personally think it as highly important because I have a tough work routine and a positive environment will definitely give me motivation”. One respondent from company Y stated that “Yes, eco-friendly office environment is very important not only for me in fact for every employee this will increase the productivity up to 100%”. It is interesting to analyse here that when it comes to their own growth and productivity, millennials are considering the element of environment as important, however when it comes to other stakeholders, millennials are not much concerned. The social dynamics including their education and preferences as society are being exhibited in these responses which shows that uncertainty avoidance is not high and long-term orientation is high as presented in the graph produced by Hofstede earlier.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “I will definitely prefer this environment because working hours makes me drain and I need to recharge myself, so I think eco-friendly environment will help”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “honestly speaking I have told this to my colleagues that in this work pressure we need to have an office environment which gives us motivation”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “The weather conditions in our city are not good for most of the months and on top of it the work pressure and dealing with customers affects my mood, but this eco-friendly environment will definitely make me happy”. Overall, the respondents gave high importance to eco-friendly work environment, however the reasons quoted by them were varied yet common across respondents of three companies. This trend is indicating that when it comes to their own working space, millennial employees are conscious about environment friendly practices. The way millennial employees have answered the interview questions is indicating that individual personality traits, current priorities, lack of focus on CSR education and focus on the work only are some key factors that have restricted the understanding and awareness about CSR and employer branding.

Scope and Strategic importance of CSR practices

One respondent from company X stated that, “My company do CSR by helping people and we keep hearing about their achievements in CSR, and I think we are aware of this concept because in this country we have serious environmental issues”. Overall, it can be stated here that the notion of environmental CSR is slowly and gradually taking its place in the telecom industry, however it is being overshadowed for several reasons which are contextual, business related and person specific as well. The answers about the dimension of switching job based of environmental CSR performance have indicated mixed trends with most respondents stating that they will not stay with their employer for long based on their improved focus on environmental CSR. One respondent from company X stated that, “Definitely yes, I will be happy with my employer and will not think about leaving the company especially when our country is not doing great with environment”. One respondent from company X stated that, “I would love to stay for longer but to be honest I am not sure how practical this decision can be”.

It can be observed that Pakistan has a low score on uncertainty avoidance and high score of power distance, the influence of these cultural dimensions can be observed in the responses as millennials are not pragmatically convinced that they will leave their employer or join another employer based on environmental CSR performance.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “This is an ideal situation we are talking about and given this situation I am not sure how I will react but at the present moment I think I will not stay”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “As fancy as it sounds, I have this feeling that I might stay longer because the company will need our support for continuing to do so”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “This is a difficult question to answer because I seriously want this to happen in reality but given the circumstances I might not stay solely because of this reason”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “If this happens this will definitely help me take decision about my stay with my employer because overall, I am already satisfied with my employer”. Overall, it has been reflected that millennial employee can potentially stay with an employer who focuses more on environmental CSR and cares about the environment in which they operate, however how practical and convincing their claim can be remains questionable. The cultural influence is significant which is restricting the millennials to take certain stances and to practice certain behaviours.

4.4 Awareness of CSR

The answers to the questions about importance and awareness of CSR practices were mixed i.e., a clear trend was not visible about having the awareness of CSR practices and the strategic importance of CSR across millennials. Some respondents believed that awareness exists, and some believed it did not exist. Reasons behind the responses were interesting and noteworthy because the element of cultural influence is visible when analysed. One respondent from company X stated that, “As per my observation the awareness of Environmental CSR exists in my colleagues and co-workers, but we still need a lot more and we together need to put extra milestones in environment side of CSR”.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “I think we do understand about the environmental issues, and I have often had discussions with my colleagues about how green initiatives can be taken by our company for giving back to the natural environment around us because the government is giving it priority from last few years”. It can be analysed that an organizational culture of giving importance and practicing environmental CSR is not prevailing across telecom companies due to which the millennials are accepting lack of awareness. This reinforces the observation about the educational and social dimensions of the culture that are not highlighting and focusing on environmental CSR concept as a priority.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “until recently I was not aware of this field in the business world because I used to think that environment protection is separate from doing business, but I have now seen that government is taking different steps for this purpose and they have asked our company as well to play our role in this.”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “I only read it in the books during my studies and that was also not much, I have not heard about this concept in my colleagues, but we know about it and in this industry, I think people know about it but they do not implement it”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “The way our company communicates information with us, we have read about it, and I personally have seen that people show concern about environment very less because of the job pressures and goals given by the department”. A more shareholder approach and less of stakeholder approach can be observed from the responses of millennials which reflects that corporate culture of Pakistan needs to draw a balance between the two approaches.

Moreover, it is evident that educational journey of a very small percentage of respondents made them aware about environmental CSR which shows that educational and social experiences of millennials are needed to be enhanced by integrating more focus and exposure about environmental CSR. This in turn will trigger the expectations and pressure from the side of employees as stakeholders on the telecom employers which currently is missing. The overall awareness of millennials about CSR concept is not significant which is validating the analysis presented in the previous section where the cultural influence has been found as a key factor responsible. One respondent from company X stated that, “CSR is a way to give back to the community and people”.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “I think this pretty much covers every social step that a company takes”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “Just like we have to be good citizens, the companies also have to behave good which we know as CSR”. One respondent from company X stated that, “It is about how companies take notice of societal issues and react to those issues”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “Whatever good actions a company takes it summed up in CSR and I have seen some adverts of CSR by other companies”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “This term asks companies to spend money on the community around and try to improve the conditions of community and take care of surroundings”. A basic level of understanding has been shown by respondents about CSR concept which indicates that level of awareness needs to be increased significantly for the purpose of drawing a balance between stakeholder and shareholder approach.

When questions were asked about the importance of environment for millennials, the level of awareness cited was considerably encouraging as opposed to the findings of previous questions. For example, one respondent from company X stated that, “Social responsibility empowers employees to leverage the corporate resources at their disposal to do good. Formal corporate social responsibility programs can boost employee morale and lead to greater productivity in the workforce. The importance should be given by telecom firms in our country to enhance the quality of business and improve the customer services”. The depth of some answers was significance and indicated that millennials certainly have a sense of acknowledgement about the importance of environment in which they operate and live. One respondent from company Y stated that, “As employees we do have some responsibilities and I am sure that behaving well towards the environment is equally important for employers and employees”. One respondent from company Y has stated that, “I think for obeying the environmental laws and obligations, it is very important for the employers to do their business by being conscious of the natural environment around”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “employees often get the backlash on the behalf of their employers for not upholding the natural environment when doing their business”. As opposed to the awareness about CSR concept, the millennials have shown enhanced acknowledgement and sense of awareness about the importance of natural environment which signifies their distinctive characteristic of being a millennial generation employee.

Generation Y employees prefer to stay with organizations that provide a good working environment (Du-Plessis, Barkhuizen, Stanz & Schutte, 2015). A good working environment comprises of the physical and social environment (Williams & Turnbull, 2015). A good physical environment includes the open space, lighting, furniture design and ambience of the workplace (Bencsik, et al, 2016). Therefore, in terms of natural environment the preferences and understanding of millennials is not pragmatic, whereas in the context of working environment they have clarity of thought.

Understanding about the organizational settings and reputation of companies have been shown by respondents by linking some theoretical concepts in their answers. For example, one respondent from company X stated that, employees are the face of their company and when this face is not presented in a welcoming and positive way then it does not only affect the reputation of the company but also it affects the personal standing of the employees”. Some respondents of company X and Z stated that the morale and confidence of employees increases when company takes initiatives for the natural environment. Overall, almost all the respondents were agreed to the fact that behaving well towards natural environment is important for the employers. Whereas some respondents from company Y and company Z did not agree that it is important for employees because employees are stakeholders they deserve and expect best behaviours from the employer, and it is not important for them to consider the environment when doing their job. Moreover, the reluctant or restrictive nature of the respondents towards making practical steps about environmental CSR have been cited which is mainly because of the cultural influence.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “I am not sure whether the environment friendly behaviours can be applied on us and how we can find time to do this when we already have strict work routines, but I think for employers it should be important”. It appeared from the responses of this question that a considerable level of awareness exists across millennial employees about the environment friendly behaviours and practices, however it still needs to be improved and there must be a reason why this margin of improvement exists considering the expectations from millennial employees. Most of the respondents did not give any answer to this question, whereas some respondents answered briefly without giving clear reasons and examples.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “I think it does not improve much, as a graduate I am keen to get a job and I will not pay attention to this issue”. High power distance culture and less focus on stakeholders’ approach are the main reasons observed that have shifted the focus of millennials towards professional growth and salary more and less on CSR related aspects. One respondent from company Z stated that, “reputation of employers in this industry are decent and people are getting jobs in telecom companies, so this environmental issue is not important”.

One respondent from company X stated that, “brand name and services make employers attractive, I do not know if CSR can make them attractive”. Even though the millennials have acknowledged the importance of employer branding, however they are not confident whether it has any link with environmental side of CSR. Lack of clarity has been cited among the respondents towards the relationship between employer branding and environmental CSR because of cultural influence and their social dynamics. The questions regarding this relationship between natural environment and employer branding incurred more time during the interview because it appeared that various respondents were not interested and bothered about this question. However, due to time shortage and for the purpose of keeping their interest alive, the researcher had to move on to next questions.

The answers to these questions about covid-19 and environmental CSR issues of Pakistan were showing a clear trend as most of the respondents did not link the COVID-19 crisis with environmental CSR i.e., only few respondents viewed it as a threat for which ECSR is imperative. One respondent from company X stated that, “It is definitely a wakeup call, but I do not see its connection with CSR”. One respondent from company X stated that, “Obviously COVID is a challenge instead of opportunity, but I think if we obey the government guidelines, we can stay safe”. It has appeared that millennials are not aware about the role of Pakistan Telecommunication Authority which has a pivotal standing in terms of practical steps and policies that govern telecom sector. One respondent from company Y stated that, “I do not think companies can do much about it because it happened naturally from outside Pakistan, and we can only try to manage it by being careful”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “Government is fighting this issue properly and I do believe that companies should strictly follow guidelines of government to keep their brand attractive”.

A basic sense of purpose and awareness about the imperativeness of adhering to the government policies is evident, however millennials were not able to quote any examples in this regard specifically. The ability to critically evaluate and think about the environmental CSR issues is not sufficient across millennial employees which is one reason why they do not raise voice and expand their understanding about these issues. One respondent from company Z stated that, “It can be a factor for coming years because we do not know when it is going to end and when it will hit us back”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “If you are talking about following SOPs then yes companies should do it and make sure that SOPs are fulfilled by all the employees working in the company”. Overall, a shallow view and understanding has been exhibited by the millennial respondents as they were not able to relate COVID-19 crisis with an opportunity to pursue environment driven CSR even though environment is a key factor in managing COVID-19.

4.5 Potential of Millennial Employees

The answer to the questions about employee voice behaviour and potential of millennial employees was a positive one as almost every respondent agreed with the idea that employees as stakeholders can influence their employers, except from few respondents from company Z. One respondent from company X stated that, “Yes, employees as stakeholders should influence their employers to practice environmental CSR to give quality of services to their maximum customer within limit of resources”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “I think in today’s social media world we employees have some powers and we definitely can use this power for influencing our employers about their business activities to respect the natural environment conditions”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “we often get such chances where we can play our role in telling the company about what they are doing right and what they are doing wrong. So, we can definitely use such chances to inform them and demand from them to take care about the environment when they are doing their business and making profits”. The willingness among millennial respondents have been observed, however due to cultural factors and less focus on stakeholder approach, their implementation aspect is weak. The millennials are gradually realising their power in the backdrop of social media platforms and multi-dimensional nature of communication.

Two respondents from company Z gave responses which were different from the rest of the respondents as they stated that it is beyond the power and authority of employees to influence their employers on such issues because there are other important issues which employees need to focus on. For example, one of these respondents from company Z stated that, “as an idea it can be good but I do not think that in reality many employees will agree with this because we have other important issues on which we often need to raise our concerns with the company and it becomes difficult for us sometimes to get the solution of our problems in the way we want, so I do not think we have power to influence on environment related matters”.

This indicated an opposite thought process that is prevailing across millennial employees of telecom sector as compared to what respondents stated in terms of employee voice behaviour. There is a visible integration of shareholder approach and lack of awareness is an added factor that the ground reality is not what respondents have reflected in some of their answers. This aspect of putting theory into practice is weak and probably is facing barriers from cultural dimensions and business driven corporate approach of companies which has not encouraged functioning of employee voice behaviour.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “it is the responsibility of the company to think about environment related issues and it is as if you are asking employees more than their capacity because I have not witnessed any such example before and never heard of it before”. Overall, it was observed that millennial employees do believe that they can influence employers over environment friendly behaviours and practices. However, two contrasting responses that were gathered from company Z is important to be considered in terms of the arguments given by the respondents and will need to be addressed in discussion chapter. It appeared in various questions that some respondents were trying to may be overthink or over do in their answers and these some respondents were giving answers that were going beyond the scope and boundaries of the interview question. However, these have been added in the results because they were taking interest in the interview process, and they wanted to get their message across in their own way and within this process some interesting and valuable responses have been gathered.

The answer to the questions about moral and social identity provided mixed results with most responses being given were without examples or reasons. However, most of the respondents think that their social standing in the society is not increased with environment focus actions and values of their employer. One respondent from company X stated that, “I have not experienced this so far and I do not think it increases social standing”. One respondent from company X stated that, “I cannot say this with confidence because I would like this to happen, but I do not think it happens in reality”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “Yes, it does make me feel proud and confident”. Three respondents from company Y stated that, “May be yes, I am not sure”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “brand name is enough I think which definitely makes my social standing increased”.

Two respondents from company Y and three respondents from company X stated that these values and actions are not noticed by people, brand name of the employer speaks for itself. Given the scores on Hofstede cultural dimensions and the mindset shown by millennial respondents so far has made it probable that strong moral and social identity are highly unlikely to be found among millennials. Overall, the answers reflected that employees are more concerned about the brand name of the employer and they do not give much importance to environment friendly actions and values. It appears that millennials do not want the moral and social identity to cost them in terms of their job and they are currently contended with the extent to which they are extracting value out of moral and social identity.

Some answers were one sided and indicating a clear trend i.e., apart from two respondents whose view about attractiveness of telecom companies was shaped, no other respondent shaped their view about the attractiveness of telecom companies based on the environmental CSR information. One respondent from company X stated that, “I have not experienced such incidents; I am not sure this has happened with me in the recent past”. One respondent from company X stated that, “To be honest, I have never read or seen any such information so I cannot say this can influence me or not, but I remember recently our Prime Minister Chaired an international conference on environment”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “I think it can influence my view about that company but first it has to happen, and I think companies should do it”.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “Even though I have not encountered any such information, but if I will, then I am not sure it will influence me or not”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “I think if a telecom company pledges its commitment and joins hands with government’s initiatives like Billion Tree Tsunami only then I think I will consider them as attractive”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “In my experience and knowledge I have not seen news or press release about environment related events so I cannot comment on it properly”. Overall, it has been reflected that no millennial employee has been exposed to such information which mentions about environment CSR initiatives due to which their opinion is restricted on this aspect.

The answers to this question were mixed and indicating two trends i.e., one is about employees who develop an association and second is about employees who do not develop an association. One respondent from company X stated that, “Yes, I often relate myself with companies who are putting efforts towards our environment”.

One respondent from company X stated that, “I do not give these activities much importance because I have other things to do and think about at work”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “I have had an experience in the past after which I do not take such activities seriously because I have understood that these are marketing gimmicks”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “This applies only to the extent when a campaign is being run because during that period you feel that association which is natural to happen for me, but it is temporary only”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “I find it closer to human nature and there is no surprise that one can develop association for the company even if the company is not my employer”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “I can say that if you see anything positive happening around you feel good about it and I can relate myself with that company doing any good to our environment”.

Overall, the answers have been encouraging in the context that a common sense of purpose and association exists across the millennial employees when it comes to the natural environment perseverance.

4.6 Customer/Business Focus

The answers to these questions about effect of environment related CSR practices on employer branding were also mixed as clear one-sided trend was not achieved i.e., some respondents were of the view that it does affect the reputation of employers, and some believed that it does not affect. Some respondents were actually unaware that this kind of impact can practically occur. However, some respondents gave interesting reasons, and some respondents did not give any reason for their answers. One respondent from company X stated that, “Yes, I think the reputation is being compromised due to lack of focus on environmental CSR”. One respondent from company X stated that, “I am not sure, but I think it does affect negatively because when other companies are doing one thing and you are missing out on it then people do notice it”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “I think it should, but I am not sure if it actually happens”.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “I do not think this happens, we do not normally pay attention on this”. With high score of 70 on uncertainty avoidance, the Pakistani society has a strong inclination for avoiding the uncertainty factor. Countries having a score in this dimension tend to be less flexible and are extremely resistant in parting ways with traditional approaches. These societies are the epitome of change resistance. Such societies have an emotional disposition towards rules even if the rules are never applied or they fail to have the right impact. The people value time, hard work while precision and punctuality are the societal standards. Innovation is not encouraged and security is the principal determinant of motivation. The aforementioned cultural disposition calibrates well with the responses of millennials i.e. the parameters of motivation and focus override the realization of actively using the environment driven practices.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “I have no idea about it, I have not heard about it before that any such thing can happen”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “as an employee I am not worried about these things so I cannot answer properly on this”. Some respondents from company Y and company Z outrightly replied that yes, the reputation is affected, however they gave no reasons and examples which gave the impression that they are not aware of the issue and are just giving their answers because they have to give some answer.

This trend extracted from the question is worth discussing in the next chapter when a complete picture will be determined in the discussion of the interview results. An overall picture obtained from the results is that due to extensive focus on business development and sustainability, there is less focus being given to the stakeholder approach and serving the shareholder approach is dominant. Millennials, despite of possessing traits different than other generations are getting used to with the implementation of customer and business focused practices. The willingness and interest of respondents is minimal towards the environmental CSR related issues.

The answers to the question about precise CSR events were mixed as some respondents were aware and some were not aware about the CSR practices of their employers. One respondent from company X stated that, “By the best of my knowledge many corporate CSR initiatives strive to positively contribute to the public, the economy or the environment. But I cannot remember any such CSR initiative of my company which highlighted environment”.

One respondent from company X stated that, “to be honest I have not seen or heard anything that my company has done for the environment”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “I know for a fact that customers are offered with packages and facilities, but not the environment”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “I remember my company made an advert about their commitment to the environment protection, but frankly I have not seen anything in reality”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “Yes, I think my company joined hands with a famous cold drink company and they did some activity about reusing of plastic”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “I cannot remember any such practices”. Overall, it has been reflected from the answers that most of the respondents are not aware of ECSR practices and only few respondents remembered about such initiatives that involved consideration of environment.

The answers to this question were indicating a clear trend as almost all respondents stated that improvement in ECSR policies is required. One respondent from company X stated that, “Yes, to compete in international market employers need to focus on environmental CSR Policies”. One respondent from company X stated that, “I think they do need to make improvements because their business is so big, they should think about environment policies”.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “Definitely, it is a big requirement”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “If we look at the situation of our city and country overall, it is for sure a major need”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “obviously it is their responsibility to have all kinds of policies, because it will give them benefit and it will give people some benefit”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “yes in reality they should do it and should encourage other companies as well”. Overall, it is clear from the answers that millennial employees want their employers to be socially responsible companies, however employers are not focusing on environmental side. A study conducted by Hassan, (2017) on Pakistan’s telecom sector revealed that telecom companies are not focusing on the environmental side of CSR. Education standards, health conditions and community development at various levels are their focus according to their priorities, objectives and strategies. It was concluded by Hassan, (2017) that the CSR strategies of the companies depend upon the corporate interests which were not including environment protection as a key component in Pakistan’s telecom sector. This evidence is reaffirming the interview results gathered and is indicating an absence of employer branding and environmental CSR link.

4.7 Lack of Communication

Responses against the questions related to the effectiveness of CSR adverts were also indicating one sided trend as most of the respondents did not get influenced by environmental CSR adverts. Some respondents did not give any answer to this question. One respondent from company X stated that, “the flow of information is very fast these days and to be honest I do not pay much attention to such information”. Another respondent from company X stated that, “I do not have time to see and read such adverts”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “sometimes I hear about initiatives of the company, but this does not affect me as such”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “in such tough job routine it sometimes makes you feel good about your company”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “I will honestly say that our company makes so many adverts and gives us so much information about services and packages after that I hardly pay attention to other information”.

This particular finding and establishment of 'lack of communication' theme is reaffirming the previously discussed theme which indicated a dominance of shareholders' approach. For example, stakeholder management is not evident across telecom companies which is halting the understanding and awareness of millennials about environmental CSR issues. It is necessary to strike a balance between the interests of stakeholders and the needs of those in charge of managing the organization's actions. Employees have traditionally been regarded as the most valuable asset in a company's operations. Due to the fact that they are both impacted by and affected by their employment, employees play a significant role in the success or failure of an organisation (Azim, 2016). However, as per the results of this study, telecom companies are not treating its millennial employees as worthy assets and is merely focusing on their role as performance contributors towards the business.

One respondent from company Z stated that, "I am too busy in my job, I have no time to think and read about this stuff". Overall, the answers have reflected that millennial employee do not find time to pay attention and focus on environmental CSR related information and for them it does not hold much importance because it is not included in the job description or job role that they are performing.

The answers to the questions about the use of social media by telecom employers were clear and showing a visible trend as most of the respondents named the social media platforms which their company uses. One respondent from company X stated that, "Usually the company uses Facebook for conveying information about their campaigns". One respondent from company X stated that, "Facebook, Instagram and twitter are frequently used by the company for sharing their social activities". One respondent from company Y stated that, "company uses their website and Facebook mostly for telling us about their different campaigns and activities". One respondent from company Y stated that, "Facebook and Instagram are the main communication methods of my company when they have to share new information". One respondent from company Z stated that, "website of the company and Facebook is used by our company for sharing news and information about what they are doing". The active presence of all the telecom employers on social media platforms is at a minimum giving them a decent opportunity to engage in building employer branding and to deliver a balance of stakeholders approach.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “I think our company mostly uses own website when they have to share a story about performance or anything else”. Overall, the answers showed that Facebook, Instagram and company’s official website is used by telecom sector employers for conveying about their CSR activities and performance. However, a key aspect noticed during the answers was that most of the respondents did not mention the CSR or environment related activities of their employers.

The answers to this question were indicating a clear pattern i.e., most of the respondents believe that telecom sector employers are not undertaking this practice of sharing environmental CSR information for potential and existing employees. One respondent from company X stated that, “They do not share such information frequently and they never ask us”. One respondent from company X stated that, “I would like to clarify here that if you are talking about CSR information then it happens but not often, but if you ask about environmental side then in my experience, I have never witnessed it”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “I have not seen any such information sharing which is about environment related activities”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “For employees they share information about financial performance and services of the company, but as per my knowledge CSR information they hardly ever share”.

The results are indicating that telecom employers are using social media platforms to build a business aspect of internal branding instead of developing CSR related internal branding. This weak and limited communication is not an encouraging sign and is another reason why millennials in this industry have low level of awareness about environmental CSR. The organizations need to ensure carrying out regular communication with the stakeholders related to the CSR for sustaining their trust and meeting the growing commitments of the business related to the CSR (Xiao et al, 2020). Duthler and Dhanesh (2018) also recommend the organizations can involve the relevant stakeholders (employees) within the internal CSR communications. Effective internal communications related to CSR allow the organizations to understand and manage the employees’ needs positively leading towards the exploitation of more innovation and growth opportunities (Gruber, Kaliauer, and Schlegelmilch, 2017; Hendriks, 2016).

One respondent from company Z stated that, “I remember last year the company shared some figures about their social work after which I do not think they have shared anything, and they do not take our input anyway”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “Our regional manager sometimes in meetings mentions about company’s initiatives for the city, apart from this no formal sharing of information takes place in the company”. Two respondents of company X and three respondents of company Y stated that, “sometimes on Facebook they see information about any activities related to society but that is not strictly for the employees internally”. Overall, it has been indicated that telecom companies are not keenly and frequently sharing CSR related information with their employees. It is few and far between because some respondents who said that companies do share such information, they added that the frequency of this sharing is very less.

The answers to the questions about fairness and transparency of telecom employers were indicating a clear pattern i.e., majority of respondents believe that telecom sector employers are not fair and transparent in their CSR communication. One respondent from company X stated that, “I do not think that employers are fair and transparent in their CSR communication towards stakeholders like any other big company in Pakistan”. One respondent from company X stated that, “I am not sure about it but whatever little I know, I think they are not always transparent”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “It is hard to tell, I usually focus on my job, so I expect them to be fair and transparent”.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “There is a perception that companies mostly manipulate information when telling something to the customers and sometimes to the employees, there is some truth about this perception”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “These companies protect their interest, and they have to compromise on fairness of information sharing which is not fair I think”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “I think companies fear to lose their profits or sales and that’s why they are not fair and transparent”. Overall, the answers to this question have indicated that millennial employees believe that telecom sector companies are not transparent and fair in their communication with stakeholders. It has been indicated that a clear pattern of understanding exists among millennials which is an encouraging sign for the analysis of these results.

Almost all the respondents have adequate basic understanding about the concept of employer branding. One respondent from company X stated that, “I think it is about putting yourself as a brand in front of candidates just like other product brands where attraction of people is the objective”. One respondent from company X stated that, “I believe it is about developing the company as a brand for the staff so that they can use that brand name”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “As I understand it is the representation of company’s image in the market, somewhat like we see brands of products or services”.

As the employer brand targets both potential and current employees, it can be considered as having an internal and external perspective. The external employer brand refers to the employer image, or the mental representations individuals have of the organization as an employer, while identity is what the insiders, i.e., employees, perceive to be the stable and persistent core of the company (Lievens and Slaughter, 2016). It is therefore evident that millennials working in telecom companies have relatively more exposure and understanding about the external perspective, and less exposure about the internal perspective of employer branding.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “I think it is the effort of a company to project their name in front of employees so that employees prefer that brand for their work experience”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “I have heard a lot about brand management, but I think this term is little different from branding of products. In my opinion it deals with highlighting a company as attractive for employees and reasons can be different, I think”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “This term is about showing the world that what kind of brand you are in a market and why you are better than others”. Overall, the level of basic understanding indicated by the millennial respondents about employer branding is satisfactory and it certainly has an impact on how the respondents have given answers to the upcoming questions. The direction of answers in this question has been adequate which was kind of a pre-requisite for gaining relevant answers in the remaining questions of this interview. The answers to the questions about internal communication have indicated a clear trend i.e., most of the respondents believe that internal communication is not regular and clear by their employers. One respondent from company X stated that, “I cannot say anything about it because I am not aware about their working process about CSR because mostly such information is restricted to managers”.

One respondent from company X stated that, “To the best of my knowledge, no such communication took place in my company in the last one year”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “Yes, in our formal and informal meetings with higher management, we are told about how the company is fulfilling CSR obligations”.

Two respondents from company Y stated that, “Performance goals and appraisals are two regular activities that occurs internally, but CSR is hardly an event on which information is shared within the company”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “I would say it is not clearly communicated and it is not regular as well mainly because only selective meetings between management sometimes refer to CSR initiatives”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “Yes in terms of annual reports we can say this happens because I have seen that CSR is talked about in these reports, but apart from annual publication of report, no internal communication happens”. Overall, the answers have indicated that internal communication is not focused on CSR activities and is more concerned about performance of the employees. Moreover, the frequency and extent of internal communication about CSR activities is not sufficient.

The answers to this question were positive and diverse at the same time i.e. respondents have shared their opinion on CSR policies that can help in improving employer branding. Two respondents from company X stated that, “Plantation is very seriously required as green campaign and then all social media platforms are important for communicating the message of the group,”. One respondent from company X stated that, “In my opinion the company should raise awareness and do some practical steps about the air pollution which is becoming more dangerous every year”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “The company should proactively use social media platforms for running campaigns about changing weather or climate which is an international issue as well”.

Two respondents from company Y stated that, “Taking care of animals, birds and plants are some very important factors that the company needs to engage in by launching different ongoing trends”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “I think social media platforms are working well for the company, however, I strongly believe that joining hands with any Government initiative will provide great benefits to the company itself”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “For improving employer branding, the company needs to focus on creating awareness about different social and environmental issues such as, water and food wastage, preserving and keeping trees/ plants”. Overall, all the respondents gave their input about the asked questions and as a result social media has remained most popular platform of communication method and natural environment has been identified as key CSR policy issues.

Below presented is the table indicating the demographics of the respondents that were included in the data collection process.

Respondent No.	Year Born	Allocated code to the Employer Company	Job Role/Position of the Interviewee	Location of Job and employer	Time duration with employer
1	1984	X	Customer Service	Lahore	2 Years
2	1984	X	Business Analyst	Lahore	3 Years
3	1986	X	Customer Service	Lahore	1.5 Years
4	1985	X	System Engineer	Lahore	2 Years
5	1986	X	Maintenance Engineer	Gujranwala	3 Years
6	1984	X	Marketing Manager	Sialkot	1 Year
7	1988	X	Customer Service	Lahore	3 Years
8	1987	X	Customer Service	Gujranwala	1.2 Years
9	1985	X	IT Manager	Islamabad	2.5 Years

10	1986	X	Accounts Officer	Gujranwala	1.6 Years
11	1990	Y	Sales Assistant	Sialkot	1.5 Years
12	1984	Y	Sales Manager	Sialkot	3.5 Years
13	1985	Y	Customer Relationship Manager	Lahore	2.5 Years
14	1984	Y	Manager Communications	Lahore	4 Years
15	1986	Y	Network Engineer	Lahore	2 Years
16	1986	Y	Customer Service	Lahore	1 Year
17	1987	Y	Customer Service	Lahore	1 Year
18	1985	Y	Business Analyst	Gujranwala	2 Years
19	1984	Y	Operations Manager	Islamabad	3 Years
20	1984	Y	Brand Manager	Islamabad	4 Years
21	1986	Y	Administration Officer	Lahore	2 Years
22	1985	Y	Marketing Analyst	Lahore	2 Years
23	1984	Z	Area Sales Manager	Gujranwala	3 Years
24	1988	Z	Assistant Manager Segments	Lahore	2 Years

25	1989	Z	Software Engineer Automation	Islamabad	1.5 Years
26	1987	Z	Customer Service	Lahore	2 Years
27	1987	Z	Customer Service	Lahore	1 Year
28	1984	Z	Business Account Manager	Islamabad	4 Years
29	1989	Z	Customer Service	Gujranwala	1 Years
30	1986	Z	Data Engineer	Lahore	3 Years

Table 3 Demographic Details of Respondents

Source: Ahmad, (2021)

Since three case organizations have been included in this study, majority of the respondents belonged to company X (12 respondents), then 10 respondents belonged to company Y, and 8 respondents belonged to company Z. Two companies selected in this study are MNCs (belonging to two different country of origin) and one company is local Pakistan based indicating a contrast and diversity. Figure below is indicating these numbers in pictorial form:

In terms of job role possessed by the respondents, it was found that four different categories of respondents were involved in data collection process in terms of their job role and title i.e. first category was of engineers working in different business functions, second category was of managers and assistant managers working in different business functions, third category was of customer service which covered individuals working at different posts of customer service function, and last category was of technical & other staff who does not fall under the previous three categories. Respondents belonging to the category of Engineers were 5, customer service-related respondents were 9, manager and assistant manager level respondents were 10, and Technical & other respondents were 6.

The valuable aspect of this profile identification is the fact that all the respondents included in data collection process are representing diverse job roles, positions and business functions which means their understanding and opinion will be based on their respective diverse experiences. This also means that the findings gathered, and conclusion developed as a result of discussion on the findings will be covering broad range of opinions and will be considered reliable in terms of its application. Figure below is indicating these numbers in pictorial form:

In terms of time duration that millennial employees have spent with their current employers, it was found that most of the employees are working for 2 or more than 2 years i.e., 20 respondents had at least 2 or more than 2 years of time duration with their current employer and 10 respondents had at least 1 year or less than 2 years' time duration with their current employer. This information is indicating that respondents giving answers to interview questions were essentially millennial employees and they had spent at least 1 year with their current employer which means their understanding and experience with the current employer is sufficient enough on which they can reflect. Figure below is indicating these numbers in pictorial form:

The background and profile related results have provided the clarity that the results which are going to be interpreted in this chapter have a strong base and source which means the input or opinion given by the respondents holds weigh. Moreover, it can be observed that based on these initial results, an understanding can be developed that the respondents were meeting the pre-requisites of this research process. For example, not only the employees were millennial generation, but they had also spent considerable amount of time with their current employers for understanding the CSR culture and approach of the company towards employer branding.

Moreover, the job roles or positions held by the respondents were diverse and of a reasonable stature and importance. For example, diverse job roles are expected to provide diverse viewpoints and experience in the respective fields which when combined under the banner of this study, then it can facilitate with meaningful conclusions and findings. This way, the chances of addressing the research objectives in an aligned and relevant manner becomes high. Since the focus of this research study is on the millennial employees due to which first question to begin the interview was about this age group to make sure that the respondent belongs to this particular generation which is also referred as 'generation Y'.

All the respondents included in the data collection process were either born in 1984 or after 1984. Majority of respondents were born after 1984 i.e., 21 respondents were born after 1984 and 9 respondents were born in 1984.

5. Chapter Five: Discussion

This chapter is presenting detailed analysis and discussion on the themes that have been identified from the results along with their sub-themes. Literature review findings will be used for analysing the identified themes and their applicability or relevance in the chosen specific context. Five distinct themes have been identified after interpreting and reviewing the results of the interviews conducted in the previous chapter. Below presented is the thematic table embedded five main themes and their respective sub-themes:

5.1 Integration of Cultural Perspectives

It has been observed that cultural influence is one common factor that has generated impact across all the four themes developed in this study.

A low score of 14 puts Pakistan in the category of collectivistic society. This establishes the Pakistan society as an arch believer of adhering to group norms and commitment be it for immediate family or any other relationships. Loyalty reign supreme in this scenario as it overrules any other cultural norm or practice. The relationships are the principal determinants where every individual is responsible for the members of his immediate and larger community. The intriguing aspect of a collectivist society is that any committed offence leads to a disproportionate degree of shame, which engulfs the group/family members. The decisions of recruitment and retentions are taken by the group of high-ranking individuals belonging to the executive board.

Individual differences in the personality can influence the reaction of employees towards CSR initiatives (Barrick et al, 2013; Hendriks, 2016). This aspect of individual differences and other contextual factors have played a key role in generating millennial employees' reactions that are indicating varying opinions and understanding about the concepts involved. Considering the educational backgrounds and job roles of respondents, the answers have not reflected clarity of thought on the part of millennial employees. For example, some respondents from company Y and company Z outrightly replied that yes, the reputation is affected, however they gave no reasons and examples which gave the impression that they are not aware of the issue and are just giving their answers because they have to give some answer.

Some respondents were actually unaware that this kind of impact can practically occur. However, some respondents gave interesting reasons, and some respondents did not give any reason for their answers.

In Pakistan, the lower scale employees usually have no authority in the decision-making processes. They are simply directed or instructed by the senior management to undertake a task rather than being consulted at any stage. The Pakistani societal setup has an autocratic structure and it resonates in the business structure as well (Islam, 2004). The senior officer always has the discretionary power to make choices for his subordinates. However, any manager having adequate exposure of foreign employment does consult his subordinates. The corporate culture of Pakistan also discourages junior employees asking too many questions or discussing business related problems with their senior counterparts beyond the approved norm of maintaining minimal interaction. Such acts get flagged and diminishes the promotion prospects of the individual.

Memon et al, (2014) identified that higher education institutions in Pakistan are not running educational programs on CSR and due to this, graduates have limited exposure and understanding of this discipline. Chaudhary, (2014) stated that practices and learning of graduates in Pakistan are weak towards CSR concept. This empirical evidence is making it clear that millennial job seekers and employees in Pakistan lack in-depth understanding about the CSR concept. This was felt during the interviews by the researcher. This means that if an employee does not have clarity about a concept, then his or her opinion about the interplay of that concept will also be restricted. This finding appears concerning because telecom sector of Pakistan is dominant by MNCs and only one local telecom company is operating which means that the impact of MNCs has not prevailed for which reasons can be investigated in future.

As it was mentioned in the research rationale section that MNCs had written CSR policies previously and this past finding appears to have not changed after a decade i.e., CSR policies are restricted to written form and practice is not being achieved.

Apart from this, the political and corporate culture of Pakistan is also to be considered which forms the perception of people about different concepts and it sets the trends which are then followed by stakeholders.

This means that when Pakistan's political and corporate culture is not highlighting and promoting the CSR practices directed towards environment then their employees are also expected to consider it less important. A study conducted by Khan et al, (2018) indicated that a small percentage of Pakistani companies on the surface level are dedicated towards CSR, however, when it comes to practice and reality, these companies are not integrating CSR practices in their business functions. This example is also indicating that the concept of CSR was not being considered adequately in Pakistan and it required more research for this purpose which unfortunately have not happened to a large extent. Despite of receiving one sided trend in the answers of respondents, mixed responses were received about the impact of ECSR on employer branding as some respondents were of the view that it does affect the reputation of employers, and some believed that it does not affect. For example, some responses can be reviewed below which are supporting this analysis:

One respondent from company X stated that, "Yes, I think the reputation is being compromised due to lack of focus on environmental CSR". One respondent from company X stated that, "I am not sure, but I think it does affect negatively because when other companies are doing one thing and you are missing out on it then people do notice it".

One respondent from company Y stated that, "I think it should, but I am not sure if it actually happens". One respondent from company Y stated that, "I do not think this happens, we do not normally pay attention on this". One respondent from company Z stated that, "I have no idea about it, I have not heard about it before that any such thing can happen".

Therefore, it can be stated here that the overall cultural dimensions of Pakistan have posed an impact on the way millennial employees are perceiving and understanding the concept of CSR and its environmental dimension.

A key finding of this study is that telecom companies in Pakistan are not bothered much about the implementation of environmental CSR practices because their performance is not receiving any negative impacts as a result of their negligence towards CSR practices. This finding contradicts from the literature findings as, Pittz et al, (2017); and Tanwar and Prasad, (2017) have found that a strong employer branding gives boost to firm performance and also enhances the willingness of employees to continue working with the same employer.

This research evidence is indicating the deeply embedded nature of employer branding concept, however in the context of Pakistan the consideration of CSR in such depth is not visible because MNCs and one local telecom company operating in Pakistan are keeping their millennial employees satisfied and relatively disinterested in CSR issues. Moreover, it can also be identified here that telecom companies in Pakistan are not using CSR as a strategic tool of competitive advantage because their employer brand is being fulfilled with probably factors other than environmental CSR. However, respondents in this study have not mentioned about integration of CSR activities in daily operations, rather most of the times employees were not even aware of it.

Greer and Hauptmeier, (2016); and Younis et al, (2020) have mentioned that matching organizational values with employees that are being hired is important for attracting competent individuals and employees have to feel attracted towards employers based on their image. This literature finding is being contradicted by the results of this study because either the telecom companies have found an organization fit using factors other than environmental CSR or the values of the telecom companies by ignoring CSR are not letting the expectations of employees down and are anyway attracting competent employees. This also shows that their performance is not affect due to their non- attention towards natural environment. Below are some responses/quotes of the respondents supporting this analysis:

One respondent from company Z stated that, “it is the responsibility of the company to think about environment related issues and it is as if you are asking employees more than their capacity because I have not witnessed any such example before and never heard of it before”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “I only read it in the books during my studies and that was also not much, I have not heard about this concept in my colleagues, but we know about it and in this industry, I think people know about it, but they do not implement it.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “The way our company communicates information with us, we have read about it, and I personally have seen that people show concern about environment very less because of the job pressures and goals given by the department”.

One respondent from company X stated that, “My company do CSR by helping people and we keep hearing about their achievements in CSR.

These responses are indicating that millennial employees are not sure or clear about the impact of CSR practices on the attractiveness of the employer.

Moreover, it can be noticed that employees are too busy and occupied with their work that they are not able to pay attention towards the CSR issues. Salary, career progression, brand name, social endorsement and socially responsible practices are some factors that attracts employees (Turban and Greening, 1996; DeMelo et al, 2017; Wang et al, 2020). Therefore, in the light of literature findings and responses given by millennial employees, it can be stated here that telecom sector employers have the understanding that for attracting competent employees they do not have to engage regularly in CSR activities, rather they have to offer employees what they are looking for which can be good salary, career growth or recognition.

The discussion on this theme has indicated that the mindset of millennial employees in the telecom sector is not adequately focused on CSR concept and they do not view environmental CSR as a decisive factor for employers to be attractive. Different socio-economic and cultural factors and the exposition to the CSR concept during their educational period is not sufficient which is not allowing millennials to consider and view CSR as a strategic tool which has a significant scope and potential to implicate in many ways.

Even though the consideration and understanding of the CSR concept has not been found as significant in the telecom sector of Pakistan, however at the same time it has been evident from results that millennial employee does have the basic understanding and awareness of CSR and especially the environmental CSR. This finding gives positivity and encouragement for future research studies and gives an indication that the acceptance and integration of CSR concept is gradually prevailing across Pakistan's business and corporate arena. Below given are some quotes of respondents which supports this evidence:

One respondent from company Y has stated that, "I think for obeying the environmental laws and obligations, it is very important for the employers to do their business by being conscious of the natural environment around".

Some respondents of company X and Z stated that the morale and confidence of employees increases when company takes initiatives for the natural environment. As per my observation the awareness of Environmental CSR exists in my colleagues and co-workers, but we still need a lot more and we together need to put extra milestones in environment side of CSR".

One respondent from company X stated that, “My company do CSR by helping people and we keep hearing about their achievements in CSR, and I think we are aware of this concept because in this country we have serious environmental issues”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “If we look at the situation of our city and country overall, it is for sure a major need”.

These quotes are reflecting that the foundations of environmental CSR are present in the telecom sector of Pakistan which can make it relatively easy and logical to provide suggestions for its improvement. Overall, it can be stated here that the notion of environmental CSR is slowly and gradually taking its place in the telecom industry, however it is being overshadowed for several reasons which are contextual, business related and person specific as well. These reasons have been discussed under the heading of previous theme.

It is clear from the answers that millennial employees want their employers to be socially responsible companies and consider the protection of the natural environment as well. The importance of environment as a key element of CSR can be determined from the fact that ISO and EU include environment in their CSR frameworks by laying emphasis on environment as a prominent force that shapes the standing of businesses. This reaffirmation and validation of environment as integral part of CSR can be observed from the responses of millennial employees in Pakistan’s telecom sector as well. Cone Communications, (2015); and Ikhida et al, (2020) have mentioned that millennial generation employees are more sensitive towards CSR issues, and they do believe that businesses hold major responsibility towards protecting the environment.

These literature review findings have been reinstated in the interview results; however, it is also evident that the extent and depth of this reinstatement need further improvement across millennials and is not convincing so far in Pakistan’s telecom sector. Telecom sector of Pakistan is dominant by MNCs of different countries including China, UAE, Norway and Egypt. Only one telecom company ‘Z’ is a Pakistani public sector company and is a wholly owned subsidiary of Pakistan Telecommunication Company Limited. Therefore, the results are indicating that that how these MNCs have implemented their CSR culture in Pakistan so far and how concerned these are about protecting natural environment i.e., results are not encouraging, and it appears that MNCs have diverged from their original CSR focus and practices in Pakistan which has also restricted the prevalence of CSR understanding in telecom sector of Pakistan.

Similarly, the preferences of millennial employees who are expected to be conscious and reactive towards environmental issues has not been encouraging so far which is not adequately aligned with the literature findings i.e., there is a margin of improvement in terms of how conscious and sensitive millennials are towards natural environment protection under CSR practices. This finding is also raising a question mark on the extent to which current telecom sector big companies are fulfilling their social responsibility by taking care of natural environment which is their key stakeholder. CSR is a concept essentially prevailed across the developed country context, and since MNCs are operating in Pakistan's telecom sector, which is a developing country context, therefore a key finding of this study can be the divergent role being played by MNCs in Pakistan in relation with ECSR awareness and implementation.

The finding extracted so far about the education system through which millennials have gone through, the corporate culture of the telecom companies and other socio-cultural factors, all these factors have majorly shaped the view and understanding of millennial employees about the concept of CSR. The process of CSR allows managers to establish stakeholder engagement and drive their relationship positively (Sarfraz et al, 2018; Donia et al, 2019). This literature review finding is applicable in the context of Pakistan's telecom sector in where the telecom companies' own culture and the overall business environment is not paying significant attention towards CSR practices especially in terms of focus on environment.

As a result, the awareness of CSR and environmental side of CSR has remained at a very basic level and has not prospered the way it should have been in the presence of MNCs in telecom industry and the characteristics of millennials. The answers of respondents that falls under this theme were mixed as a clear trend about having the awareness was not achieved. Some respondents believed that awareness exists, and some believed it did not exist.

Respondents have shown awareness of the environmental issues that are prevailing across the country and this awareness is in line with the literature findings which confirms that Pakistan is facing serious environmental problems. Environmental issues especially climate change has been a significant problem that Pakistan is facing from the last few decades. Air pollution and water pollution/ water waste are the highlights of environmental problems faced by Pakistan in parallel of the industrial, agriculture and other economic developments (Khan and Awan, 2020).

These issues are giving rise to several health-related problems which have been pointed out by World Health Organization. Pakistan has been ranked 3rd in the world by the International Monetary Fund among countries where water shortage is present (Qureshi, 2020).

One respondent from company X stated that, “My company do CSR by helping people and we keep hearing about their achievements in CSR, and I think we are aware of this concept because in this country we have serious environmental issues”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “until recently I was not aware of this field in the business world because I used to think that environment protection is separate from doing business, but I have now seen that government is taking different steps for this purpose and they have asked our company as well to play our role in this.”.

Overall, it can be stated here that the notion of environmental CSR is slowly and gradually taking its place in the telecom industry, however it is being overshadowed for several reasons which are contextual, business related and person specific as well. However, the kind of environmental challenges Pakistan is facing, it can be stated here that MNCs and one local telecom company are not doing justice with their CSR practices and are not playing their role appropriately due to which the awareness and understanding about the concept of CSR is not prevailing across millennials. By undertaking effective CSR practices in such situation, telecom sector companies can certainly reap benefits of improving their brand image and employer attractiveness.

This also shows that telecom employers in Pakistan are lacking in the development of CSR policies and practices. There needs to be specific CSR standards and regulations that telecom employers should follow for making sure that they are behaving in a socially responsible way in the society where they are doing business.

Concerns have been raised in Pakistan about the network towers being installed by telecom companies near and within the populated areas of different cities. It has been mentioned that telecom companies are contributing towards air pollution which does not help in improving employer branding. Air pollution is another key environmental issue faced by Pakistan which has increased consistently in the last decade (Habib et al, 2021). A panel of top judges in Pakistan recently gave orders to the government for detailing their efforts towards managing the air pollution which shows the threatening nature of this issue.

Especially the urban cities where most industrial and business development has occurred, are facing deteriorating situation of air quality. A report published by Medical Journal Lancet in 2015 stated that approximately 22% of annual deaths are caused by air pollution in Pakistan (Shaikh and Tunio, 2018).

Despite of all these facts and information, even the millennial employees are not finding it concerning or alarming and they are not proactive about it because of their lack of awareness and understanding about the concept of CSR. This finding is rejecting, and invalidating arguments of scholars presented in literature and is giving a new finding that employer attractiveness and reputation is not affected by CSR practices.

Government intervention and awareness campaigns by private sector have become inevitable for managing air pollution especially during smog period (Rehman, 2018). However, despite of these challenges, millennial employees are not aware of any prominent CSR campaign or environment related initiative that their employers might have taken independently as well as by entering into a partnership with Government. This finding is not positive and encouraging because MNCs are dominant in telecom industry. Quotes of respondents presented below are supporting this discussion:

Two respondents from company X stated that, “Plantation is very seriously required as green campaign and then all social media platforms are important for communicating the message of the group”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “I think social media platforms are working well for the company, however, I strongly believe that joining hands with any Government initiative will provide great benefits to the company itself”.

One respondent from company X stated that, “To be honest, I have never read or seen any such information so I cannot say this can influence me or not, but I remember recently our Prime Minister Chaired an international conference on environment”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “I think if a telecom company pledges its commitment and joins hands with government’s initiatives like Billion Tree Tsunami only then I think I will consider them as attractive”.

Natural environment being a key stakeholder of the businesses needs to be taken care of and preserved. It is the responsibility of big businesses along with government to engage in protecting the natural environment in which they are doing business. Therefore, it can be stated that conducting CSR practices with focus on environment by businesses in Pakistan is imperative for managing the prevailing environmental issues in the country. Even the respondents are aware about the Government level initiatives, and they suggested for telecom companies to join hands with Government on initiatives to preserve natural environment. Billion Tree Tsunami project has been mentioned by the respondents which has also gained acclaim and recognition at the international level (UN Environmental Programme, 2020). This shows that there are opportunities available for giant telecom companies for engaging in environment driven CSR in Pakistan.

Moreover, the kind of environmental problems Pakistan is facing exhibits the dire need of creating awareness about the serosity of ECSR in Pakistan. Engaging in this research study is one significant way of improving understanding and awareness about the management of environmental issues especially by putting pressure on big companies to initiate ECSR activities by realising their responsibility. As mentioned by one respondent, the Prime Minister of Pakistan was given the chance to Lead the environment protection and sustainability conference recently in March because international agencies acknowledged the efforts of Pakistan towards plantation. Boris Johnson also appreciated this initiative of Pakistan and suggested other countries to follow the same project for making sure the protection of natural environment.

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Two respondents from company X stated that, “Plantation is very seriously required as green campaign and then all social media platforms are important for communicating the message of the group”.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “The company should proactively use social media platforms for running campaigns about changing weather or climate which is an international issue as well”. Two respondents from company Y stated that, “Taking care of animals, birds and plants are some very important factors that the company needs to engage in by launching different ongoing trends”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “For improving employer branding, the company needs to focus on creating awareness about different social and environmental issues such as, water and food wastage, preserving and keeping trees/ plants”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “I think if a telecom company pledges its commitment and joins hands with government’s initiatives like Billion Tree Tsunami only then I think I will consider them as attractive”.

Natural environment being a key stakeholder of the businesses needs to be taken care of and preserved. It is the responsibility of big businesses along with government to engage in protecting the natural environment in which they are doing business. Therefore, it can be stated that conducting CSR practices with focus on environment by businesses in Pakistan is imperative for managing the prevailing environmental issues in the country. Even the respondents are aware about the Government level initiatives, and they suggested for telecom companies to join hands with Government on initiatives to preserve natural environment. Billion Tree Tsunami project has been mentioned by the respondents which has also gained acclaim and recognition at the international level (UN Environmental Programme, 2020). This shows that there are opportunities available for giant telecom companies for engaging in environment driven CSR in Pakistan.

Moreover, the kind of environmental problems Pakistan is facing exhibits the dire need of creating awareness about the serosity of ECSR in Pakistan. Engaging in this research study is one significant way of improving understanding and awareness about the management of environmental issues especially by putting pressure on big companies to initiate ECSR activities by realising their responsibility. As mentioned by one respondent, the Prime Minister of Pakistan was given the chance to Lead the environment protection and sustainability conference recently in March because international agencies acknowledged the efforts of Pakistan towards plantation. Boris Johnson also appreciated this initiative of Pakistan and suggested other countries to follow the same project for making sure the protection of natural environment.

The results have indicated that COVID-19 crisis has not made much difference in the opinion and perception of millennial employees working in the telecom sector. They have certainly acknowledged that environment focus attitude is required and such policies needs to be devised that can protect the environment while doing business. However, the consideration of CSR as a construct which can drive or implicate on their decision about choosing an employer and as a construct which can affect employer attractiveness is not present.

Most of the interviews were conducted during the COVID-19 crisis, however the millennial respondents as employees did not give high importance to CSR policies and not convincingly linked the far-reaching implications of COVID-19 with CSR initiatives.

They viewed COVID-19 as a distinct and independent phenomenon which needs to be dealt by the government, hospitals and people themselves. Personal factors such as, knowledge of CSR, awareness of CSR, age, gender and cultural background are important when it comes to attracting employees (Ogunmokun et al, 2020; Waples et al, 2020). Therefore, it appears that personal factors along with previously mentioned contextual factors are quite strong in Pakistan which are restricting the improvement in the understanding of millennials about CSR concept and environment being its vital element. Below presented quotes of respondents are supporting this discussion:

One respondent from company X stated that, "It is definitely a wakeup call, but I do not see its connection with CSR". One respondent from company Y stated that, "I do not think companies can do much about it because it happened naturally from outside Pakistan, and we can only try to manage it by being careful".

One respondent from company Y stated that, "Government is fighting this issue properly and I do believe that companies should strictly follow guidelines of government to keep their brand attractive". One respondent from company Z stated that, "It can be a factor for coming years because we do not know when it is going to end and when it will hit us back".

The literature finding presented in chapter two are helpful in understanding the responses given by the millennial respondents. In the results, it was observed that no employer has engaged in collaboration or partnership with government or non-government organizations because some respondents were viewing this option as a feasible one and they were aware of some government led initiatives directed towards environmental sustainability. Below presented quotes are supporting this discussion:

One respondent from company Y stated that, "I think we do understand about the environmental issues, and I have often had discussions with my colleagues about how green initiatives can be taken by our company for giving back to the society and natural environment around us because the government is giving it priority from last few years".

One respondent from company Z stated that, “I think if a telecom company pledges its commitment and joins hands with government’s initiatives like Billion Tree Tsunami only then I think I will consider them as attractive”.

Therefore, it has been found that government in Pakistan is quite interested in initiating environment driven projects and their exposition has been extensive due to which millennials are aware of it. However, the chosen telecom companies being the giants in the market have not joined hands with government or any other agency for adding their contribution towards preserving the environment which has restricted the understanding of millennial respondents about the pragmatic importance of CSR.

The novel Corona Virus outbreak also known as COVID-19 created multiple health implications all across the world causing The World Health Organization to declare an emergency. Multiple economic, as well as social risks, were created because of the COVID-19 outbreak. Similar to the past example, business organizations need to understand their social responsibility in such kinds of scenarios and take rapid actions to ensure suitable future development after the pandemic (Ding et al. 2020).

COVID-19 also tends to impose a different challenge for the organizations related to CSR. However, there had been many organizations that did not attempt to exploit this pandemic situation and even provided suitable support to the people for combating the COVID-19 pandemic (Lindsay et al, 2020). These contemporary literature findings are making it clear that local and MNCs operating in telecom sector of Pakistan needs to play their role in managing the COVID crisis effectively and renewed focus on CSR is a desirable way of doing so. Companies need to transmit this renewed focus at their employee levels as well for availing meaningful results.

5.2 Organizational Identification and Social Identity Application

A key finding identified from the interview results is the absence of employee voice behaviour across the telecom companies of Pakistan. This absence is undermining the potential of millennial employees to influence their employers in different ways which includes the impact of employer attractiveness. As per Umme-Rubab and Naqvi, (2020) trust of employees can be developed and improved about their employers when employee voice behaviour is encouraged.

The Pakistani culture and its people have a strong inclination towards teamwork and they believe in unconditional loyalty of their respective groups. The individuals in Pakistani society have the ability to take responsibilities of their primary group. The family structure is such that the financial dependency of the entire family rests with one or two individuals. In addition, the Pakistani society has a culture of strong bonds with extended family network (Islam, 2004) and the notion of individualism of the western urban setup is absent in Pakistan. An individual in Pakistan is an integral part of the group thus carrying shared belief. In the corporate sector, the decisions are taken by the executive board rather than an individual. This also includes the executive decisions pertaining to recruitment, retention and even termination of employment as endorsed by Hofstede's results. Morale and engagement level of employees also increases when organizational environment allows them to express their viewpoints and ideas (Prince and Roa, 2021). In line with these literature findings, the quotes stated by the respondents can be analysed adequately and a clear picture can be drawn. Some quotes of respondents supporting this analysis are presented below:

One respondent from company X stated that, "They do not share such information frequently and they never ask us". One respondent from company Z stated that, "I remember last year the company shared some figures about their social work after which I do not think they have shared anything, and they do not take our input anyway".

One respondent from company X stated that, "I cannot say anything about it because I am not aware about their working process about CSR because mostly such information is restricted to managers".

One respondent from company Z stated that, “Yes in terms of annual reports we can say this happens because I have seen that CSR is talked about in these reports, but apart from annual publication of report, no internal communication happens”.

Societies with a low score in this dimension have a tendency to cynicism and pessimism. Also, in contrast to Indulgent societies, Restrained societies do not put much emphasis on leisure time and control the gratification of their desires. Pakistan, with an extremely low score of 0 on this dimension, can be said to be a very Restrained society. People with this orientation have the perception that their actions are Restrained by social norms and feel that indulging themselves is somewhat wrong. Relatively weak control is called “Indulgence” and relatively strong control is called “Restraint”. It is appearing that in Pakistan’s telecom sector in line with Pakistan’s national and social culture, a restraint culture is in place. Cultures can, therefore, be described as restrained in telecom sector of Pakistan due to which employees are not confident and concerned in a desirable manner towards the issue of environmental CSR and are not pragmatically viewing their employers from this lens. Millennials working in Pakistan’s telecom sector are following the norms primarily and are not indulging in the issues of ECSR which they feel are out of their domain and authority.

Stewart et al. (2017) list some of the common Millennial’s traits, such as seeking a team-based workplace, having a lack of initiative and their lack of etiquette. They also talk about how Millennials value different things in the organization that they work in, such as frequent feedback and not being willing to fully commit their time to their work. Confident, team players, smart, rule-followers and optimistic are some characteristics of millennials generally mentioned across literature (Hui et al, 2021). Given the nature of their characteristics, MNCs operating in the telecom sector are expected to enable employee voice behaviour for encouraging millennials to give their input and be involved in the pursuit of being a socially responsible organization.

However, millennial employees have indicated that management maintain only one-dimensional communication and that too is not frequent from the top when it comes to CSR. By not motivating and encouraging millennials to give their input and ideas, telecom companies in Pakistan have given them a psychological message that employees cannot influence the decision making and activities of the company.

As a result of this, a mindset across millennial employees is prevailing that their input is either not important or not required in the matters related to CSR. This way, the telecom sector companies are not adhering to the stakeholder theory which asserts that employees are key stakeholders of organizations. Therefore, telecom firms in Pakistan have established their position as a brand in the minds of employees without involving the CSR construct. Millennial employees want to engage in employee voice behaviour as mentioned by some respondents in the interview results which means that this absence is restricting their exposure and awareness which is not productive for employers.

A key finding identified from the interview results is the absence of employee voice behaviour across the telecom companies of Pakistan. This absence is undermining the potential of millennial employees to influence their employers in different ways which includes the impact of employer attractiveness. As per Umme-Rubab and Naqvi, (2020) trust of employees can be developed and improved about their employers when employee voice behaviour is encouraged.

Morale and engagement level of employees also increases when organizational environment allows them to express their viewpoints and ideas (Prince and Roa, 2021). In line with these literature findings, the quotes stated by the respondents can be analysed adequately and a clear picture can be drawn. Some quotes of respondents supporting this analysis are presented below:

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One of these respondents from company Z stated that, “as an idea it can be good but I do not think that in reality many employees will agree with this because we have other important issues on which we often need to raise our concerns with the company and it becomes difficult for us sometimes to get the solution of our problems in the way we want, so I do not think we have power to influence on environment related matters”.

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This identified theme is reflecting that millennial employees of telecom sector do possess basic level of moral and social identity which is a positive sign in the context of considering CSR as influencer of employer branding. However, the extent of moral and social identity is not high and convincing because of neglecting behaviour being displayed by the employers. Taking value from symbolic interactionism, OIT focuses on the perspective related to the language, meaning and thought organizing the connection of the employees with the organization. Identity theory supports understanding the need by which the organizations must keep the stakeholders engaged with themselves to achieve desired success (Lupina-Wegener et al, 2020).

The social identity theory had been used in different perspectives for proposing the relationship between the expected employee outcomes and perceived CSR mediated through the organizational identity (Hogg and Terry, 2004). Specifically, when the employee perceives the organizational CSR positively, then they remain satisfied and develop a strong relationship with the organization as well. It leads towards a positive attitude from the employees at work (Gioia et al, 2013).

In the light of these theoretical understandings and assumptions, the results can be analysed by stating that organizational identification among millennial employees does not exist considerably and visibly. Below presented quotes of respondents are supporting this discussion that

One respondent from company X stated that, “Yes, I often relate myself with companies who are putting efforts towards our environment”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “This applies only to the extent when a campaign is being run because during that period you feel that association which is natural to happen for me, but it is temporary only”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “I find it closer to human nature and there is no surprise that one can develop association for the company even if the company is not my employer”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “I can say that if you see anything positive happening around you feel good about it, and I can relate myself with that company doing any good to our environment”.

One respondent from company X stated that, “I would love to stay for longer but to be honest I am not sure how practical this decision can be”.

It has therefore been found that moral identity exists among millennial employees to a large extent, and they also have exhibited social identity. For example, most of the respondents admitted that if an employer is taking environment friendly decisions, then they will develop an association with the employer. Moreover, the word ‘our environment’ has been mentioned by some respondents while referring to the natural environment and ECSR which indicates that they can relate themselves with environment as an external construct. However, it is not clear that to what extent millennials are identifying themselves with their respective employers in relation with CSR efforts.

Given the responses of millennial employees it cannot be evidently said that they have no organizational identification because it is already mentioned in the previous themes that awareness of CSR concept is not high among these millennials. However, they do exhibit moral traits and social identity. These findings are also indicating that telecom employers in Pakistan are lacking in the development of CSR policies and practices.

Previous studies showcased a relationship between the employees' reaction and perceived CSR with a mediating role of organizational identity. For instance, Carmeli et al. (2007) recommend the organizations make use of perceived CSR to promote the organizational identity amongst the employees to gain better employee outcomes (Jones, 2010), intent to stay (Jones, 2010), job satisfaction (Kim et al., 2018), and job performance (De Roeck et al., 2014). In the light of these literature findings and comparing them with responses of millennials, it can be said that a low level of organizational identification does exist among millennials of telecom sector.

Making use of self-categorization theory (Turner et al., 1987), individuals tend to evaluate the linkage between their self-categorization process and social group to activate their social identity by categorizing themselves as a group member. Making use of identity-based perspective (Tajfel and Turner, 1986; Hogg et al., 2004), individuals take part in the groups aligned with their attributes and values positively to meet their psychological needs related to the sense of being and attributions. It allows the individuals to compare their similarities and differences with each other in a particular group. These literature findings are holding true in the case of millennial employees under discussion because some respondents indicated relatively less care about ethical responsibilities or activities. Moreover, as per the answers of respondents and secondary research evidence, telecom companies are not actively engaged in CSR activities due to which it is highly unlikely that organizational identification exists among millennial employees.

However, the chances or probability of organizational identification to be established are present which is a positive sign. Below presented quotes of respondents are supporting this analysis:

One respondent from company X stated that, "Definitely yes, I will be happy with my employer and will not think about leaving the company especially when our country is not doing great with environment". One respondent from company X stated that, "I would love to stay for longer but to be honest I am not sure how practical this decision can be".

One respondent from company Z stated that, “This is a difficult question to answer because I seriously want this to happen in reality but given the circumstances I might not stay solely because of this reason”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “If this happens this will definitely help me take decision about my stay with my employer because overall, I am already satisfied with my employer”.

A key point to be noted here is that few telecom employers have had undertaken some CSR initiatives in the past and this has not been turned into a regular activity. Moreover, it has been identified that employers are not taking CSR initiatives with special focus on environment i.e., environmental side of CSR is being neglected by employers. This means that some kind of focus on other aspects of CSR has allowed millennial employees to develop moral and social identity to some extent.

It has been found in the interview results that millennial are working in a tough work routine and this theme is indicating that due to the work pressure at workplace, millennials tend to pay less attention towards the internal and external communication being pursued by the telecom companies. Given the tough work routine, it is probable that work-life-balance of employees becomes at stake of disturbance which can ultimately affect the level of concentration, attention and focus paid by employees on information other than their job. It can be stated here that the low level of awareness and understanding about CSR concept in practice and not being proactive towards ethical issues by millennials is also due to this tough work routine. Below presented quotes of respondents are indicating the validation of this sub-theme and the direction of discussion being carried out:

One respondent from company Y stated that, “The way our company communicates information with us, we have read about it and I personally have seen that people show concern about environment very less because of the job pressures and goals given by the department”. One respondent from company X stated that, “the flow of information is very fast these days and to be honest I do not pay much attention to such information because of my job routine”.

Another respondent from company X stated that, “I do not have time to see and read such adverts, I have hectic job routine”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “I am too busy in my job, I have no time to think and read about this stuff”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “The weather conditions in our city are not good for most of the months and on top of it the work pressure and dealing with customers affects my mood, but this eco-friendly environment will definitely make me happy”.

It can be noted that respondents are mentioning about work pressure even when the question was focused on something else which reflects that work pressure exists in reality and it is part of their work routine which restricts them from engaging in different other activities or makes them disinterested in CSR related activities/ information.

5.3 Relevance of Stakeholder Perspective

This identified theme is indicating that telecom sector employers in Pakistan are not paying attention towards addressing the expectations of employees and preservation of environment. It has been noted that telecom companies are not adhering to the stakeholder theory which is highly regarded across contemporary CSR literature. The focus of CSR lies on nine important factors, which include governance, business relationships, ethics, value of product, employment policies, financial gains, transparency, and involvement of community and protection of environment (Statman, 2018).

Environment has emerged as a key pillar of CSR in the last two decades especially with the emphasis paid by ISO and EU on this issue. It is surprising that despite of international consideration and focus on CSR, the telecom companies are not adhering to the global CSR trends especially when majority of telecom companies in Pakistan are MNCs. Customers as key stakeholders are not receiving relevant treatment across telecom sector of Pakistan because employers are neglecting their requirements and demands as stakeholders. In addition to this, the employers are paying more attention towards providing services to the customers and introducing new products/services i.e., a sale and profit-oriented focus is evident among telecom employers.

As a result of this, the millennial employees have developed a disinterest towards CSR activities and information i.e., they are kept busy in their job routines and work stress keeps their mind diverted. It has been found that millennial employees are not aware and informed about important CSR related activities and practices by employers.

Moreover, it has been identified that employers are not taking CSR initiatives with special focus on environment i.e., environmental side of CSR is being neglected by employers. Below presented quotes of respondents are supporting this discussion:

One company Z respondent stated that, “as an idea it can be good but I do not think that in reality many employees will agree with this because we have other important issues on which we often need to raise our concerns with the company and it becomes difficult for us sometimes to get the solution of our problems in the way we want, so I do not think we have power to influence on environment related matters”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “as an employee I am not worried about these things so I cannot answer properly on this”. One respondent from company Z stated that, “it is the responsibility of the company to think about environment related issues and it is as if you are asking employees more than their capacity because I have not witnessed any such example before and never heard of it before”.

The widespread agenda of CSR involves certain issues like those involved in the process of anti-corruption, product responsibility, animal testing and greenhouse gas emissions. Multinational corporations working at a large scale have to make contributions to the country in which they operate. It is expected by MNCs to play their role for the benefit of the entire community other than the business motives. Other examples include the concept of corporate citizenship (Matten and Crane, 2017).

This literature finding is strengthening the argument that has been extracted from the results i.e. apart from 1 local player, all the other telecom companies are MNCs in Pakistan who are not following the CSR agenda prevailing across the globe. It is therefore a question mark on the CSR performance and commitment of MNCs as well.

CSR also emerges as the need of MNCs from political perspective of CSR. The common factor among all these concepts is the basic or central function of the stakeholder approach (Mehra, 2014). Practically it has been argued that it is the key responsibility and interest of any corporation to pay regard to its stakeholders. This literature finding is indicating that from a political perspective of CSR, telecom sector MNCs in Pakistan should have displayed high orientation towards CSR and especially environmental side of CSR.

Stakeholder theory taking value from managerial mechanisms informs that an organization must take care of its stakeholders positively that could be affected by its actions (Freeman, 1984). Freeman (1984) defines a stakeholder as an individual carrying influential power within the organizational operations. The stakeholder theory focuses on the key relationship existing between the organizations with its social welfare, communities, customers, and employees (Donaldson & Preston, 1995). Francis et al. (2019) also defines it as a leading paradigm related to CSR.

This theoretical perspective is indicating that employees as stakeholders do possess power to influence by default and the telecom employers of Pakistan are failing to comply with stakeholder theory by not protecting the interest of their key stakeholders. Below presented quotes of respondents are supporting this analysis:

One respondent from company X stated that, “Yes, employees as stakeholders should influence their employers to practice environmental CSR to give quality of services to their maximum customer within limit of resources”.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “I think in today’s social media world we employees have some powers and we definitely can use this power for influencing our employers about their business activities to respect the natural environment conditions”.

A valuable analysis in this regard is the consideration of a recently conducted empirical CSR study in Pakistan by Bux et al, (2020) which identified the barriers of CSR adoption in Pakistan. Lack of concern for reputation, lack of interest by customers about CSR, lack of policy incentives, and lack of regulations/ standards were found as some key barriers. Bux et al, (2020) also concluded that government as implementing agency and as stakeholder needs to act as moderator for managing these issues and making sure that CSR is being integrated across manufacturing industry of Pakistan.

Analysing this literature finding with interview results, it can be observed that telecom employers in Pakistan are lacking in the development of CSR policies and practices. This finding has been reaffirmed again in this theme as it was mentioned in two previous themes as well. Development and use of policies, standards and regulations has also been mentioned in literature for pushing companies to practice environmental CSR policies (Ng et al, 2020; Jamali and Karam, 2018).

This also strengthens the finding of this theme that telecom employers are neglecting employees and environment because one of the many reasons behind is the lack of policy and regulations support. Telecom sector employers in Pakistan are not pursuing corporate branding for achieving strategic competitive advantage which can be due to the reason that market dynamics in Pakistan are different as compared to developed countries. The role of political and social culture also becomes evident here which was mentioned earlier in the first identified theme.

This reflects that cultural trend are impacting on the way telecom sector employers are pursuing CSR practices and these factors are essentially shaping the understanding of millennial employees. The objective of generating sales and profits across telecom sector employers is overshadowing the environmental and CSR goals as these employers are trying to fulfil their ethical, environmental and philanthropic expectations by merely engaging in some charity work and that too with a long gap.

This is one reason why employer branding is not being viewed in its original form and is far from its actual meaning in the telecom sector of Pakistan. The national culture of Pakistan is such that it does not significantly tilts towards being disciplined and preparing goals for future systematically i.e., future orientation of Pakistan is not high with a score of 50. This is reflected from the interview results as well that employees were not thinking much about their future plans of employment, and they were happy with the way they were being treated in the present. Since low future orientation has kept the employees attentive towards their present situation more and ignore the future developments and progression, due to which employees did not seek environmental CSR standing of telecom employers as decisive. Generation Y employees tend to guide their parents and relatives about using information technology (Coates, 2017), and the use of IT and social media by generation Y employees have made them socially more active than generation X employees (Kultalahti & Liisa-Viitala, 2014). In addition, generation Y employees are more conscious about interacting with people on the social media (Fok & Yeung, 2016). However, this comparative finding from literature is not appearing true or valid in the context of generation Y employees working in telecom sector of Pakistan. Moreover, telecom employers are not considering these factors because they are appearing as less concerned about the environmental CSR issues, and they are pursuing employer branding from a totally different perspective.

The investigation of outcomes suggests that MNCs have a range of social programs which are designed to address general social issues such as public health and education, rather than as an outcome of a specific environmental assessment exercise. Exceptions are when MNCs come under direct pressure from the community to address natural unexpected crises or disasters (Yunis et al, 2018). In the context of Pakistan, the empirical evidence has suggested that none of the MNCs are involved in a formal and systematic environmental assessment process which is a key component of environmental CSR practices. The CSR activities of most of the MNCs operating in Pakistan address general social issues such as tree planting. Education and health mainly. CSR is not considered a core business function due to these cultural and social dimensions which ultimately keeps the attention of companies less towards environmental CSR (Yunis et al, 2018).

5.4 Pursuing Employer Branding

Communication is integral when it comes to developing employer branding especially in the age of social media when flow of information and communication channels are efficient (Illia et al, 2017). However, it has been found in the results of interviews that telecom employers in Pakistan are not using a formal communication strategy due to which their millennial employees are largely unaware and uninformed about CSR activities and engagements. This particular theme has been developed by considering the importance of communication strategy for employer branding and by observing that telecom employers are falling short of this practice.

At the organizational level, greater uncertainty avoidance results in more feedback and preparation, as well as more planned and controlled innovation. It scores notably high on power distance and in-group collectivism but low on assertiveness and gender egalitarianism. This finding implies that Pakistan as a society accepts an unequal distribution of power; in which people express pride in, loyalty to, and cohesiveness with their families and society; where people avoid assertive, confrontational, or aggressive behaviour; and that acknowledges clear differences in gender roles in society.

Internal branding holds importance for engaging and keeping existing employees on board about CSR activities and policies being implemented by the employer (Lindhom, 2018). Communication is the most important method of conducting internal branding and telecom employers in Pakistan are not even undertaking frequent, comprehensive and clear communication with the millennial employees. In the presence of social media platforms, inefficiency and less frequent use of information sharing is a surprising finding of this study. Rasheed et al, (2021); and Garas et al, (2018) have stated that communication strategy of a company is imperative for achieving employee engagement and positive attitude of employees can be achieved by building a strong employer brand.

Below presented quotes of respondents are supporting this theme discussion and is indicating that millennials do have an opinion about environmental CSR and currently there is a weak internal branding pursued by telecom employers in Pakistan:

Two respondents from company X stated that, “Plantation is very seriously required as green campaign and then all social media platforms are important for communicating the message of the group,”.

One respondent from company X stated that, “In my opinion the company should raise awareness and do some practical steps about the air pollution which is becoming more dangerous every year”.

One respondent from company Y stated that, “The company should proactively use social media platforms for running campaigns about changing weather or climate which is an international issue as well”.

Two respondents from company Y stated that, “Taking care of animals, birds and plants are some very important factors that the company needs to engage in by launching different ongoing trends”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “I think social media platforms are working well for the company, however, I strongly believe that joining hands with any Government initiative will provide great benefits to the company itself”.

This EU, (2008) CSR framework (which focused on environmental CSR) and the interview results are indicating that telecom employers especially the MNCs are not fulfilling and adhering to this EU framework of CSR.

This means that naturally after this ignorance about environmental CSR, employer branding will stay weak and in addition to this, a lack of formal communication strategy is not helping the cause.

The employer brand conveys the company values (Stotz & Wedel-Klein, 2013) and it is appearing in this theme that telecom employers are not conveying their values to millennials about CSR responsibilities and practices. Thus, it cannot be used by millennial employees to compare company values with the own self-concept and own aspired value system and in case of a match to identify with the company and its values (Herriot, 2002; Ross, 1971). Yang et al. (2015) suggest that value is created internally among employees, as the impact of internal branding is consistent across employees' age groups which means that high chances are present that telecom employers are missing out on achieving a strong internal branding.

Internal branding holds potential of providing several benefits to the employers which makes it a viable concept to be adopted, however it is appearing that telecom employers in Pakistan are either not aware about the embedded benefits of internal branding or they are not finding it imperative in Pakistan's context. It is argued that employer branding strategies and CSR initiatives have a positive impact on employee recruitment (Turban & Greening, 1997; Lin et al., 2012), and on employee retention and development (Maier et al., 2001; Cable & Graham, 2000). This literature finding is reflecting that even if telecom employers are not interested in extracting benefits of internal branding, however they still need strong internal branding for conveying their CSR activities.

In the last decade, the topic of environmental sustainability has undoubtedly attracted considerable attention (Paillé and Raineri, 2015). However, it is quite surprising to observe that telecom employers which includes MNCs are not projecting and implementing the concept of environmental sustainability which should get considerable attention given the environmental issues faced by the country.

Social media use is also minimum by employers when it comes to communicating with millennial employees who are active on social media platforms in Pakistan (Majeed et al, 2020). By ignoring internal branding and regular communication, telecom employers are also risking their person-organization fit as person-organization fit is about compatibility between culture and values of a company and its respective image as employer (Geoge, 2020).

The perspective of the person-organisation fit has been commonly used in conjunction with research on the employer brand to explain the level of congruence between employers and employees (Christiaans, 2013). Past research on the person-organisation fit indicates that potential employees compare the prevalent brand of an organisation with their values, needs and ideas, and a match between the two fosters greater attraction towards the organisation for the individual (Schneider, 1987).

This means that in the long run as the millennials will be obtaining improved understanding and awareness about the CSR concept, the person-organization fit can get weakened which can then negatively implicate on employer branding. Due to the cultural differences between developed and developing countries, and due to lack of communication from employers, the millennials in telecom sector of Pakistan might not consider environment related CSR practices of employers while applying for jobs which is appearing true in this study.

However, this trend can change in the coming years as the CSR concept is prevailing gradually across the Pakistan's business and social environment (Zhang and Ahmad, 2021). Linking of corporate interests and environmental/community values is gradually being understood in the context of Pakistan as sustainable growth and development concepts have prevailed significantly in the recent years in Pakistan (Abbas, 2020). Most of the respondents believe that internal communication is not regular and clear by their employers which will weaken the person-organization fit.

However, frequency of communication via social media is also not encouraging. CSR as a concept is not being perceived in the same way by all the employees, therefore a margin of deviation will exist which needs to be considered by the organizations. Role of internal branding becomes crucial here in narrowing this margin of deviation and telecom companies in Pakistan are appearing as not concerned about this factor. Communicating internal brand strategy and embedding it in the communication even for making employees feel valued is worthy of pursuing by employers. Below presented quotes of respondents are supporting this discussion about weak communication and use of social media for internal branding:

One respondent from company X stated that, “To the best of my knowledge, no such communication took place in my company in the last one year”. One respondent from company Y stated that, “Yes, in our formal and informal meetings with higher management, we are told about how the company is fulfilling CSR obligations”.

One respondent from company Z stated that, “Yes in terms of annual reports we can say this happens because I have seen that CSR is talked about in these reports, but apart from annual publication of report, no internal communication happens”.

Overall, the answers have indicated that internal communication is not focused on CSR activities and is more concerned about performance of the employees. Moreover, the frequency and extent of internal communication about CSR activities is not sufficient. In addition to this, social media is not being used with the help of a formal CSR communication policy due to which millennial employees are not aware about the CSR performance of employers, moreover the values and culture of employers are not integrating these policies which can negatively affect the reputation of a company as argued by (Stohl et al, 2017). This finding appeared valid when the researcher visited the Facebook and Instagram pages of telecom companies in Pakistan, and it was found that in the last one year they are mainly focusing on the customers. Moreover, it has been determined in literature that positive assessment of stakeholders can only be influenced by CSR when stakeholders are aware about the social responsibility activities of the company.

Plaskoff, (2017) strongly recommends involving employees to actively take part in creating employee processes in the organization, and Mlk (2018) proposes that involving people from different hierarchical levels in strategy formulation could be a more inclusive approach and lead to a better buy-in from stakeholders. These aspects are being missed by the telecom companies which in turn can affect their employer branding because a small percentage of respondents have indicated their concern about not including them in the process. Ignoring employees as stakeholders is risky practice which telecom companies in Pakistan are following.

Organizational processes and routines allow coordination of different activities and incentives, so that they become congruent and complement each other (Teece et al., 1997). The role of processes is also to create learning, as each repetition develops the task and makes it more efficient, both for the individual engaging in the task and the organization. Internal branding as a process is not targeted towards employees and environmental CSR activities, rather a clear focus on business growth and customer attraction is being practiced by telecom companies in Pakistan. On theoretical grounds, employer branding is not in the position of receiving positive influence from telecom companies' environmental CSR function, however in practice, this is still in progress. For example, employees slowly and gradually are gaining awareness about their expectations as stakeholders and about the negligence of their employers towards the social responsibility.

5.5 Chapter Summary

This chapter has presented detailed discussion and analysis on the data collected through semi-structured interviews. Significant variation in the trends have been observed while analysing the results which shows that millennial employees possess different perception and understanding about the research problem. Five different themes have been identified in this chapter after interpreting the interview results i.e., the results have been categorized into five themes and each theme is underpinning few sub-themes for clearly reflecting on the depth of results. This chapter has concluded that the prevalence of CSR and employer branding concepts in Pakistan's telecom sector is not encouraging and lacks awareness. Millennial employees working in Pakistan's telecom sector are not showcasing characteristics and attributes that are similar to what have been mentioned in the literature.

This chapter has presented that developing and developed country context are functioning in dissimilar ways when it comes to the influence of environment driven CSR practices on employer branding. The understanding and perception of environment driven CSR in Pakistan is vague and employer branding is being perceived from a lens that is different than CSR. Cultural factors and the exposure through education and social life have restricted the understanding of millennials about the CSR practices and employer branding. Research findings are indicating that even though Pakistan is going through serious environment related issues, however the millennials still have not understood the sensitivity of this problem.

Millennials are appeared to be quite busy in their work routine which gives them pressure to keep their attention focused on their jobs, as well as the element of job security is keeping them away from availing effective understanding of CSR and employer branding concepts. With a basic level understanding, currently millennial employees are not creating any influence on employer branding, neither the telecom employers are engaging themselves in CSR practices regularly. MNCs have been found as dominating the telecom sector of Pakistan and two case organizations out of three in this study were MNCs from which data was collected. However, results have shown the MNCs operating in Pakistan are pursuing shareholders approach instead of stakeholder approach.

6 Chapter Six: Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Concluding Remarks

This study has achieved several key concluding remarks after conducting analysis on the interview results in the light of literature. This conclusion section is presenting concluding remarks in line with the achievement of each research objective that was established during first chapter of this study. Identification and evaluation of CSR perception possessed by millennial employees was the first objective which has been addressed. In line with this objective, it has been concluded that the perception of millennial employees is not adequate and in-depth about CSR concept and especially about the nature and scope of environmental CSR. The cultural and contextual factors of Pakistan (e.g., higher education system, political system and priorities, social and hierarchical life) are some of the reasons behind this weaker perception and lack of adequate understanding about CSR.

Millennials are viewing the environmental issues/responsibilities as distinct or separate from CSR which in turn has restricted their perception about employer branding concept as well. Due to the lack of efforts from telecom employers including the MNCs about sustainable development and CSR practices, millennial employees have only basic level of understanding about employer branding. Moreover, a shallow perception about employer branding is evident across millennials because they have not been given the desired exposure by their employers, therefore, employer branding is being perceived as less important construct. The impact and change that CSR and employer branding concepts can bring is not being realized by millennial employees which in turn is giving a safe passage to the telecom employers. This way first objective of the study is being addressed which was about analysing the perception of millennials employees about environmental CSR and employer branding in Pakistan.

In terms of theory, it has been concluded that organizational identification is not being achieved by telecom sector employers of Pakistan because the belongingness of millennial employees has not been reflected from their responses. As per symbolic interactionism, Language, thought and meaning tends to constitute belongingness of employees for their employers and using this perspective of organizational identification theory it has been concluded that due to different reasons most millennial employees does not possess organizational identification.

This failure is two ways i.e., millennial employees lack desired level of awareness about CSR and employer branding concepts due to which they are not able to comprehend the application of organizational identification and the responsibility of employers in this context. This way first objective of the study is being addressed which was about analysing the perception of millennial employees about environmental CSR and employer branding in Pakistan.

Stakeholder theory has stressed on organizations to pay back to the stakeholders and has mentioned that stakeholders expect from organizations to engage in ethical practices. However, despite of wider acclaim of stakeholder theory, it is not being implemented by telecom employers in Pakistan as they are not diverging from the local culture and social norms. This way second objective of this is being addressed which was about analysing the environment related CSR behaviour of telecom companies in Pakistan.

Respecting environmental protection needs is an integral part of CSR which businesses are expected to consider while earning profits and operating in their respective region. However, telecom employers in Pakistan have been concluded as relatively disengaged and disinterested in respecting environmental protection needs despite of the prevailing serious environmental issues in Pakistan. Telecom employers currently are not considering and addressing their environmental burden in Pakistan even when major telecom companies are MNCs in Pakistan. This way second objective of this study is being addressed which was about analysing the environment related CSR behaviour of telecom companies in Pakistan.

It has been concluded that telecom employers are not making use of the opportunity created by COVID-19 crisis by proactively engaging in CSR activities and taking CSR initiatives. Even though pundits and scholars are referring COVID as a potential catalyst in the long run for beginning a new era of CSR development. Given the challenges of COVID and environmental problems of Pakistan, telecom employers could have exhibited their commitment and intent towards environmental CSR. Moreover, millennials are also not able to understand the scope of COVID-19 crisis for employers and they are of the view that government is responsible for dealing with this challenge. Yet again, the lack of understanding, awareness and exposure of millennials is allowing telecom employers to get away with their CSR responsibilities. This way second objective of this study has been addressed which was about evaluating the environment related CSR behaviour of telecom companies in Pakistan.

After addressing the first two research objectives and by considering the concluding remarks presented on these two objectives, it can be stated here that these deviations and unconventional nature of findings is primarily because of the unique developing country context of Pakistan. There is very little evidence available in literature about interplay of CSR and employer branding construct across such developing country context due to which the findings of this study are appearing alien.

By considering the literature review findings about the vital role of CSR in impacting employer branding and by considering the vague understanding and low level of awareness possessed by millennial employees in Pakistan, it has been concluded that consistent and significant efforts are required for raising the awareness level in Pakistan. For this purpose, it is evident to say that improvement in the understanding of employer branding concept in practice is equally important because exposition to both these concepts will go hand in hand. The depth, nature and clarity of research findings is certainly indicating a positive sign for raising this awareness among millennials more so because they already possess a basic level of understanding, and this study can capitalize on this already existing foundation. Two MNCs and one local telecom company (from the total of five telecom companies operating in Pakistan) were part of data collection process and millennials working in these companies have shared their opinion based on which findings are generated. This means that the reach of awareness will be considerably extensive and realistic as barriers have been identified which are restricting the awareness of millennials about CSR and employer branding. Third research objective has been addressed in this manner which was about creating awareness and understanding of the employer branding and environment drive CSR concepts.

It has been concluded that environmental CSR practices are not included in the CSR policies of the telecom employers in Pakistan and environment driven CSR initiatives or practices are few and far between which is not exhibiting a positive sign. Subsequently, in the absence of environmental CSR practices, the chances of influencing employer branding get obsolete. Moreover, the consideration of interplay between environmental CSR and employer branding is vague and perception about it is not aligned with its original essence across millennial employees.

Millennials are aware and understand the environment driven initiatives of government, and they are of the view that it is majorly the responsibility of government to care about the environment. Therefore, it has been concluded that environmental CSR practices are not influencing employer branding of telecom employers in Pakistan. This concluding remark is addressing the fourth research objective.

In terms of putting theory into practice, it has been concluded that stakeholder theory and organizational identity theory are not being adhered in the desired manner i.e., only moral and social identity has been found as intact across millennials of telecom sector in Pakistan. The efficiency, frequency and extensiveness of communication is not adequate across telecom employers in Pakistan due to which employees are not being engaged in CSR activities and have less exposure about employer branding concept in relation with CSR. Lastly, it has been concluded that the focus of telecom employers is solely customer oriented rather than a balance of customer, employee and environment. Employers are using social media platforms for communicating information about their business, services and packages about customers, and internal branding is not being pursued. Employee voice behaviour is not encouraged and exercised across telecom employers and are not communicated regularly about CSR activities which concludes that millennials do not have the confidence and belief that they can influence the decisions and CSR practices of their employers.

6.2 Contribution of Research

This research has multiple contributions to offer for the body of knowledge. A long-term perspective has been provided by this study because realistic and theoretically sound exposure has been offered by this study for millennial employees by presenting detailed insights about the interplay of CSR and employer branding. Below presented are some key contributions of this research categorized in distinct dimensions:

Theoretical and Empirical Contributions

A theoretical contribution is the identification that EU's CSR framework does not legally bound EU based MNCs operating in countries outside EU to implement the framework. Most stakeholders support an EU-wide legislative initiative regarding social and environmental due diligence, in order to level the playing field for companies across the EU (European Parliament, 2022). Therefore, the environmental CSR performance of MNCs based in EU countries cannot be evaluated on the basis of EU's CSR framework, however it only puts moral or ethical obligation, and it gives MNCs an element of discretion when operating in non-EU countries.

A key contribution is the limited application of stakeholder theory and organizational identity theory in the developing country context of Pakistan. In the presence of contextual factors, these theories are not being applied and yet the performance of telecom companies is commendable. In the developing country context, organizational performance is appearing as irrelevant and out of reach when the discussion is about the scope, application and effectiveness of CSR construct. The value system, norms, preferences, and socio-economic dimensions of developing countries can undermine the strengths of CSR concept.

Societal expectations and in particular expectations of millennial employees as stakeholders about CSR behaviours of telecom firms are low in Pakistan which indicates a contribution by clearly suggesting that cultural values, norms and preferences are dominant instead of millennials' characteristics which are widely identified as pro-environment. Theoretical understanding and identification of characteristics possessed by millennials in Pakistan needs to be investigated because as observed in this study, the characteristics of millennials are varying significantly in Pakistan which is a developing country context. Therefore, a contribution is the clarity achieved about not generalizing the characteristics of millennials.

A key empirical contribution is the clarity that telecom companies including MNCs in Pakistan have a different way that organizations usually regard towards environmental side of corporate social responsibility across developed world, and this has led to believe that CSR concept has not taken roots in the mindset of telecom companies with its complete essence.

Ignoring and paying considerably less attention towards environmental side of CSR in Pakistan where environmental damage is a concerning factor has led to a contribution that political, cultural and social system of Pakistan is restricting effective implementation of environmental CSR concept.

The possible reasons that might be playing a role in restricting the development of understanding for millennial employees in Pakistan have been identified in this study which indicates a contribution to research. This is so because given the characteristics of millennials, inclusion of MNCs in telecom sector and prevalence of environmental issues in Pakistan, it is quite unlikely to observe such results, therefore, it becomes a contribution to logically identify the factors causing these results.

Another key contribution is the awareness that characteristics of millennial employees in developing country context are primarily different from millennial employees' characteristics in developed country context due to which new construct of millennial characteristics is required for reliable application in developing countries.

Policy and Managerial Contributions

The decision-making of business leaders, managers and shareholders in telecom companies is not revolving around environment protection, rather they are focusing on business development, customer satisfaction and other elements of societal and community development. Ultimately, differentiating the developing country context from a developed country context in relation with the development and prevalence of CSR construct.

Despite of being a developing country, the government of Pakistan has shown keen interest and has led pro-environment project which has set examples for other countries i.e., Billion Tree Tsunami project. Therefore, a contribution for research is that even though MNCs are not practicing CSR framework proposed by EU and other reputed agencies, a developing country government is showing more environment orientation which means that willingness to perform and intent is the foremost requirement that needs to be measured or evaluated for developing CSR construct effectively.

The Government of Pakistan and the Ministry of Environment along with their agencies such as, PTA can integrate their policy and regulations in line with EU's CSR framework which will indirectly provide an opportunity to enforce MNCs operating in Pakistan for adhering to EU's CSR framework components.

Companies' activities on the environment and the society as a whole significantly affect citizens' lives. As a consequence, policymakers face the question of whether companies are to meet duties to prevent, identify, manage and mitigate any possible negative impact that they may cause on society as a whole (and thus human rights, health, environment and so on), including those impacts produced along their global supply chain. Therefore, a key policy contribution of this study is the question posed about the ineffective functioning of environment protection agencies and weak enforcement of Pakistan's environment protection law 1997.

Pakistan's Environmental Policy is based on participatory approach to achieving objectives of sustainable development through legally, administratively and technically sound institutions. However, a policy contribution of this study is indicating that Pakistan does not have sound institutions for ensuring the implementation of environmental policy devised at the government level. MNCs and local telecom companies in Pakistan are not adhering to the environment protection regulations and frameworks and are not communicating about their performance in this regard which reflects a weak link between theory and practice.

A key policy and managerial contribution are the awareness and adoption of global environment related initiatives by telecom companies. The UN Global Compact, in particular, supports companies in carrying on their businesses responsibly, by aligning their strategies and operations with the UN's Ten Principles on human rights, labour, environment and anti-corruption ("UN Guiding Principles"). It also supports companies in taking strategic actions that advance broader societal goals, such as the UN Sustainable Development Goals (UN 2030 agenda), focusing on collaboration and innovation. Such principles are derived from the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the ILO's Declaration on Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work, the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, and the UN's Convention Against Corruption.

Telecom companies especially MNCs operating in Pakistan needs to communicate and publish information about their adherence to these initiatives while functioning in Pakistan which is a developing country. The head office in country of origin of these MNCs will have to play a proactive role in this regard.

6.3 Directions for Future Research

Below presented are some future research directions that can potentially assist in understanding and exploring the interplay of CSR and employer branding in a developing country context:

- Three big players of the telecom industry operating in Pakistan are ignoring the environmental factor in their business activities, therefore it will be of interest to research the application and existence of environmental laws in Pakistan which can often shape the focus of businesses towards CSR. Moreover, a related research direction can be the interest to determine that what kind of motivations and reasons can actually encourage businesses especially telecom employers to take environment friendly practices in a developing country context. Given the serosity and extent of environmental issues prevailing in Pakistan can it be expected that employers especially MNCs operating in a developing country context are willing to contribute through CSR practices.
- It has been understood from the study findings that there exists a need to investigate the link between corporate reputation and CSR reporting as it was urged by (Colleoni, 2013; Michelon, 2011; Othman et al, 2011). Therefore, a key future research direction can be to conduct investigation on determining this link in the context of developing country Pakistan.
- Employee retention of telecom companies in Pakistan given these results can be of interest to research because a big question mark has been posed by this study results on the way employees make decision about their employer and how or to what extent telecom employers are able to retain millennial employees when employer branding is not functioning. Idea behind this future research direction is the argument that what kind of implications telecom employers are facing by not paying attention to CSR and employer branding.

- A key future research direction can focus on the question that what kind of impacts can be generated by COVID-19 in the long run for CSR construct in the developing country context. For example, research can be carried out in terms of opportunities and challenges both.
- How COVID-19 factor can implicate on shaping the understanding and perception of millennials about employer branding and about importance of CSR practices directed towards environment protection. This future research direction contains importance in the context of developing countries where resources and infrastructure are limited as compared to developed countries.
- How CSR construct can take a different direction and scope in the developing country context as compared to developed country context i.e., what are the ground realities and theoretical assumptions that makes CSR less effective and applicable across developing country context can potentially be a future research direction.
- It is necessary for the responsible businesses to realise that they need to work in tandem with other organizations to move the CSR agenda forward and a key future research direction can be to conduct studies for building a consensus on CSR agenda (with special focus on environment) in Pakistan so that a particular framework of CSR can be anticipated for governing the functioning of CSR in the country.
- Another future research direction can be about conducting a comparative analysis of the millennial employees working in developing country context and developed country context for understanding where the difference lies which is causing such significant variation in their behaviours and perceptions.

6.4 Limitations of Research

There are several potential limitations that this research study has faced. Below presented is the list of those limitations:

- The occurrence of COVID-19 crisis was a key limitation faced by this research study, because the process of data collection was halted amid COVID-19. Some responses were collected before the lockdown restrictions in Pakistan and some responses were collected after the lifting of lockdown restrictions.

Interview questions were improved and changed after pilot study and then after the occurrence of COVID-19, again it was modified. Moreover, to access the potential respondents became difficult due to COVID-19 and especially it was difficult to track and arrange interview meeting with respondents during the COVID-19 work routine.

- While interpreting the interview results, it was strongly felt by researcher that few more precise questions could have been included in the interviews for extracting some more insights. For example, information about any kind of invitation that employers had given to millennials about participating in CSR activities. However, this need was felt only after deeply understanding and interpreting the results which indicates limitation on the aspect of researcher's competence and experience.
- A rather basic level of understanding possessed by the millennial employees about the CSR and employer branding concept is a limitation of this study because this restricted the quality and depth of answers given by the respondents ultimately undermining the validity of the research findings.
- The competence and experience of the researcher might also have restricted the ability to construct precise and meaningful interview questions and especially the interpretation of results might have been subject to the researcher's bias. This can be a potential research limitation impacting on the reliability of the research findings and conclusion.
- Limited availability of empirical evidence and studies on the research problem under investigation was also a potential limitation because in the absence of relevant empirical evidence it becomes complex to generalize the findings and identify the commonalities. Moreover, it makes the data collection process difficult because no empirical support and guidance was available for constructing the data collection and analysis process.
- Various initiatives at international level, such as the ones adopted by the United Nations (UN), the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and the International Labour Organisation (ILO), highlight companies' duties to behave responsibly and respect human rights. Questions could have been asked about the awareness and adherence to these during data collection for gaining a precise perspective because information about these initiatives in the context of selected telecom companies was not found on their official websites, press releases and other reports.

6.5 Theoretical and Managerial Implications of Research

This research study has offered some theoretical and managerial implications which will be presented in this section:

- A key managerial implication is for the managerial staff of telecom and other sector employers regarding the importance of pursuing internal branding and especially by using social media platforms and networks. This is important because employee engagement can be improved by driving internal branding with the help of efficient, regular and clear communication. If millennial employees do not possess a sound understanding and opinion about CSR and employer branding, then it is a matter of concern for the future of the relevant organizations.
- Another managerial implication is to think about entering into partnerships and joint ventures with the government initiatives towards environment protection because millennial employees view it as important. The importance of individual and independent initiatives by employers is equally important, however when employers contribute towards national level cause then it increases the visibility and image of the brand because it reflects a collective effort. This way employer branding will get the boost and awareness across employees will also prevail.
- Managers can potentially start to pay attention towards their communication strategy across telecom companies because with sound communication strategy multiple benefits can be extracted by the employers including employee engagement, clarity of thought about employer, belongingness with employer, trust on employer and sense of being valued.
- A key theoretical implication is on the application and validation of the stakeholder and organizational identification theories in a developing country context. The way these theories have been ignored and not adhered raises a question mark about the need of these theories in developing country context.
- Characteristics of millennial employees shaped in the extant literature is primarily based in developed country context which does not necessarily represent the millennial employees in developing country context.

Therefore, a key theoretical implication is to treat and consider the characteristics of millennial employees from developing country distinct and different which means several theories and arguments cannot be applied in the developing country context. Therefore, managerial decisions have to be informed by this difference.

6.6 Recommendations

A set of recommendations have been presented below after considering the nature of research findings achieved and by considering the themes developed earlier and by considering the literature review findings:

- Lack of intent, and absence of a clear and consistent CSR strategy was observed on the part of telecom employers in Pakistan, therefore a key recommendation here is to develop and implement a clear strategy for pursuing CSR activities. Another step linked with this CSR strategy development is the formulation of a clear, coherent and comprehensive communication strategy for successfully and regularly reaching out to the employees. CSR communication and reporting has already gained significant attention in academia i.e., corporate annual reports and separate social reports are often advised and followed by companies around the world which is also a recommendation for telecom firms of Pakistan (Golob et al, 2013; Hackston and Milne, 1996).

Also, Du et al, (2010) stated that without a clear communication, no impact on stakeholders can be generated irrespective of the scale of CSR initiatives being undertaken by the company. Therefore, communication non-financial performance information has become imperative for company's own benefits because it leads to stakeholders' engagement. In terms of developing and exhibiting intent, it is suggested to facilitate managerial leadership a relevant training program so that they can develop a mindset compatible with the strategic CSR and communication implementation. International and national level online and offline training programs are available in this regard such as CIPD in the UK and Highly Keen Institute in Pakistan is offering relevant training programs.

Brunton et al, (2017) mentioned that organizations can influence and understand their employees in an improved manner with the help of an effective internal CSR communication, however it is suggested here to the telecom employers, to not misuse or deceive stakeholders with CSR information because it can lead to negative consequence as mentioned by (Zizka, 2017). This is important as few respondents mentioned that they think CSR is a marketing gimmick. Putting it in simple words, CSR communication should be reflecting CSR practices of the company i.e., both should align. For example, the managers should be told to walk their CSR talk i.e., “walk the talk” as a general rule which means practicing what they are preaching (Morsing and Spence, 2019; Crane & Golzer, 2018; Wickert et al, 2016).

- Leadership of the telecom companies in Pakistan needs to create a CSR policy and they need to show their commitment by doing so that a message is conveyed to the stakeholders especially employees. Setting environmental goals (about specific environmental issues of Pakistan) can be a feasible strategy in this regard (Marques, 2019). Being mindful as leadership of these companies is also important as ISO 26000 mentioned that ethics are linked with business performance and respecting the natural environment is at its core. Therefore, mindfulness as a skill is suggested to be developed by the management of telecom companies because ethics are linked to CSR ultimately (Marques, 2020). Khalique et al. (2015) suggested that internal stakeholders (employees) of the organizations learn their behaviour and attitudes through their leaders, which makes this recommendation desirable.
- Controlled and uncontrolled media channels have been categorized by Kim and Ferguson, (2014) which means telecom companies can differentiate and utilize these channels in line with their CSR strategy. For example, social media pages, website of the company, brochures, annual reports and newsletters are media channels controlled by the company, whereas, non-company social media platforms, blogs of industry experts, and news media are uncontrolled media.
- Telecom employers need to improve their knowledge base about the benefits and importance of having such employees who have social and moral identity and a well as organizational identification in relation to CSR construction.

In response to CSR practices of employers, their employees tend to exhibit creative work behaviours and CSR perception of employees is replicated in their views about the organizations (Gond et al, 2017; Nejati et al, 2021; Tafolli and Grabner-Kräuter, 2020).

Since, telecom companies are more business and customer focused, therefore it is important for them to know that ultimately CSR orientation will help their business cause as well. Consequently, telecom companies need to make sure that this improvement in knowledge is being transferred to their employees.

- Environmental awareness and education of the millennials holds critical importance and for addressing the root cause of low level of awareness identified, it is recommended for telecom employers especially MNCs to participate and initiate awareness programmes for young graduates in Pakistan. This way, millennials can avail much needed education about the importance of CSR and its implications for the society at large.
- It is suggested here that person-organization fit of telecom sector firms in Pakistan should be given importance and for this purpose the previous recommendation will be helpful. George et al, (2020); and Agnihotri and Bhattacharya, (2021) have emphasized on the importance of establishing person-organization fit for aligning the culture and mindset of employers and employees. With CSR and communication strategy alignment, it will be easy for the companies to achieve person-organization fit and will ultimately lead to positive employer branding.
- MNCs are dominant in the telecom sector of Pakistan, and they are suggested to play a proactive role in changing the corporate culture and mindset of employees towards CSR concept. Therefore, it is important for MNCs to integrate the original CSR construct and employer branding construct in their organizational culture in Pakistan for giving much needed exposure to the employees. This way experience gained by employees will assist in shaping their perception and views about the interplay of CSR and employer branding constructs in a developing country context.

Strategic CSR alliances have been undertaken by MNCs regularly such as, Intel, Google, Unilever and Nestle by pursuing shared value approach (Camilleri, 2017; European Union, 2016; Porter and Kramer, 2011). Organizations can achieve competitive advantage by effectively using their relationship with stakeholders and CSR practices is an optimal way of doing so (Bhattacharya et al. 2017; Olsen, 2017).

Therefore, it is recommended for the telecom companies in Pakistan especially the MNCs to pursue partnerships and collaborations with government and non-government agencies for driving their socially responsible image. It is kind of a long-term investment for gaining competitive advantage and for strengthening the strategic CSR approach (Camilleri, 2017).

- For generating brand supporting behaviours, it is recommended to engage in internal branding with the help of social media networks and platforms. Companies are already using Facebook and Instagram applications for communicating about services and products with customers.

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8.1 Appendices A: Transcripts

8.1.1 Respondent 1 (Company X)

Profile/Background of the Participant

1 You were born in the year 1984 or after 1984?

A: After 1984.

2 Which telecom company you are working in and for how long?

A: I am working in Compan X for 3 years.

3 What is the job role that you are performing, or you are intending to perform in telecom sector?

A: I am doing customer service job.

Importance and awareness of Environmental CSR

4. What do you understand by the term corporate social responsibility (CSR)?

A: Whatever good actions a company takes it summed up in CSR and I have seen some adverts of CSR by other companies.

5. To what extent do you think the environment friendly behaviours and practices (Corporate Social Responsibility) are important for employers and their employees?

A: Social responsibility empowers employees to leverage the corporate resources at their disposal to do good. Formal corporate social responsibility programs can boost employee morale and lead to greater productivity in the workforce. The importance should be given by telecom firms in our country to enhance the quality of business and improve the customer services.

6. Do you think employees as stakeholders can influence their employers towards behaving in an environment friendly manner?

A: We often get such chances where we can play our role in telling the company about what they are doing right and what they are doing wrong. So we can definitely use such chances to inform them and demand from them to take care about the environment when they are doing their business and making profits.

7. To what extent do you think the awareness about environmental CSR exists across your colleagues and telecom sector?

A: As per my observation the awareness of Environmental CSR exists in my colleagues and co-workers, but we still need a lot more and we together need to put extra milestones in environment side of CSR.

8. Do you think that ignoring environmental CSR by telecom firms in Pakistan affects their reputation as attractive employers?

A: As an employee I am not worried about these things so I cannot answer properly on this.

9. To what extent do you think environmental CSR practices can improve attractiveness of telecom companies as employers in Pakistan?

A: I think it does not improve much, as a graduate I am keen to get a job and I will not pay attention to this issue.

10. While applying for a new job or switching job roles, to what extent you consider the environmental CSR performance of the employer?

A: I can say this about their social activities but I have not done this specifically about the environment factor.

11. To what extent you get influenced by the environmental CSR related adverts and information shared by telecom companies?

A: I will honestly say that our company makes so many adverts and gives us so much information about services and packages after that I hardly pay attention to other information.

12. Do you review CSR policy of the employer while applying or switching jobs as one of the factors that influences your decision?

A: It depends because for my first job I did not review CSR policy, but when I switched my job I did had a look on CSR policy for the sake of information.

13. To the best of your knowledge, what practices your employer undertakes for addressing the environmental side of CSR?

A: I know for a fact that customers are offered with packages and facilities, but not the environment.

14. What methods and platforms your employer use for communicating their environmental CSR practices and performance?

A: Facebook and Instagram are the main communication methods of my company when they have to share new information.

15. To what extent eco-friendly office environment is important for you as an employee?

A: I personally think it as highly important because I have a tough work routine and a positive environment will definitely give me motivation.

16. Environment focused values and actions of your employer increases your social standing in the society?

A: I cannot say this with confidence because I would like this to happen but I do not think it happens in reality.

17. Do you think telecom sector employers need to improve their focus on environmental CSR policies for standing out as socially responsible employers?

A: Obviously it is their responsibility to have all kinds of policies, because it will give them benefit and it will give people some benefit.

18. Do you think telecom sector employers are fair and transparent in their CSR communication towards employees and other stakeholders?

A: There is a perception that companies mostly manipulate information when telling something to the customers and sometimes to the employees, there is some truth about this perception.

Importance and understanding of Employer Branding

This section covers the question number 18 to question number 24 of the interview and the responses given to these questions will now be interpreted and presented.

19. What do you understand by the term employer branding?

A: I think it is the effort of a company to project their name in front of employees so that employees prefer that brand for their work experience.

20. To what extent telecom sector employers are sharing information about their environmental CSR activities for potential and existing employees?

A: I remember last year the company shared some figures about their social work after which I do not think they have shared anything and they do not take our input anyway.

21. To what extent the environmental CSR information shared by telecom companies shapes your view about their attractiveness?

A: Even though I have not encountered any such information, but if I will, then I am not sure it will influence me or not.

22. A telecom company practicing environmental CSR allows you to relate with that company and develop an association with that company?

A: This applies only to the extent when a campaign is being run because during that period you feel that association which is natural to happen for me but it is temporary only.

23. Improved environmental CSR focus of your employer will make you stay with the firm for a longer period of time?

A: This is a difficult question to answer because I seriously want this to happen in reality but given the circumstances I might not stay solely because of this reason.

24. Internal communication of your employer about their CSR activities is clear and regular?

A: I would say it is not clearly communicated and it is not regular as well mainly because only selective meetings between management sometimes refer to CSR initiatives.

25. In your opinion what kind of CSR policies and methods of communication your employer can use for improving their employer branding and attractiveness?

A: I think social media platforms are working well for the company, however, I strongly believe that joining hands with any Government initiative will provide great benefits to the company itself.

26. Do you think COVID-19 crisis is an opportunity for employers to take environment driven CSR seriously for improving their attractiveness and for fighting this crisis?

A: It can be a factor for coming years because we do not know when it is going to end and when it will hit us back.

8.1.2 Respondent 2 (Company Y)

Profile/Background of the Participant

1. You were born in the year 1984 or after 1984?

A: After 1984

2. Which telecom company you are working in and for how long?

A: I am working in Compan Y for 2.5 years.

3. What is the job role that you are performing?

A: I am doing job as engineer.

Importance and awareness of Environmental CSR

4. Whatever good actions a company takes it summed up in CSR and I have seen some adverts of CSR by other companies.

A: I think this pretty much covers every social step that a company takes.

5. To what extent do you think the environment friendly behaviours and practices (Corporate Social Responsibility) are important for employers and their employees?

A: As employees we do have some responsibilities and I am sure that behaving well towards the environment is equally important for employers and employees.

6. Do you think employees as stakeholders can influence their employers towards behaving in an environment friendly manner?

A: I think in today's social media world we employees have some powers and we definitely can use this power for infleuencing our employers about their business acitivities to respect the natural environment conditions.

7. To what extent do you think the awareness about environmental CSR exists across your colleagues and telecom sector?

A: I think we do understand about the environmental issues and I have often had discussions with my colleagues about how green initiatives can be taken by our company for giving back to the natural environment around us because the government is giving it priority from last few years.

8. Do you think that ignoring environmental CSR by telecom firms in Pakistan affects their reputation as attractive employers?

A: I do not think this happens, we do not normally pay attention on this.

9. To what extent do you think environmental CSR practices can improve attractiveness of telecom companies as employers in Pakistan?

A: Reputation of employers in this industry are decent and people are getting jobs in telecom companies so this environmental issue is not important.

10. While applying for a new job or switching job roles, to what extent you consider the environmental CSR performance of the employer?

A: While I apply for a new job or switching job, I consider 40% of environmental CSR Performance of the employer.

11. To what extent you get influenced by the environmental CSR related adverts and information shared by telecom companies?

A: Sometimes I hear about initiatives of the company but this does not affect me as such.

12. Do you review CSR policy of the employer while applying or switching jobs as one of the factors that influences your decision?

A: I did not review it because for me it was not relevant and obviously my decision is based on other factors.

13. To the best of your knowledge, what practices your employer undertakes for addressing the environmental side of CSR?

A: I remember my company made an advert about their commitment to the environment protection, but frankly I have not seen anything in reality.

14. What methods and platforms your employer use for communicating their environmental CSR practices and performance?

A: Company uses their website and Facebook mostly for telling us about their different campaigns and activities.

15. To what extent eco-friendly office environment is important for you as an employee?

A: Yes, eco-friendly office environment is very important not only for me in fact for every employee this will increase the productivity up to 100%.

16. Environment focused values and actions of your employer increases your social standing in the society?

A: Yes, it does make me feel proud and confident.

17. Do you think telecom sector employers need to improve their focus on environmental CSR policies for standing out as socially responsible employers?

A: Definitely, it is a big requirement.

18. Do you think telecom sector employers are fair and transparent in their CSR communication towards employees and other stakeholders?

A: I do not think that employers are fair and transparent in their CSR communication towards stakeholders like any other big company in Pakistan.

Importance and understanding of Employer Branding

19. What do you understand by the term employer branding?

A: I think it is the effort of a company to project their name in front of employees so that employees prefer that brand for their work experience.

20. To what extent telecom sector employers are sharing information about their environmental CSR activities for potential and existing employees?

A: I have not seen any such information sharing which is about environment related activities

21. To what extent the environmental CSR information shared by telecom companies shapes your view about their attractiveness?

A: I think it can influence my view about that company but first it has to happen and I think companies should do it.

22. A telecom company practicing environmental CSR allows you to relate with that company and develop an association with that company?

A: I have had an experience in the past after which I do not take such activities seriously because I have understood that these are marketing gimmicks.

23. Improved environmental CSR focus of your employer will make you stay with the firm for a longer period of time?

A: This is an ideal situation we are talking about and given this situation I am not sure how I will react but at the present moment I think I will not stay.

24. Internal communication of your employer about their CSR activities is clear and regular?

A: Yes, in our formal and informal meetings with higher management, we are told about how the company is fulfilling CSR obligations.

25. In your opinion what kind of CSR policies and methods of communication your employer can use for improving their employer branding and attractiveness?

A: The company should proactively use social media platforms for running campaigns about changing weather or climate which is an international issue as well.

26. Do you think COVID-19 crisis is an opportunity for employers to take environment driven CSR seriously for improving their attractiveness and for fighting this crisis?

A: Government is fighting this issue properly and I do believe that companies should strictly follow guidelines of government to keep their brand attractive.

8.1.3 Respondent 3 (Company Z)

Profile/Background of the Participant

1 You were born in the year 1984 or after 1984?

A: In the year 1984.

2 Which telecom company you are working in and for how long?

A: I am working in Compan Z for 5 years.

3 What is the job role that you are performing, or you are intending to perform in telecom sector?

A: I am working as Operations Manager.

Importance and awareness of Environmental CSR

4. Whatever good actions a company takes it summed up in CSR and I have seen some adverts of CSR by other companies.

A: This term asks companies to spend money on the community around and try to improve the conditions of community and take care of surroundings.

5. To what extent do you think the environment friendly behaviours and practices (Corporate Social Responsibility) are important for employers and their employees?

A: I am not sure whether the environment friendly behaviours can be applied on us and how we can find time to do this when we already have strict work routines, but I think for employers it should be important.

6. Do you think employees as stakeholders can influence their employers towards behaving in an environment friendly manner?

A: It is the responsibility of the company to think about environment related issues and it is as if you are asking employees more than their capacity because I have not witnessed any such examples before and never heard of it before.

7. To what extent do you think the awareness about environmental CSR exists across your colleagues and telecom sector?

A: I only read it in the books during my studies and that was also not much, I have not heard about this concept in my colleagues but we know about it and in this industry I think people know about it but they do not implement it.

8. Do you think that ignoring environmental CSR by telecom firms in Pakistan affects their reputation as attractive employers?

A: I am not sure but I think it does affect negatively because when other companies are doing one thing and you are missing out on it then people do notice it.

9. To what extent do you think environmental CSR practices can improve attractiveness of telecom companies as employers in Pakistan?

A: No answer.

10. While applying for a new job or switching job roles, to what extent you consider the environmental CSR performance of the employer?

A: They only consider their professional growth when applying for jobs and two respondents considered job security as attractive point which they believed that company Z will provide them.

11. To what extent you get influenced by the environmental CSR related adverts and information shared by telecom companies?

A: I am too busy in my job, I have no time to think and read about this stuff.

12. Do you review CSR policy of the employer while applying or switching jobs as one of the factors that influences your decision?

A: No, I do not read company policies, I only see the job advert information.

13. To the best of your knowledge, what practices your employer undertakes for addressing the environmental side of CSR?

A: Yes, I think my company joined hands with a famous cold drink company and they did some activity about reusing of plastic.

14. What methods and platforms your employer use for communicating their environmental CSR practices and performance?

A: I think our company mostly uses own website when they have to share a story about performance or anything else.

15. To what extent eco-friendly office environment is important for you as an employee?

A: The weather conditions in our city are not good for most of the months and on top of it the work pressure and dealing with customers affects my mood, but this eco-friendly environment will definitely make me happy.

16. Environment focused values and actions of your employer increases your social standing in the society?

A: Brand name is enough I think which definitely makes my social standing increased.

17. Do you think telecom sector employers need to improve their focus on environmental CSR policies for standing out as socially responsible employers?

A: Yes in reality they should do it and should encourage other companies as well.

18. Do you think telecom sector employers are fair and transparent in their CSR communication towards employees and other stakeholders?

A: I think companies fear to loose their profits or sales and that's why they are not fair and transparent.

Importance and understanding of Employer Branding

19. What do you understand by the term employer branding?

A: This term is about showing the world that what kind of brand you are in a market and why you are better than others.

20. To what extent telecom sector employers are sharing information about their environmental CSR activities for potential and existing employees?

A: Our regional manager sometimes in meetings mentions about company's initiatives for the city, apart from this no formal sharing of information takes place in the company.

21. To what extent the environmental CSR information shared by telecom companies shapes your view about their attractiveness?

A: In my experience and knowledge I have not seen news or press release about environment related events so I cannot comment on it properly.

22. A telecom company practicing environmental CSR allows you to relate with that company and develop an association with that company?

A: I can say that if you see anything positive happening around you feel good about it and I can relate myself with that company doing any good to our environment”.

23. Improved environmental CSR focus of your employer will make you stay with the firm for a longer period of time?

A: If this happens this will definitely help me take decision about my stay with my employer because overall I am already satisfied with my employer”.

24. Internal communication of your employer about their CSR activities is clear and regular?

A: Yes in terms of annual reports we can say this happens because I have seen that CSR is talked about in these reports, but apart from annual publication of report, no internal communication happens.

25. In your opinion what kind of CSR policies and methods of communication your employer can use for improving their employer branding and attractiveness?

A: For improving employer branding, the company needs to focus on creating awareness about different social and environmental issues such as, water and food wastage, preserving and keeping trees/ plants.

26. Do you think COVID-19 crisis is an opportunity for employers to take environment driven CSR seriously for improving their attractiveness and for fighting this crisis?

A: If you are talking about following SOPs then yes companies should do it and make sure that SOPs are fulfilled by all the employees working in the company.